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Consumer understanding, perceptions, and behaviours relating to aquaculture and seafood consumption

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Executive Summary

It is estimated that 60% of Europeans “eat or buy fishery or aquaculture products at least once a month” (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2017). However, according to a 2022 EUMOFA report, whilst 10.41 million tonnes live weight equivalent (LWE) of fish and aquaculture products were consumed in the EU in 2020, approximately 6.16 million tonnes LWE were imported from outside the EU in the same year (EUMOFA, 2022) (pp. 26-28).

Aquaculture is widespread in Europe: of the 4.05 million tonnes LWE of seafood products produced in the EU in 2020, 1.09 million (26.9%) came from aquaculture (FAO, 2022) (p. xvi). However, farmed products remain less popular than wild ones in the EU. The FishEUTrust project aims to increase consumer trust in, and thus uptake of, EU aquaculture products by addressing two problems: a current lack of product traceability and transparency, and a lack of trust in aquaculture products. To address the latter problem, the aim of work package 2 (WP2) is to design and validate a tailored set of intervention strategies intended to increase consumers’ trust in and consumption of seafood products produced in the EU. FishEUTrust project partners can then use these intervention strategies to define and develop the most effective methods for promoting uptake of FishEUTrust products.

A key preliminary component of WP2 was to identify the factors that motivate consumers’ seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour, and to understand how those factors interact. The first WP2 task (task 2.1) was thus to conduct a review of existing evidence and information relating to the barriers to and drivers of seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour. This comprised two parts: a grey literature review and a scientific literature review. The findings from task 2.1 are discussed in detail in Part 1 of this report.

Following the literature reviews, interviews were carried out with stakeholder experts to validate the findings and clarify some concepts that were still unclear. The interviews were conducted with experts representing the quintuple helix of stakeholders (academia, civil society, environment, government, and industry), from five countries utilised as proxies for three European regions, namely Croatia and Slovenia (Mediterranean), Norway and Sweden (Central and North), and the UK (Atlantic).

In total, 73 grey literature and 70 scientific literature sources were utilised in the reviews. The grey literature sources were all published between 2009 and 2022, and the scientific literature sources between 2012 and 2022.

The grey literature review identified 59 barriers and drivers in total. The ten factors which were discussed by the highest proportion of grey literature sources (in descending order) were: 1) price; 2) health/nutrition and wellbeing; 3) sustainability concerns; 4) production method; 5) taste; 6) convenience; 7) safety concerns; 8) origin; 9) labelling/certification; and 10) jointly freshness and quality. Analysis of the frequency of mention of different barriers and drivers within the sources reiterated the importance of price, health-related factors, sustainability, freshness, production method, quality, and origin of the products.

The scientific literature review identified a large number of factors that influence consumers’ purchasing and consumption behaviour, particularly as regards aquaculture products. Price, origin, sustainability, taste, nutrition, healthiness (an attribute of the product) and health (an attribute related to the benefit to the consumer), information, freshness, and environmental impact were among the most commonly identified drivers. The main barriers to aquaculture uptake relate to its perceived environmental impact, concerns about animal welfare, perceived safety risks in the production processes, and the wide availability of wild-caught seafood as an alternative. The literature indicated that consumers associate a high number of positive attributes, including quality, safety, freshness, and taste, with wild-caught seafood. The attributes identified in the literature reviews were organised according to the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) framework.

Each source was carefully read, and a narrative account of the main themes, findings, and issues discussed in the sources was constructed, complemented by additional information from the stakeholder interviews. The barriers and drivers that received sufficient discussion within the literature for a dedicated consolidation and summary to be provided in this report were: price; health, nutrition, and wellbeing; self-efficacy and convenience; sensory characteristics; freshness; quality; safety; origin; labelling and certification; sustainability and environmental concerns; and production method. Consumer trust, a concept based upon many of these factors, is also covered.

The literature reviews and stakeholder interviews provided a diverse range of perspectives, but further information on a number of concepts was required, particularly consumers’ understanding of sustainability, freshness, and quality as they relate to seafood products, and how this understanding influences their purchasing behaviours. Although the reviews identified a general preference among consumers for wild-caught fish products, the reasons behind this preference remained hazy. Consumers’ knowledge and understanding of labelling and certification also needed further investigation, as did their knowledge and resulting perceptions of aquaculture.

The results of task 2.1 informed the development (in task 2.2) of a survey to collect primary data relating to the drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption in three European countries. The survey complemented and built upon existing knowledge (as identified in task 2.1) and the results were used to identify clusters of consumers characterised by their fish and seafood purchasing and consumption patterns.

The survey provided a comprehensive picture of seafood consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours in three European countries, representative of Northern Europe (Denmark), Southern Europe (Italy), and Central Europe (Slovenia). Initial analysis of the results provided information on respondents' demographics, purchasing preferences, and views on aquaculture. A cluster analysis was then performed on the survey results to identify distinct groups of consumers for whom intervention strategies will be tailored in tasks 2.3 and 2.4. The findings of task 2.2 are discussed in detail in Part 2 of this report.

Results of those activities provided a comprehensive picture of seafood consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours. The cluster analysis led to the identification of 13 distinct profiles of seafood consumers, four each in Denmark and Slovenia, and five in Italy, each with peculiar characteristics and patterns of choice related to fish-based products. While these 13 groups of consumers present distinctive aspects and declared behaviours, some common trends can be identified across countries.

Wild fish is preferred over farmed fish by the majority of consumer groups in the three countries. However, despite the preference for wild fish over farmed fish, several clusters presented a high share of respondents who stated they had no preference between the two types of products. This was registered for one group in Denmark, and three groups in Italy and Slovenia, and could be considered as a market opportunity for aquaculture products, since there is not a preclusion towards them in a large share of consumers.

Considering the drivers of and barriers to fish consumption, price is the most relevant item for all the clusters of consumers. This is observed in particular for groups who declared lower income levels, which are also the groups who generally declared a lower frequency of purchasing fish-based foods and a preference for frozen and tinned products. A partial exception to this trend is registered for Slovenia, where groups with lower income levels also declared some preferences for whole fish.

Besides price, the clusters of respondents identified in each of the three countries declared different drivers and barriers as relevant, but with several commonalities. In general, the origin of a product, while considered important, was not the main driver for consumption for the largest number of identified groups, this being true especially for Slovenia. On the other hand, freshness and quality were considered as crucial drivers for consumption by the majority of the clusters in all three countries.

Also, groups of consumers focusing on the health benefits of eating seafood can be observed. In particular, two 'healthy' groups were identified for Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia. These results show that the focus on health benefits generated by FishEUTrust solutions could represent an effective driver for their diffusion among relevant European consumers.

Finally, concerning knowledge and perception of fish products and aquaculture, wild fish is considered better tasting than farmed fish by a large share of consumer groups in the three countries. Farmed fish is considered better tasting than wild fish only by the wealthier cluster of Denmark, while only one cluster in Denmark and one in Italy do not perceive a difference in taste between the two products.

Consumers' self-declared levels of knowledge of aquaculture and aquaculture-related labels is often directly related to their education level: groups of more educated consumers self-declare the highest level of awareness about the topic. This self-perceived knowledge, however, is often followed by a high level of accordance with misleading statements on the negative impact of aquaculture: this can be observed in two consumer groups each in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia. On the other hand, one cluster each in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia present a medium or high education level and do not agree with the misleading statements on the negative impacts of aquaculture.

To a broader extent, the results show a general negative perception of aquaculture and its products. Hence, information actions and campaigns aiming at disseminating accurate information about the impact of aquaculture on the environment, and the quality and safety of its products, will be crucial for the success of FishEUTrust activities and solutions.

The detailed profiles of the consumers identified within the 13 clusters, together with the results from the literature reviews and stakeholder interviews, will provide a strong base from which to begin the development and testing of activities foreseen for tasks 2.3 and 2.4. In particular, the identification of profiles of consumers will be the base for the development of tailored real and virtual consumer experiences (task 2.3) that will test a set of solutions identified in FishEUTrust, and co-defined with project partners, with consumers matching the characteristics identified through the survey and the cluster analysis.

Results from the previous three tasks will then form the base for the design of tailored intervention strategies for the promotion of FishEUTrust solutions that will be developed in task 2.4. These strategies will increase consumer knowledge of, and demand for, FishEUTrust products, with the ultimate goal of encouraging increased consumption of sustainable and authentic EU aquaculture products.

Introduction

It is estimated that 60% of Europeans “eat or buy fishery or aquaculture products at least once a month” (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021). However, according to a 2022 report issued by the European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA), whilst 10.41 million tonnes live weight equivalent (LWE) of fish and aquaculture products were consumed in the EU in 2020, approximately 6.16 million tonnes LWE were imported from outside the EU in the same year (EUMOFA, 2022) (pp. 26-28). Although it is a major seafood producer (producing 4.05 million tonnes LWE of seafood products in 2020), the EU is also the world’s largest importer of seafood; China, the next largest importer, imported 5.80 million tonnes LWE in 2020 (EUMOFA, 2022) (p. 26).

It is projected that between 2020 and 2030 there will be a “15 percent increase in aquatic food consumption”, and it is expected that seafood will thus “provide a larger proportion of humanity’s nutritious food requirements” (FAO, 2022) (p. xxi). However, the depletion of fishery sources caused by, among other things, “overfishing, pollution, [and] poor management” means there is a need for more sustainable sources of seafood produce to be developed. Aquaculture is an important source of seafood products, and it is set to become even more so in the future. However, a report from the FAO states that, while “[a]quaculture has great potential to feed ... the world’s growing population,” it must become more sustainable: “Sustainable aquaculture development remains critical to supply the growing demand for aquatic foods” (FAO, 2022) (p. xvi).

Aquaculture is widespread in Europe: of the 4.05 million tonnes LWE of seafood products produced in the EU in 2020, 1.09 million (26.9%) came from aquaculture (FAO, 2022) (p. xvi). However, farmed products remain less popular than wild ones in the EU. When asked about their preference for wild or farmed seafood, 32% of respondents in a Eurobarometer survey indicated they prefer wild products, while only 7% preferred farmed products. Although this may initially seem conclusive, a further 30% stated they have no preference, and 15% said they did not know if the products they purchase are wild-caught or farmed. The remaining 16% said their decision depends on the type of product they are buying (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021) (p. 73). There is thus an opportunity to encourage further uptake of aquaculture products among those who have no preference, those who do not know if what they currently buy is wild-caught or farmed, and those who base purchasing decisions upon the type of product they are buying.

To make the EU aquaculture industry more sustainable, it is vital that consumers purchase the seafood products it produces. The FishEUTrust project aims to increase consumer trust in, and thus uptake of, EU aquaculture products by addressing two problems: a current lack of product traceability and transparency, and a lack of trust in aquaculture products. It is not always easy to identify if a product was made in the EU or imported, and consumers are generally faced with seafood of uncertain origin, with little information about the fishing and production methods used (gear, feed, welfare, processing, and transport), adding to the existing lack of trust, especially regarding farmed seafood.

Consumers surveyed by Eurobarometer indicated that, after appearance and cost, a product's origin is the third most important factor to them when making seafood purchasing decisions, suggesting that transparency and traceability are important factors (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021) (p. 66). It is a central goal of FishEUTrust to ensure seafood produce from European and local sources is authenticated as such. The project will develop innovative solutions, combining smart control systems for safety and quality, an advanced suite of tools integrating microbiome, genetic and stable isotope approaches and advanced digital technologies/solutions to ensure quality, safety, and traceability in the seafood supply chain. However, the development of such innovations alone will not be sufficient to drive behaviour change in consumers, a process which is notoriously challenging. Through the project’s work package 2 (WP2), a tailored set of intervention strategies to stimulate behavioural change, increase consumer trust and uptake, and promote FishEUTrust’s products and solutions will be developed.

Work package 2

The overall aim of FishEUTrust’s WP2 is to design and validate a tailored set of intervention strategies intended to increase consumers’ trust in and consumption of seafood products produced in the EU. This in turn will enable the project’s partners to define and develop the most effective strategies for promoting uptake of FishEUTrust products.

WP2 consists of four tasks which were developed to achieve this objective. Task 2.1 used literature reviews and stakeholder interviews to identify the drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption in Europe. Task 2.2 built on task 2.1, focusing on identifying clusters of consumers according to their stated seafood preferences, purchasing choices, and knowledge. Using the knowledge gained in task 2.2, task 2.3 will assess consumers’ awareness and acceptance of new innovations through evaluation of their decision-making processes and their sensory and hedonistic analyses of new products. The results of task 2.3 will help define the characteristics of products and innovations that are most appealing to different target consumer clusters. Task 2.4 will then draw on outputs from the previous three tasks to define the most effective intervention strategies that will increase consumer knowledge of and demand for FishEUTrust products.

This report presents the activities involved in carrying out task 2.1 and task 2.2, and the results obtained.

Part 1. Task 2.1 Mapping consumer expectations to identify key characteristics and behavioural drivers across EU countries

1. Overview of task 2.1

A key first step in WP2 was to identify the factors that influence consumers' seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour, and endeavour to understand the interactions between these factors. Thus, task 2.1 was to conduct a review of existing evidence and information relating to the drivers of and barriers to seafood purchasing and consumption. This comprised three parts: a grey literature review; a scientific literature review; and interviews with relevant stakeholders. The reviews enabled the barriers and drivers observed in previous research and analysis to be identified, and an examination of evidence relating to their relative effects to be carried out. The identified factors were then organised according to the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework of consumer behaviour to help identify the most suitable ways to promote sustainable seafood consumption patterns among consumers.

The literature reviews were followed by a series of stakeholder interviews with the aim of validating the review findings and clarifying some concepts which remained unclear. The interviews took place in five countries utilised as proxies for three focal European regions: Croatia and Slovenia (Mediterranean); Norway and Sweden (Central and North); and the UK (Atlantic). Experts representing the quintuple helix of stakeholders (academia, civil society, environment, government, and industry) were interviewed.

Part 1 of this deliverable presents the findings from task 2.1. After a section on the methodology, there is an overview of the main drivers and barriers identified, followed by an in-depth discussion of those that feature most prominently in the literature. Additional information gathered during the stakeholder interviews is included in the discussion of the relevant factor. Finally, conclusions from task 2.1 are presented along with their relevance to task 2.2.

2. Methodology

2.1 Grey literature review

The grey literature review comprised two parts, a manual search for relevant sources (performed by WRG), and an automated literature search tool (designed and developed by BELIT) which was used to validate the manual search and identify any additional sources not already included in the review.

2.1.1 Manual search methodology

To identify the grey literature to use in this review the first step was to generate search terms, which were comprised of relevant search words. In total ten relevant search words were identified (see *Table 1*). These terms naturally fell into three categories: four of the terms relate to the products of interest (i.e., what consumers purchase and/or consume); four relate to consumers' behaviour concerning those products; and two relate to how consumers' behaviours are influenced with regards to purchasing/consuming those products.

To create a single search term one word from each of the three categories was needed (e.g., 'fish consumption driver'; 'fish perception barrier'). Any combination of search words from fewer than three categories resulted in a search term which was too broad and unlikely to generate relevant results (e.g., 'fish consumption' or 'fish perception'). Each search word in each category was combined with each of the search words in the other two categories to generate a total of 32 search terms (4 x 4 x 2).

Table 1 Categorised search terms used

Product term	Behaviour term	Influencing term
Fish	Consumption	Driver
Seafood	Perception	Barrier
Aquaculture	Behaviour	
Shellfish	Purchase	

A Google search was carried out using each of the 32 search terms and the first ten pages of results were examined for sources of relevance. It was established that ten pages of results were suitable by conducting several trials in which very few relevant results were identified after the eighth page. During this initial search step, all results of potential interest were recorded, yielding 231 results.

Each source was then reviewed in detail and a set of inclusion/exclusion criteria applied to ensure that the final set of sources included in the literature review were directly relevant. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are detailed in *Table 2*.

Whilst the focus of FishEU Trust is on seafood produced via aquaculture, sources relating to both wild-caught and farmed seafood were included. This was necessary as many sources do not differentiate based on production method. It was also determined from the literature that production method is a key factor which drives purchasing decisions for many consumers and is therefore an important characteristic to understand. Furthermore, many consumers appear to be unsure what the difference is between seafood produced using the different methods. For these consumers, and for those who are unaware that there is a difference, it is important to understand what does drive or prevent purchase and consumption if not production method. Including only aquaculture-specific sources would have resulted in significantly less grey literature to review and, thus, less insight.

Table 2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria used to select grey literature sources

Inclusion	Exclusion
Must contain information about drivers of or barriers to consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviour	Must not be solely about consumer purchasing trends
Must contain information specifically about fish and/or seafood	Must not contain only information about general food purchasing and consumption behaviour
Can be relevant to wild-caught fish and/or seafood or that produced via aquaculture	Must not be specific to plant-based fish and seafood alternatives or cultivated fish/seafood (i.e., 'lab-grown')
Must be a grey literature source (defined as any source which is not an academic journal article)	Must not be an academic journal article
Sources pertaining to all geographic areas (countries, regions, continents, etc) to be included	

Following a careful sift applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 73 sources remained. An Excel spreadsheet was used to record the name of the source, the year of publication, the type of source (e.g., report, online or magazine article, white paper), the author type, and the geographic area(s) that each source related to (see Appendix 1 for the full list).

Each source was read carefully, and a three-component analysis process was utilised:

- 1) Text from each source pertaining to barriers to and/or drivers of fish and/or seafood purchase and/or consumption was copied from the source and saved in a .txt file. These files were used to produce a word cloud (section 3.2.1).
- 2) The same text was used to construct a narrative description of the grey literature (forming part of the content of section 3.3).
- 3) All the barriers and drivers mentioned across all the sources were recorded. For each source, a record was kept of the barriers and drivers referred to. This provided a simple record of how many sources of each type, relevant to each geographic area, contained mention of each barrier and driver.

2.1.2 Automated search methodology

The manual grey literature search was augmented by a custom developed automatised literature review tool (web/document scraper) in the key workflow steps of discovery, systematisation, mapping and storing relevant sources and results. Following testing and refinement, the Literature Review Tool was used to find additional grey literature sources. *Figure 1* depicts the automated grey literature search process.

Figure 1 Review method workflow supported by the web-scraping FishEUTrust Literature Review Tool, with listed key features of the Tool (in lavender blue and yellow areas) supporting each workflow step (in green frames)

The main search engine used by the Literature Review Tool was Google, although other search engines with a lower bias were considered and can be supported. The method workflow had three main steps:

- 1) Useful source websites were found based on the search terms defined in the queries.
- 2) Specific useful articles and other grey literature sources were found on the identified websites.
- 3) Occurrences of specific query search terms were found in the content of the most relevant documents, and additional potentially relevant sources, by performing a full text search. A score was given for relevance and relevant terms were highlighted.

The initial terms and queries for the keyword search were derived using the same approach as the manual search of combining at least one product domain term, one behavioural term, and one influencing term. Sites that received a term appearance score of 7 out of 10 or above were sifted using additional, more specific, keywords in any of the three relevant categories. Not only were more specific terms used but also antonyms of the keywords. This approach enabled the search results to be narrowed down so only the most focused results were included.

The most successful queries using additional search terms were introduced into the behavioural and influencing term categories, while the product term category showed similar results without refinement. *Table 3* shows the additional behavioural and influencing search terms used.

Table 3 Categories added to the automatised grey literature review

Behavioural term	Influencing term
Purchasing*	Factor
Attitude	Trigger
Buy	

*In addition to the already existing term 'Purchase'

2.1.3 Limitations of the methodology

The searches were conducted only in English. Thus, all of the sources reviewed were also in English. Whilst this represents a limitation of the review, many of the sources nevertheless discussed drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption in non-English speaking countries; in fact, just 25% of the sources with a European focus concerned only the UK or Ireland. Furthermore, annex 1 of the *EU Consumer Habits Regarding Fishery and Aquaculture Products* report detailed the work carried out compiling, listing, examining, and summarising existing studies on consumer habits in relation to seafood consumption in the (at the time) 28 EU member states (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016). This work included studies conducted and reported in countries' own languages.

Only the UK English spelling of behaviour was used when conducting the searches (as opposed to the American English spelling – ‘behavior’). This was deemed appropriate given the focus of FishEUTrust on the European market. Sources from outside Europe were utilised to provide additional relevant information, rather than as the primary focus of this report.

The sole use of Google as the search engine of choice may have been a limiting factor in the identification of sources. Search engine results are often inherently biased as a result of search engine optimisation techniques, the search history of users, and the algorithms used to determine the most relevant results to show. Google was chosen as it is the most-used search engine (Muller & Moz, 2019), and its algorithm design “prioritizes content that seems to be the most helpful” (Haynes, 2022). Google also returns results on discrete pages, rather than on one continuous page of results (as search engines such as DuckDuckGo do), thereby enabling a defined cut-off point for the screening of results (page 10 of returned results).

2.1.4 Terminology

The terms ‘barrier’ and ‘driver’ are used to refer to factors which influence consumers’ purchasing and consumption behaviour. The term ‘factor’ is also used as a neutral synonym.

During the automated searches, all the keywords were unified from plural to singular, e.g., ‘drivers’ to ‘driver’, as it has been observed that when singular words are used, search results also include most of those same words in plural.

Whilst conducting the review, it was noted that there are two main types of drivers and barriers: those that promote or prevent people from purchasing and consuming any type of fish and seafood; and those that promote or prevent the purchasing and consumption of specific species of fish and seafood. Individual drivers and barriers can often serve in both capacities. For example, a perceived high price of seafood in general compared to meat might act as a barrier to the purchase of any seafood product. Equally, price might act as a barrier to purchases of a comparatively expensive species of seafood, and a driver for the purchase of an alternative, comparatively cheap species. These two classes of drivers and barriers are not clearly distinguished in the grey literature and are often discussed interchangeably; thus, it was not always possible to differentiate between them.

2.2 Scientific literature review

The scientific literature review (led by REDINN) was conducted through a search on Web of Science (WoS), an open-access repository which allows downloading of publicly available information on scientific papers, including title, keywords, abstract, journal name, and publication date. For this research, only the title, keywords, and abstract were considered. The analysis included only those papers published in the 10 years between 2012 and 2022, and collected through the search string “((seafood OR fish) AND (“farmed fish” OR aquaculture OR “fresh water”) AND consum* AND (perception OR behaviour OR purchas* OR intention* OR driver* OR attitud* OR determin*))”. The resulting dataset included 653 papers. Due to the number of papers published that discussed production method, and more specifically aquaculture and consumers’ attitudes towards it, the scientific literature review focused on those sources related to farmed seafood.

To select the most relevant papers, a collaborative systematic analysis was conducted on the titles, keywords, and abstracts of the 653 papers, using a set of exclusion criteria. Papers were excluded from further analysis if they presented:

- A wrong outcome: an outcome not related to individual behaviour or a synonym thereof, such as enabler, factor, lever, push, trigger, motivation
- The wrong study design
- The wrong target population
- A duplication
- Not enough information
- The wrong publication type
- Collective behaviour
- A focus only on wild fish
- The wrong scope of research

The presence of one or more exclusion criteria was determined through a collaborative review of the 653 papers conducted by six researchers from REDINN, UNIBO, and WRG using the web platform Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai>), a tool designed for collective review and categorisation of documents. Each paper was screened by at least three researchers and the decision on whether to include it in further analysis was taken by majority. After this screening, 544 papers had been excluded from the review. A further analysis resulted in an additional 39 papers being excluded for ‘wrong outcome’.

The in-depth analysis of the remaining 70 scientific papers allowed the attributes that drive consumer behaviour regarding the purchase of fish and seafood products to be identified. Copies of all the papers to be included in the analysis were obtained and divided between the six researchers for careful reading. The researchers completed an Excel sheet for their papers listing author names and details of the studies conducted, including the drivers and barriers mentioned in each. These drivers and barriers were then allocated to one of the three MOA framework categories (see section 2.2.2 and section 3.2.3). Appendix 2 lists all the papers analysed in the scientific literature review with details about the studies performed.

2.2.1 Limitations of the methodology

A limitation of this method of analysis was that it generated a high number of mentions of most of the factors identified as drivers and barriers, but not all of them could be discussed fully in the literature, making it difficult to understand the extent of their influence on consumers' decisions.

It must be noted that most of the studies used in the literature review did not clearly label the factors that influence consumer decisions as drivers or barriers. The interpretation of the results of the studies and the discussion presented by the authors were used by the FishEUTrust researchers to classify the identified factors as either drivers or barriers.

2.2.2 The Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework

As mentioned above, the attributes identified in the literature review were organised according to the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) framework (for examples of the model and its application to sustainable food consumption, see (Cornish, et al., 2019) and (Michie, et al., 2011). Jackson writes that "The important structural feature of the MOA model is its attempt to integrate motivation, habitual and contextual factors into a single model of pro-environmental behaviour" (Jackson, 2005) (p. 97). In the context of FishEUTrust, this form of model-based research can provide valuable insights into the underlying factors that influence consumer behaviour regarding sustainable seafood purchasing, leading to the development of effective interventions and policies that can promote sustainable consumption patterns within the EU.

The Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework is, as its name suggests, comprised of three components, outlined below using the definitions given by (Michie, et al., 2011).

Motivation – "Motivation is defined as all those brain processes that energize and direct behaviour, not just goals and conscious decision-making. It includes habitual processes, emotional responding, as well as analytical decision-making."

Opportunity – "Opportunity is defined as all the factors that lie outside the individual that make the behaviour possible or prompt it."

Ability/Capability – "Capability is defined as the individual's psychological and physical capacity to engage in the activity concerned. It includes having the necessary knowledge and skills."

2.3 Stakeholder interviews

Online interviews were conducted with representatives of the quintuple helix of stakeholders in three geographical areas. In the context of FishEUTrust, the quintuple helix is a stakeholder mapping model comprising the five stakeholder types needed to increase consumer trust in and uptake of European aquaculture produce: academic institutes, seafood production industry actors, government agencies, natural environment agencies, and civil society representatives. This approach, rather than interviewing consumers directly, was chosen for the contact it allowed with the stakeholders who will be directly involved in project activities, and because it provides a high-level perspective on topics.

Following the geographical coverage of the project across three different regions of Europe, the stakeholder sample consisted primarily of representatives from Norway (Central and North), the UK (Atlantic), and Croatia (Mediterranean). Where stakeholders in one of these countries were not available for interview, alternative interviewees of a similar nature were sought; the Slovenian Consumer Board was approached in place of a Croatian civil society representative, and WWF Sweden instead of a Norwegian environmental agency.

The interview guide (see Appendix 3) was developed by members of REDINN and WRG. Interviews were conducted by researchers from NORCE (stakeholders in the UK, Norway, and Sweden) and Bugenvila (stakeholders in Croatia and Slovenia). Each interview lasted approximately one hour. The interviews had a semi-structured nature, with interviewers following the questions outlined in the interview guide yet allowing space for issues of interest to be explored in greater depth.

The interview guide included questions on a range of topics related to the drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption, along with some related concepts that were identified during the literature reviews as needing further clarification. During the interviews, the following themes were explored:

- Consumer perceptions of aquaculture
- Freshness, quality, and safety attributes
- Sustainability
- Consumer trust in seafood products
- Labelling of seafood products

2.3.1 Ethics compliance

To ensure compliance with the EU's ethical guidelines (Regulation 2016/679) and to promote the highest standards of ethical research, the interview process included a comprehensive set of steps that addressed the issues of confidentiality, informed consent, and data protection. Steps taken included:

- Providing participants with a clear description of the purpose of the study, the parties involved, and the reason for their invitation to interview.
- Informing participants of their right to not participate.
- Informing participants of their right to withdraw at any time during the study.
- Providing participants with an information sheet detailing the data protection protocols and an agreed consent form prior to the interview.
- Confidential treatment of any personal data provided by participants.

These measures were implemented to protect the rights of the participants, uphold ethical research standards, and ensure the integrity and quality of the findings.

3. Findings

3.1 Sources

In total, 73 grey literature and 70 scientific literature sources were utilised in the reviews. The grey literature sources were all published between 2009 and 2022, and the scientific literature sources between 2012 and 2022. The geographic focus of these sources is detailed in *Table 4*. Complete lists of the sources used in both literature reviews can be found in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2. A full discussion of all the findings is below.

Table 4 Geographic areas represented within the grey and scientific literature and the number of sources pertaining to each

Geographic area	Number of grey sources	Number of scientific sources
International (two or more countries on two or more continents)	22	3
Africa	3	0
Asia	1	18
Australasia	4	0
Europe (including sources relevant to only one country or more than one country within Europe)	24	36
North America	18	12
South America, including the Caribbean	1	1
Total	73	70

14 interviews were completed with stakeholders representing the quintuple helix in three regions. *Table 5* presents an overview of the stakeholders interviewed. It should be noted that the civil society stakeholders interviewed in Norway and the UK do not fit the traditional definition of the term. However, Seafood Norway often engages consumers in their research, actively seeking their perspective on the seafood industry. Likewise, SAIC connects with a range of stakeholders in its work and its objectives align with the goals of more traditional civil society organisations in promoting sustainability and societal benefits. It was not possible to complete an interview with a governmental stakeholder from the UK due to conflicting schedules and issues of timing, so it was decided to proceed with the analysis without this interview.

Table 5 Interviewed stakeholders

Stakeholder	Norway	The UK	Croatia
Academic	University of Stavanger	James Hutton Institute	University of Dubrovnik
Civil society	Seafood Norway	Sustainable Aquaculture Innovation Centre (SAIC)	Slovenian Consumer Board

Environmental	WWF Sweden	OpenSeas UK	Greenpeace Croatia
Governmental	Directorate of Fisheries	-	Ministry of Agriculture Aquaculture Department
Seafood industry	Lerøy Seafood	Salmon Scotland	Amfora Dubrovnik

3.2 Drivers and barriers identified

3.2.1 Drivers and barriers identified in the grey literature review

The grey literature review identified 59 barriers and drivers in total. *Figure 2* shows all the barriers and drivers identified alongside the percentage of the sources that included mention of each. It should be noted that *Figure 2* does not necessarily provide an indication of which drivers and barriers are the most important or relevant to consumers; it simply provides one indication of how much each barrier/driver is discussed within the grey literature.

The ten factors which were discussed by the highest proportion of grey literature sources (in descending order) were: 1) price; 2) health/nutrition and wellbeing; 3) sustainability concerns; 4) production method; 5) taste; 6) convenience; 7) safety concerns; 8) origin; 9) labelling/certification; and 10) jointly freshness and quality.

Figure 2 Percentage of total grey literature sources which mentioned each barrier/driver (total number of sources across all geographic areas = 73)

An alternative indication of how much each barrier and driver was discussed in the grey literature is seen in *Figure 3*. The word cloud provides an illustration of the relative frequency with which individual words (including many of the barriers and drivers) were used across all the sources. To produce this word cloud the following words were removed as they appeared very frequently within the literature but were uninformative for the purposes of the word cloud: 'fish', 'seafood', 'consumers', 'consumed', 'consumption', 'survey', 'respondents', 'purchase', 'mentioned', 'also', 'important', 'products', 'et', and 'al'.

Figure 4 Word cloud illustrating frequency of occurrence of drivers of sustainable fish and seafood consumption within the scientific literature reviewed

As can be seen from *Figure 4*, price, origin, sustainability, taste, nutrition, healthiness (an attribute of the product) and health (an attribute related to the benefit to the consumer), information, freshness, and environmental impact are among the most commonly identified drivers. All the identified drivers reflect how consumers perceive attributes as related to the products themselves, to the self-perceived benefits to and capabilities of the consumer, and to the overall positioning of the aquaculture industry as regards its impacts and benefits. The price of farmed fish and seafood, as can be seen from the size of the word 'price' in the word cloud, is the main driver of acceptance of farmed products because of the perception of affordability and value for money that is attributed to farmed seafood in comparison to wild-caught.

Figure 5 Word cloud illustrating frequency of occurrence of barriers to sustainable fish and seafood consumption within the scientific literature reviewed

Figure 5 shows that the main barriers to aquaculture uptake relate to its perceived environmental impact, concerns about animal welfare, perceived safety risks in the production processes, and the wide availability of wild-caught seafood as an alternative. The literature indicated that consumers associate a high number of positive attributes, including quality, safety, freshness, and taste, with wild-caught seafood. This association suggests the presence among consumers of not only more positive feelings about wild seafood, but accompanying negative feelings towards farmed seafood, which is perceived as being inferior.

3.2.3 Drivers and barriers placed within the MOA framework

As can be seen from *Figure 2*, *Figure 3*, *Figure 4*, and *Figure 5*, many of the factors that appear to have the most influence over consumers' seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour overlapped between the two literature reviews. Of the top ten factors identified in the grey literature review, eight were also among the most commonly mentioned factors in the scientific literature (price, health/nutrition, sustainability, production method, taste, safety concerns, origin, and freshness).

For a further analysis of the factors, they were sorted into the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework according to how they influence consumer behaviour. In the initial analysis of the papers, the number of factors identified was found to be too high to allow for a coherent evaluation of their influence on consumer behaviour. Therefore, one of the researchers scrutinised the factors based on how they were defined, and categorised them according to theme. 18 categories of barrier and driver were identified, encompassing the various factors as shown in *Figure 6*.

Figure 6 Attributes for sustainable fish and seafood consumption according to the MOA framework

The drivers and barriers identified during the literature review that relate to the motivation behind consumers' seafood consumption can be categorised as animal welfare concerns, environmental factors, socio-economic impacts, status and lifestyle, production process, and trust. In this context, motivation encompasses those factors that relate to an individual's behaviour with regards to seafood (especially farmed seafood) purchase and consumption.

The main categories identified with regards to opportunity were origin, availability, price, product presentation, place of purchase, and quality. Opportunity refers here to the presence of the precise set of circumstances that favour easy and affordable access to sustainably sourced seafood, with a focus on seafood from aquaculture.

Finally, the main categories linked to ability were sensory characteristics, habits, place of eating, health and nutrition, self-efficacy, and knowledge derived from product information given at the point of purchase, including labelling, branding, and certifications. Ability in this case concerns the capacity of the consumer to select, purchase, prepare, and consume seafood, particularly that from aquaculture.

A full discussion of the main drivers and barriers identified in the literature reviews, and how they are perceived to influence consumers' seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour is presented in section 3.3.

3.2.4 Validation of drivers and barriers with stakeholder interviews

The literature reviews provided a wealth of information about the factors which influence consumers' purchasing and consumption of seafood. Significant headway was made in identifying the most important factors to consumers and starting to understand both the complex ways in which their effects differ across different consumer groups and the ways in which they interact with one another. However, a number of areas were highlighted where further knowledge was needed in order to obtain the level of understanding required.

Although important barriers and drivers were identified, clarity was needed regarding the definition and meaning ascribed to some of them by consumers. This would, in turn, help researchers to identify the best means to encourage increased consumption of sustainable farmed seafood. The concepts of freshness, quality, safety, and sustainability remained ill-defined following the literature reviews; although all clearly act as factors in consumers' purchasing decisions, consumers' definitions of them remained somewhat nebulous. In addition, the extent to which consumers understand and rely on labelling and certification was unclear.

It was also hard to determine from the literature reviewed if consumers fully understand what different seafood production methods exist, and how their level of understanding of these methods influences their purchasing and consumption behaviour. The reviews clearly showed a discrepancy between consumers' knowledge about aquaculture and its actual benefits and drawbacks.

Finally, trust was found to be a paramount factor in consumers' decision-making. Consumer trust in a product is influenced to some extent by most of the barriers and drivers discussed in section 3.3, especially when there is a perception that consuming seafood products may carry health risks. Trust-related critical points were observed in consumers' relations with farmed fish suppliers, regulatory organisations, and commercial actors. Further investigation was required to address critical aspects of the inevitable touch points between consumers and the varied actors in the aquaculture supply chain.

These knowledge gaps were addressed initially through a series of stakeholder interviews with actors representing the quintuple helix of stakeholders as they pertain to the FishEUTrust project, and further in the consumer survey that formed part of task 2.2 (see Part 2).

The stakeholder representatives interviewed provided diverse perspectives on these topics, resulting in a range of opinions. While some themes and concepts were agreed upon, stakeholder views on several points exhibited significant disparities. Findings from the stakeholder interviews are discussed below in section 3.3.

3.3 Discussion of the identified drivers and barriers

Due to space restrictions, it is not possible to discuss every barrier and driver that was identified as having an effect on consumers' seafood purchasing behaviours. A selection of those factors that were most commonly mentioned in the literature (both grey and scientific) is presented here. Where further information was obtained during the stakeholder interviews, this is also included in the discussion of the relevant factor.

3.3.1 Price

Both literature reviews found that price is a key factor which influences seafood purchasing. High price most commonly acts as a barrier to purchase whilst promotions and offers serve to encourage it (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)). Numerous sources described the effects of price on consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours. In research conducted in the UK it was found that price was a major barrier to fish consumption: 46% of the adults surveyed stated that the cost of fish was a barrier to eating it (Banrie, 2012). Murray et al. found, in a survey of consumers in British Columbia, Canada, that 41% strongly disagreed with the statement that seafood was inexpensive (Murray, et al., 2017). In the Norwegian Seafood Council's survey of French consumers, it was found that the single most important reason given for why children don't eat more fish is that the parents think it's too expensive (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016). According to EUMOFA research 68% of consumers stated that they would increase consumption if prices were lower. Price levels, product assortment, and promotional strategies were given as the main external factors which encourage consumers to purchase more fishery and aquaculture products (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2017).

The price of seafood commonly does not act as a barrier or driver in isolation; its relative price compared to other protein sources also appears to drive purchasing behaviour (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Belchior & Boteler, 2016), (San Juan & Dainelis, 2015)). For example, fish and seafood in Japan must compete with cheaper livestock products that are available (Kitano & Yamamoto, 2020). However, farmed seafood was often seen as more affordable than its wild counterpart or its cost (price/benefit ratio) was seen as viable by consumers.

Price is also often affected by consumers' socio-demographic factors. It can act as a driver of or a barrier to the consumption of farmed seafood products depending on the level of income and occupation of the buyer. Income and age also appear to work together to influence the precise way in which price acts as a barrier or driver. In the PrimeFish project's study, younger consumers (under 30) were more concerned about price than older consumers due to their having a lower budget for food shopping (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016).

Although price is, without doubt, an important attribute, the way in which it acts as a driver or barrier is not always uniform across different groups of consumers, across different geographic areas, and across different time periods. The interviews conducted in five countries as part of the PrimeFish project (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016) provide some illustration of this complexity. Whilst price was a very important attribute for UK consumers, and was detailed as a barrier to purchase by French consumers, Italian respondents attached extreme importance to quality and were not willing to trade off quality for price. Price did not influence the purchasing choices of Italian respondents except in the case that a lower price was offered in the lowest quality category that was acceptable to the respondents.

3.3.2 Health, nutrition, and wellbeing

It is apparent from the literature that health is one of the most important reasons, if not the most important reason, why people eat fish (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Banrie, 2012), (Senior & Stewardson, 2019), (Meridian Institute and

Ocean Strategies, 2021), (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2021)). In research conducted by EUMOFA consumers were asked to choose three out of eight given reasons for buying and eating fish. Factors relating to health and wellness ('they are healthy'; 'they contain little fat'; 'they are easy to digest') were the most important at an EU level (these findings were averages across all member states and differences were observed at country and regional level) (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2017). Murray et al. showed that consumers highly value the health benefits of seafood: it was the most important factor for 12% of respondents and among the top three most important for nearly half (47%) the respondents. 70% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that they purchase seafood for the health benefits (Murray, et al., 2017). Health and nutrition are therefore important factors which could be further used to incentivise sustainable seafood consumption, particularly of that from aquaculture.

Two further surveys delivered similar findings. In a survey of French seafood consumers conducted on behalf of the Norwegian Seafood Council, health was the most important reason given for eating seafood (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016). In further research conducted globally by the Norwegian Seafood Council, it was found that the third most important reason for buying seafood (measured against 12 other reasons) was that it is healthy (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2021).

More recently, in 2022, the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) published the results of a consumer survey for which over 12,000 consumers in 12 countries were interviewed about their consumption and perception of seafood (see (The Fish Site, 2022) and (Aquaculture Stewardship Council, 2022)). Across all 12 countries health was found to be the primary driver for consumers purchasing seafood, with consumers in Germany and France leading this trend. Between 80% of consumers (in the Netherlands) and 96% of consumers (in Spain) questioned agreed that including fish in their daily shopping is important for health reasons.

The 2021 Eurobarometer report examined changes that occurred in relation to consumers' fishery and aquaculture consumption during the COVID-19 pandemic. Among consumers who reported an increase in consumption, the most common reason given was an increase in health consciousness (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021).

3.3.3 Self-efficacy and convenience

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their own ability to demonstrate a certain behaviour or achieve certain goals. Self-efficacy also has a key role in changing behaviours (Bandura, 1977, Tassel & Flett, 2005, as cited in (Davoodi, et al., 2018)). Self-efficacy in relation to the purchase of seafood is discussed in the literature as it pertains to a consumer's perceived ability to prepare and cook the produce at home, and to their ability to evaluate particular characteristics of fish and seafood, specifically freshness, safety, and quality. According to a *Supermarket News* online article from the US, there is one main reason for the gap that exists between how much seafood people are recommended to consume and the amount they do consume, and this is the tendency of seafood to intimidate consumers (Mitchell, 2021). Whilst the other evidence reviewed does not support the strength of this claim, a number of sources do highlight a role for self-efficacy in determining whether people purchase and consume seafood and, if so, how much (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Bruns, 2009), (Lamy & Szejda, 2020), (Ivoninskii, 2016), (Senior & Stewardson, 2019)).

Self-efficacy is related to the driver/barrier 'convenience'. If seafood is seen as difficult to prepare and cook, it is viewed as being less convenient than easier options, and this negatively affects consumption (Ivoninskii, 2016). Encouraging individuals to build their confidence and skills in selecting, preparing, and cooking seafood may help to increase their consumption of these foods and improve their overall diet quality. A further discussion of self-efficacy can be found in section 7.2.3.

3.3.4 The sensory properties of fish and seafood

The sensory properties of seafood, also referred to as their intrinsic cues (see (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017)), are consistently reported as being among the most important factors influencing consumers' choices when purchasing seafood. They have also been shown to be among the main reasons given by people who never, or rarely, consume fishery and aquaculture products as to why they do not do so (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021). They particularly act as barriers to the acceptance of seafood from aquaculture. This is due not only to the perceived (un)pleasantness of the sensory characteristics but to consumers' attitudes towards the product in question, determined by factors such as production method, animal welfare, origin, health claims, nutritional properties, brand quality certification, and price (Claret, et al., 2016). The following text provides a discussion of the literature relating to those sensory characteristics which received the most attention. Other sensory characteristics besides these include texture (e.g., (Ivoninskii, 2016), (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Getchis, et al., 2020), (FRDC, 2019), (Seafish, 2018)), and the presence of bones (e.g., (Seafish, 2018), (Altintzoglou, et al., 2016), (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)).

Smell and taste

The smell of fish is commonly detailed as a barrier to consumption (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Shaw, et al., 2019), (Seafish, 2018)). In the interviews conducted as part of the PrimeFish project, smell was listed as one of the main barriers to fish consumption by respondents from three of the five countries surveyed (France, the UK, and Spain) (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016).

Govzman et al. also identified that sensory preferences such as taste and smell were commonly named as barriers to seafood consumption (Govzman, et al., 2021).

Taste can serve as either a barrier to or a driver of fish purchase and consumption, and in numerous sources it is consistently listed amongst the most important attributes which determine purchase and consumption (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Lamy & Szejda, 2020), (Agricultural Utilization Research Institute, 2021), (Meridian Institute and Ocean Strategies, 2021), (Shaw, et al., 2019), (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (The Fish Site, 2022), (Seafish, 2018)). The Norwegian Seafood Council found that taste was the second most important reason given for eating seafood, beaten only by health (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016). In a UK study conducted by the non-departmental public body Seafish in 2018, taste came top of the list of reasons why people do not purchase fish, and top of the list of why people do (Seafish, 2018). In two separate US-based surveys, one conducted in Minnesota (Agricultural Utilization Research Institute, 2021) and the other in Wisconsin (Shaw, et al., 2019), taste came out top when participants were asked about the importance of different attributes of fish.

Appearance and presentation

The 2021 Eurobarometer report on EU consumer habits regarding fishery and aquaculture products found that across the EU member states consumers rated a product's appearance as the most important aspect when shopping for that product. When the results were broken down by country, appearance was placed first in 15 of the 27 member states. Appearance also tends to affect consumer perceptions about other product attributes (such as quality, freshness, origin, and value for money) and thus the consumer's willingness to purchase (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021).

It is important to note that the term 'appearance' is used inconsistently within the literature. It is often discussed in general terms but is also referred to in terms of individual attributes such as colour, and what the eyes and skin look like (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)). Furthermore, in the Eurobarometer report, appearance was qualified as pertaining to characteristics such as freshness and presentation while, in many other sources, freshness was referred to as a factor in its own right (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021).

According to Murray et al., preferences related to product presentation and preparation vary at the individual level and can be socio-culturally moderated; they cited as examples North American and Asian markets, which feature widely different products presented in different ways (Murray, et al., 2017). The visual appearance of the product packaging is also relevant for consumers. This was evidenced by Risius et al., who showed that consumers preferred a package which was associated with 'the sea', 'lakes', 'ponds', and 'freshness' (Risius, et al., 2017).

3.3.5 Freshness

Freshness is consistently stated as one of the most important attributes of seafood products (e.g., (Rhode Island Seafood Marketing Collaborative, 2012), (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Shaw, et al., 2019), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021), (Seafish, 2018), (Safe Food Queensland, 2021)). It is a relevant indicator of the quality of a product, especially for highly perishable products like fish and seafood (López-Mas, et al., 2022). In interviews conducted as part of the PrimeFish project, freshness was given as the most important attribute by respondents in France, Germany, Italy, and Spain. The only survey country for which freshness was not listed as a key attribute was the UK (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016). In interviews conducted by the ASC across 12 countries (see (The Fish Site, 2022) and (Aquaculture Stewardship Council, 2022)), freshness and cost were given as the two highest considerations for consumers when buying seafood. Similarly, in a survey conducted in Florida, US, freshness was found to be the most important determinant when choosing the point of purchase for seafood (Krimsky, et al., 2014).

Østli et al. have stated that perceptions of freshness depend largely on where the product is bought and how long consumers estimate it will keep (Østli, et al., 2013). In many countries it is most often bought from a fresh fish counter, without packaging and with limited labelling, making the fish seller the main source of information regarding its freshness (although this information may not always be reliable).

There was almost unanimous agreement among the stakeholders interviewed on the attributes of freshness for fileted and boxed fish. The most commonly listed attributes of a product used to judge freshness were the date of expiry, the presence of slime or water in the packaging, firmness, and colour. While a red colour is preferred for salmon in general, stakeholders felt that some consumers may be reserved about red-coloured salmon because the colour of farmed salmon is perceived as artificial. Similarly, greyish-coloured white fish is not well-received by consumers according to the interview findings. For whole fish, gills, eyes, firmness, and smell were identified by interviewees as important determinants of freshness. A stakeholder from the UK also mentioned that presenting the fish on a slab of ice could imply freshness to some consumers.

As to whether there are geographical variations on the perception of freshness, most stakeholders agreed that consumers from coastal areas with rich fishing traditions and access to active fisheries might have stronger views on the freshness of the seafood products they purchase. Additionally, a stakeholder from the UK linked the ideas of "farm to fork", "zero mileage on food", and purchasing seafood that is "as local as possible" to consumer perceptions of freshness.

Stakeholder interviewees commented that many consumers believe that fish should not be more than a few days old at the time of purchase, and there is a misconception that non-frozen fish is fresher than frozen fish. Freezing was also mentioned by some stakeholders as a barrier to judging freshness. A US survey report (Shaw, et al., 2019) highlights the potential complexity associated with freezing: ‘freshness’ as an attribute received a higher ranking than either ‘harvested recently’ or ‘never frozen’. This led the authors of the report to suggest that consumers have a “more abstract or intuitive way of thinking about what fresh means” (p. 10).

Attitudes towards farmed fish in relation to freshness are also varied. Farmed fish is usually seen as fresher by consumers who believe the farms have greater control over their production processes (Engle et al, 2017, as cited by (López-Mas, et al., 2022)). However, other studies (e.g., (Claret, et al., 2014), (Vanhonacker, et al., 2013)) showed that participants believe wild fish to be fresher than farmed fish. In reality, for many species and market segments, farmed fish are usually the fresher alternative because, as some stakeholder interviewees noted, they are not affected by seasonality. This ambiguity shows that consumers are not always aware of the origin and the implications of the production methods and processes in the definition of product attributes, particularly in the case of freshness, which remains a somewhat hazy concept. Freshness is discussed further in section 7.2.2.

3.3.6 Quality

The perceived quality of fish and seafood is a further factor which influences consumers’ choices, but which is ill-defined. It appears that quality is a somewhat amorphous virtue which can act as a driver or barrier in its own right (e.g., (Senior & Stewardson, 2019)), but which can also be attributed to produce with a particular origin (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017)), production method (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)), brand (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)), degree of freshness (e.g., (Lamy & Szejda, 2020)), or capture method (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016)). Most commonly, wild seafood is viewed as being of higher quality than farmed (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016), (Claret, et al., 2014), (Reig, et al., 2019), (López-Mas, et al., 2022), (Vanhonacker, et al., 2013)), and locally or nationally sourced seafood is viewed as being of higher quality than produce from further afield (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017)).

Many of the stakeholders interviewed mentioned that consumers consider properties such as expiry date, smell, appearance, firmness, colour, ease of preparation, and absence of bones to indicators of quality. Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC)/Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) certifications were cited by some of stakeholders as an important factor. Some attributes of quality less frequently suggested by the stakeholder interviewees included country of origin (as a proxy for quality), and the cooling chain of the product (in high-end markets). One industry stakeholder noted that consumers’ understanding of quality can involve many aspects, from environmental impacts to freshness of the product, which can vary across markets.

Price also interacts with quality as a deciding factor, as consumers may consider the price of a product to be an indicator of quality. As was perhaps to be expected, the salmon producer industry stakeholders agreed that price is a major factor for their consumers, regardless of the product’s country of origin, potentially overshadowing other quality attributes. Because farmed fish is often cheaper than wild fish, it is felt by consumers to be of a correspondingly lower quality (e.g., (Claret, et al., 2012)). Based on these interpretations, it may not be advisable to ask consumers how they perceive the quality of farmed fish directly, focusing instead on how consumers perceive specific attributes, such as health benefits, product safety, price, and production method, and then ask consumers to state which attributes they relate to quality.

Quality can be seen to interact with a number of other barriers and drivers to influence consumers’ fish and seafood purchasing decisions. However, it remains a difficult concept to pin down by itself, as it is not often viewed in isolation. Further understanding of this concept is required to help tailor intervention strategies to those consumers who consider farmed seafood to be of lower quality than wild. Quality is discussed further in section 7.2.2.

3.3.7 Safety

The perceived safety of fish and seafood is stated within the literature as either a driver of or barrier to purchase and consumption (e.g., (FRDC, 2019), (Safe Food Queensland, 2021), (Zander, et al., 2018), (Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2022), (Fernández Polanco & Llorente, 2015), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2017)). However, it too is not a term which is well-defined. In some cases, the literature refers directly to issues related to the presence of mercury (e.g., (Lamy & Szejda, 2020), (Fernández Polanco & Llorente, 2015)) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) (Lamy & Szejda, 2020) in seafood. However, in many other sources, perceived safety is stated as a factor which influences purchasing decisions, but what determines whether a product is safe is not defined (e.g., (Safe Food Queensland, 2021), (Fernández Polanco & Llorente, 2015), (Agricultural Utilization Research Institute, 2021)).

The perceived safety of aquaculture specifically can act as both a barrier and a driver. Aquaculture is generally seen as a high-impact process, especially by consumers considering previous harm caused by inappropriate use of industrial feeds (e.g.,

(Hoque, 2021), (Ruiz-Chico, et al., 2020)), chemicals ((Ruiz-Chico, et al., 2020), (Hoerterer, et al., 2022)), toxins (e.g., (Schlag & Ystgaard, 2013), (Hoerterer, et al., 2022)), and heavy metals (Schlag & Ystgaard, 2013) with their ensuing health risks. Perceived health risks, especially those brought about by factors related to fish farming operations, will hinder acceptance of aquaculture seafood consumption. Murray et al. found that women especially are more likely to consider potential health risks to be an important factor when making purchasing decisions (Murray, et al., 2017).

On the other hand, a belief in the safety of aquaculture can also directly result in the increased consumption its products (Lee & Nam, 2019). Fernandez-Polanco and Luna found that belief in the safety of the farming methods used in the aquaculture sector may increase consumption, which may, in turn, improve other consumers' perceptions of aquaculture. Their research found that those under 65 years old with a superior level of education tended to think especially positively about the safety of aquaculture (Fernandez-Polanco & Luna, 2012).

Although many of the sources reviewed referred to or described safety as a driver of/barrier to seafood purchase and consumption, the volume of information about this factor was comparatively low, making it difficult to obtain a clear understanding of how it influences behaviour and how it relates to other factors such as origin and production method. The stakeholders interviewed suggested that consumers tend to delegate safety issues to retailers, assuming that retailers will not sell products that may be harmful, further adding to the ambiguity.

3.3.8 Origin

In most of the studies analysed, origin was among the attributes considered to be of the highest importance, and the importance that consumers place on it is growing. The 2021 Eurobarometer report indicates that of a list of six factors (appearance, cost, origin, brand or quality label, how easy and quick to prepare, environmental, social, or ethical impact) the importance placed by consumers on the origin of fishery and aquaculture products had seen the greatest increase in a three-year period (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021).

Origin is determined by various factors that are related to the place of production (going from local to imported), consumer awareness of local fishing operations, and the location of purchase. Where a preference exists, it is almost universally for produce which is either locally produced (for example, in coastal locations) or produced in the same country or continent as the consumer.

Claret et al. show the importance of country of origin to consumers, citing various studies revealing that: 1) it relates to the perception of the quality of the product among other attributes; 2) it is especially important for fresh and perishable products for which a higher health and safety risk is perceived; and 3) it echoes the perceived superiority or inferiority of the country of origin of the products (Claret, et al., 2012).

The stakeholder interviewees held differing views on whether seafood that is produced and processed locally to the consumer is preferred. An academic stakeholder argued that only a niche group of consumers are even aware of the origin of their food and that awareness is heavily dependent on labelling. In contrast, most of the other stakeholders agreed that people do care about where their fish comes from, but the degree of importance to the consumer and the motivation they feel to seek it out varies from market to market (Seafood Norway). For example, a salmon producer stakeholder stated that in the UK people prefer locally produced seafood because they feel it helps support their community and create jobs. This notion was backed up by a Norwegian stakeholder, who argued that, for most consumers, the greatest motivation for buying local seafood is to generate local production. The 2017 PrimeFish report suggested that a sense of patriotism may also be relevant to consumers' preferences for more local fish and seafood (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017). On a different note, while acknowledging the importance of local production for consumers, an environmental stakeholder interviewee noted that Swedish consumers associate sustainability first and foremost with local production.

According to Richter and Klöckner, 'local' is a term that is both variably defined and exploited by seafood providers. Many people may like the idea of 'local' as a characteristic of their seafood, as they assume that it represents a fresher, higher quality product, that it supports local economies and livelihoods, that it is more environmentally friendly, or some combination of these things (Richter & Klöckner, 2017). The absence or presence of origin certification label is a key factor in the identification of the product's origin, and therefore influences consumer acceptance of the product.

While there is a general tendency for consumers to prefer fish and seafood from their home country, there are some exceptions. As highlighted by the authors of the 2016 Norwegian Seafood Council report about seafood consumption in France, for species such as salmon that people are very aware of and for which they possess knowledge about where the produce ideally comes from, their preferences are often more specific (e.g., they may state a specific preference for Norwegian salmon over Scottish salmon or vice-versa) (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016). An interview participant from the UK noted that a product of Scottish provenance is often prominently marketed as such by retailers, indicating that origin (particularly in relation to Scottish salmon) is a major selling-point for UK consumers.

Origin also influences how consumers perceive other attributes such as quality, price, freshness, environmental-friendliness, and certification. Evidence is reported that consumers may judge the quality of seafood based on origin, with domestic

products being considered superior because they don't require long transportations and elaborate preservation treatments (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017). The price of fish may also interact with geographic origin and perceptions of quality: as summarised in the literature review within the PrimeFish (2017) report, foreign fish are often cheaper than domestic products which leads to the perception that imported fish is of lesser quality (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017).

In some cases, the origin of a product can signal to consumers that it should be actively avoided, and that other supply sources should be found. This was the case, for example, for products imported into South Korea from Japan following the Fukushima nuclear plant disaster, when safety concerns affected the acceptance of the Japanese products (Lee & Nam, 2019).

Regarding aquaculture products specifically, Risius et al. found from a survey conducted in Germany that most consumers preferred local products or at least those farmed in Germany. This not only demonstrated consumer trust in the German Veterinary and Food Administration scheme overseeing aquaculture in Germany, but it suggested that local fish production was popular because it offered consumers the opportunity to investigate the production facilities themselves. The authors also highlighted that consumers associated origin with the ability to find information on the precise company or production plant products come from, increasing supply chain transparency. The short transportation distance between facility and place of purchase was also viewed favourably (Risius, et al., 2017).

The importance of origin across Europe

A number of grey literature sources examined and, in some cases, compared seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour across Europe (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017), (Curles, 2019), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)). A summary of the evidence reviewed pertaining to various European countries is presented in *Table 6*.

Table 6 Evidence and information specific to European countries in relation to the importance of the origin of fish and seafood

Country and geographic origin	Source reference	Information/evidence about origin
Croatia	(Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)	95% of consumers surveyed preferred local over imported fish.
Denmark	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in last position.
Estonia	(Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)	Origin was considered important for fresh and smoked fish products. It was less important for frozen produce.
Finland	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in first position.
France	(Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)	The majority of respondents in the reported survey preferred not to buy from outside Europe. Those from coastal areas preferred locally caught fish.
	(Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016)	Nine out of ten consumers stated that country of origin is important when buying fish or seafood, and this preference is increasing. French consumers' preferred origin for salmon is Norway. For the other species that consumers were questioned about (cod, prawns, and trout), the preference was for French produce. However, the number of people who were not sure for these species was very high. The importance of origin was found to increase with consumption frequency.

Germany	(Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)	Origin was given by consumers as an important consideration when purchasing fish.
	(Canadian Ministry of Agriculture and Agri-Food, 2018)	75% of German consumers preferred regional products and 70% were prepared to pay more for them.
	(Curles, 2019)	The main drivers of choice were reported as cost, country of origin, the way fish are raised, and sustainability labelling.
	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in first position.
Italy	(Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)	Survey respondents generally preferred local fish, Italian fish, or fish from known and trusted countries.
Luxembourg	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in first position.
Lithuania	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in last position.
Malta	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in last position.
Slovenia	(Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)	Origin was important for people aged 56 – 65 years with a high salary and a high educational level. The rest of the population tended to neither take into account the origin, nor consume fresh fish products.
Spain	(Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)	Survey respondents preferred local produce.
Sweden	(Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)	Of a list of six factors (appearance; cost; origin; brand or quality label; how easy and quick to prepare; environmental, social, or ethical impact), consumers placed origin in first position.
UK	(Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)	None of the UK respondents to a survey minded if fish was imported, although they exhibited a preference for local fish and caution about products from far away.

3.3.9 Labelling and certification

Labelling can be used to convey information about multiple different seafood product characteristics, including the origin or source, the production method, and the catch method. Any certifications that the product has received (such as MSC or ASC certification) can also be used to make claims about the sustainability of the fish or seafood.

The multitude of characteristics that can be indicated on a label through certification or simple printed information, and the inconsistent way in which this topic is dealt with in the sources, makes it somewhat difficult to disentangle. Whilst some sources focus on specific labels and the relative importance of these to consumers (e.g., (Curles, 2019)), others take a more overarching view, looking at what information on labels is important to consumers or which of the available certifications they report as making a difference to their purchasing behaviour (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016)).

An additional complicating factor is that labelling and certification is wrapped up with other drivers of and barriers to consumption including origin, sustainability, and environmental and animal welfare concerns. These factors are, of course, interwoven and, thus, untangling what specifically it is that drives purchasing behaviour (the labels themselves or what consumers interpret them to mean and represent) is challenging.

Most of the stakeholder representatives interviewed agreed that only a small fraction of consumers truly understand the implications of the labels used in the seafood industry. Academia representatives from both Norway and the UK suggested that the information provided can be overwhelming and difficult for consumers to interpret. Many stakeholders mentioned that

consumers may not want to engage with too much information when doing daily food shopping in contrast to other goods which they shop for rarely. They argued that, except for consumers looking for specific products, most consumers do not really pay attention to these labels, and one stakeholder noted that the information on labels might be more relevant for business-to-business (B2B) transactions rather than business-to-consumer (B2C) transactions (University of Stavanger).

Some stakeholder interviewees identified several labels which consumers value, including the ASC and MSC certification labels, organic product labels, local production labels, EU production labels, and mid-tier and premium-tier labels, that may potentially encourage a higher willingness-to-pay among consumers. However, stakeholders from the seafood industry and environmental agencies argued that, although some consumers recognise the ASC and MSC labels, they do not understand the difference between them, and they can mistakenly believe that these labels indicate the quality of the seafood (WWF Sweden and Salmon Scotland). Another stakeholder pointed out that labels function as a regulatory tool, but they do not help consumers establish a product's quality (SAIC Scotland). Focusing only on information provision to yield consumer behavioural change might thus turn out to be ineffective, since an understanding of the content of labels by the consumer is required as well as their presence on products (e.g., Jonell, et al., 2016), (Hoerterer, et al., 2022)).

A critical aspect influencing consumer behaviour when purchasing farmed seafood products is their lack of knowledge about the environmental impact of aquaculture (Jonell, et al., 2016). Information provided on eco-labels about the sustainability of a product may stimulate a shift toward more environmentally friendly consumer behaviour (Taufique et al, 2016, as cited in (Galati, et al., 2022)). Nonetheless, there are still some doubts about sustainable seafood eco-labels, as it is unclear whether they are truly effective in informing consumers about choosing environmentally friendly products (Song et al, 2019, as cited in (Galati, et al., 2022)).

Labelling and certification can also act as barriers to seafood purchasing. Consumers' trust in farmed fish products is already hindered by the presence of a number of different actors in the supply chain whose reliability is sometimes questioned. A lack of trust in the seafood industry and its regulatory organisations and certifiers (van Osch, et al., 2019) is a problem that must be overcome to ensure a higher consumer acceptance of aquaculture products. A stakeholder representative from Croatia claimed that many consumers do not believe the labelling system adds any value to products as they do not trust that system or the people who oversee it. A possible solution to this critical level of distrust is represented by independent governmental agencies providing certifications for farmed fish products (Danso, et al., 2017).

Pulcini et al. emphasise the role that value chain stakeholders could play in raising confidence in aquaculture products. They suggest that value chain stakeholders should provide information and guarantees about aquaculture products, on labels that: 1) show the product is safe because it is traceable; 2) clearly indicate the very limited and responsible use of antibiotics; 3) describe farming practices; and 4) provide accurate information about farmed animals' nutrition and feed quality (Pulcini, et al., 2020).

It is difficult to know for certain what influence (if any) labelling and certification have on consumers' decisions to purchase seafood products. Fernandez-Polanco and Luna showed that the amount of available information, as well as the consumer's ability to understand it, are critical factors in achieving a positive attitude among consumers toward aquaculture (Fernandez-Polanco & Luna, 2012). However, some of the stakeholder interviewees warned that, given current inflation, price may be the main determinant of consumer behaviour, and even if consumers value certain labels, they may prioritise lower prices when making purchasing decisions.

3.3.10 Sustainability and environmental concerns

Sustainability is, without doubt, an important factor which influences the purchasing and consumption of seafood. However, as highlighted in the report on consumer trends produced by the Norwegian Seafood Council in 2021, sustainability is a concept, and a somewhat ill-defined one at that (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2021). Thus, what individuals associate with sustainability and how it is understood varies. There are also cultural differences in how the term 'sustainability' is used. Furthermore, concerns about sustainability overlap with environmental concerns, and both in turn interact with other purchasing drivers such as those associated with production methods, labelling, and certification.

The stakeholder interview participants brought up a diverse range of issues related to consumer perceptions of the sustainability of seafood products, further highlighting the complexity and multi-faceted nature of the topic. For instance, a Norwegian stakeholder cited a past study they had conducted, which asked respondents to define the concept of sustainability in the seafood industry. The study identified 26 different categories of definitions, ranging from issues related to the value chain and ethical fishing practices to animal welfare (Seafood Norway).

Hynes et al. found that more than half of the consumers they sampled (57%) felt worried about negative environmental impacts related to seafood consumption, while 44% perceived themselves as environmentally conscious (Hynes, et al., 2019). These results emphasise the relevance consumers place on environmental factors when purchasing seafood. However, Bronnmann & Hoffmann's research indicated that a high share of respondents believed that farmed products have negative impacts on the environment (Bronnmann & Hoffmann, 2018). There were also diverse views among the stakeholders interviewed regarding the public's understanding of sustainability in the wild fishing and aquaculture industries. For instance, a Croatian stakeholder

noted that while most people recognise that wild capture fishing cannot be sustainable in the long-term, they are uncertain about how to connect different dimensions of sustainability to the aquaculture industry.

According to the majority of the stakeholders interviewed, the key sustainability concerns for the seafood industry from a consumer perspective are environmental, including farms' CO₂ footprints, the impact of farming sites on water quality and local fjords and fish stocks, fishing practices when obtaining feed, farms' benthic impacts, biodiversity disruptions, MSC/ASC certification, sustainable packaging, overfishing, TAC regulations, pollution and waste management. It was also suggested that sustainability concerns may vary in line with local issues, such as the problems connected to overfishing Swedish herring for feed production. However, all the environmental stakeholders pointed out that consumers generally lack adequate knowledge about the sustainability aspects of the seafood industry as a whole.

Third-party certification schemes, such as MSC, ASC, Royal Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals (RSPCA), and Global Gap, were most commonly identified by stakeholder interviewees as the primary channels of communication about environmental sustainability. It is important to note that some of these labels, such as the ASC, also expand into social, economical, and governmental sustainability dimensions. Additionally, Norwegian stakeholders cited companies' individual efforts at sustainability reporting, such as publishing online sustainability libraries, tracking reports, and communicating CO₂ emissions per kg on labels. The stakeholders observed an overall trend towards increased documentation in the industry. However, environmental stakeholders challenged the idea that these efforts are sufficient to consider the industry environmentally sustainable. While some non-industrial stakeholders felt that the industry is transparent in its practices, the environmental stakeholders argued that these efforts were more about marketing than sustainability.

While most of the stakeholders interviewed discussed the environmental sustainability of the seafood industry, some highlighted that the industry also involves economic and social dimensions of sustainability (e.g., Salmon Scotland). Overall, the consensus among stakeholders was that the public's attention is primarily on environmental sustainability in both the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, rather than social and economic sustainability. However, stakeholders from Norway and the UK observed an increasing awareness among the public regarding the social and economic sustainability of the aquaculture industry. Industry stakeholders identified well-paid jobs, infrastructure, and support for rural communities as key factors contributing to this increased awareness. The academic representative from the UK noted that while traditional farming benefits only the farmer, fish farming benefits the entire community, which can raise awareness in society. Environmental representatives from Sweden and the UK also acknowledged the social and economic benefits that fish farming brings, in contrast to the fishing industry, which often experiences employment problems (OpenSeas UK).

It appears that, although sustainability is clearly important to consumers and is among the most important considerations when making seafood purchases, other factors often tend to take precedence. For example, in reporting of the large-scale survey conducted across 12 countries by the ASC between 2021 and 2022 (see (The Fish Site, 2022)), it was summarised that while sustainability is a top consideration in seafood purchases, it actually comes in third place after freshness and cost. A white paper produced by The Good Food Institute in 2020 (Lamy & Szejda, 2020) summarises research which shows that consumers must be predisposed to caring about sustainability to make purchases based on this attribute, and that social pressure from friends, family, and colleagues correlated with intention to purchase sustainable seafood. This is confirmed by (Hynes, et al., 2019), who found that only when consumers consider environmentally friendly products to be of utmost importance, will they consider paying a price premium, and even then this does not always result in an actual willingness to pay a higher price (Bronnmann & Hoffmann, 2018).

There is some indication that environmental and sustainability concerns have a differential effect on fish and seafood purchasing behaviour depending on individuals' characteristics. For example, research in the UK found that environmental and ethical concerns were especially important among younger and well-educated individuals who were more aware about fish stocks and fishing methods (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016).

An observation made while conducting the grey literature review was that there was no discussion of the sustainability of packaging; this is surprising given the focus placed on the use of plastics to package food in many other sectors of the industry.

Consumer behaviour in purchasing farmed seafood products is influenced by a range of environmental factors related to sustainability and ecosystem health. Understanding these factors and their benefit for local communities is essential for producers, marketers, and policymakers to develop effective strategies to promote sustainable and responsible aquaculture practices (e.g., (Murray, et al., 2017), (Witter, et al., 2021)). Sustainability is discussed further in section 7.2.2.

3.3.11 Production method

The way in which seafood is produced, and how this influences purchasing and consumption behaviour, is mainly discussed in the literature in relation to whether that seafood is wild-caught or from aquaculture. As aquaculture is considered to be the only alternative to wild capture fishing which is able to satisfy the increasing consumer demand for sustainable production of safe seafood of the highest quality and nutritional value (Claret, et al., 2016), it is important to understand consumers' views on it.

Numerous sources have sought to address the question of whether consumers prefer wild or aquaculture products. The picture that emerges is that, where a preference exists, it is for wild produced products, but the strength of feeling is geographically dependent with little or no preference observed in some areas.

According to the Eurobarometer report, almost one-third (32%) of consumers of fishery and aquaculture products stated that they had a preference for wild produce (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021). However, a similar proportion (30%) stated that they had no preference. When the results were broken down by country it was found that respondents in 14 member states were more likely to state a preference for wild products, with the highest levels seen in Greece, Cyprus, and Portugal.

Geographic variations in the strength of feeling regarding wild versus farmed fish were also observed in the PrimeFish project's research on drivers of seafood consumption across various European countries (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016). For example, for French consumers, production method was found to be very important, and the majority preferred to buy wild fish. However, the final choice was usually determined by price. Meanwhile, in the UK, whilst there was a general preference for wild, there was very limited knowledge of the differences between wild and farmed fish.

A Eurobarometer article suggests the proportion of individuals who hold a strong preference for either wild (32%) or farmed products (7%) has slightly decreased in the majority of member states. Consumers are now more likely to say that their preference depends on the type of product, or that they do not know if the products they buy or eat are wild or farmed (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2021).

Based on their previous research, some of the stakeholder interviewees felt that, excepting very engaged consumers, the general public is ambivalent about production methods. However, most participants also agreed that farmed fish has a reputation issue. It was noted that, while most meat protein comes from farmed animals, it is salmon farming, in particular, that is often singled out in the minds of consumers when they are asked about aquaculture. Furthermore, the Croatian industry stakeholder representative reported that some consumers consider farmed fish to be an inferior product and they expect to be served wild fish at a reputable seafood restaurant.

Consumers' knowledge and perceptions of aquaculture

Consumers' uncertainty and confusion regarding seafood production methods is reported in a number of the sources reviewed. French consumers, when asked to give their opinion on farmed, wild, and organic fish, felt that wild fish was more natural, of better quality, and more tasty and nutritious than both farmed and organic fish. Farmed fish was seen as better value for money and more 'risky' than wild and organic fish. Organic fish was seen as more environmentally friendly, healthier, more animal friendly, and safer to eat than both wild and farmed fish (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016). As highlighted by the authors of the report, "What is interesting with these impressions is that apparently consumers are confused about organic and farmed fish. Do they know that organic fish is farmed? Not sure." (p. 47).

The stakeholder interviewees unanimously agreed that the general public's understanding of the aquaculture industry is limited, if not entirely uneven. While many stakeholders asserted that people are familiar with the term "fish farming," several believed that the term "aquaculture" remains unfamiliar to a significant portion of the population. Nevertheless, a few stakeholders noted that there has been considerable progress in recent years in raising awareness and recognition of the industry, resulting in increased public knowledge (e.g., WWF Sweden, Salmon Scotland). Regarding consumers' attitudes towards wild-caught versus farmed fish, some representatives argued that most consumers do not consider it during their purchase decisions, or they mistakenly believe that the farmed seafood they consume is wild-caught (e.g., WWF Sweden, Seafood Norway).

Consumers' perceptions of aquaculture can also change depending on the production method used, which can lead to them disregarding the benefits of some methods, such as genetic modifications and wastewater-based aquaculture (Claret, et al., 2016). Much attention is paid in the literature to the usage of wastewater within aquaculture production processes. This innovation is generally viewed with concern by consumers who prefer to avoid it, even though they are usually unaware of whether the farmed fish they eat is wastewater-based (Danso, et al., 2017).

Petereit et al. found that some consumer prejudices can be linked to the reinforcement of false media images, which often propagate the negative narrative of harmful aquaculture systems and ignore the industry's efforts to develop sustainable aquaculture production systems (Petereit, et al., 2022). This finding corroborates Vanhonacker et al., specifically in regard to negative news coverage on the use of colorants and antibiotics in salmon farming (Vanhonacker, et al., 2013). Many of the stakeholder interviewees agreed, commenting on the persistent false belief amongst consumers that farmed seafood is packed with chemicals and antibiotics, even though the salmon industry, to take one example, has phased antibiotics out in recent decades. Both the academic and the seafood production industry stakeholders highlighted the media's role in pollution and toxicity scrutiny. Consumers are sensitive to such information and have the tendency to project any negative images they see onto the whole sector (Petereit, et al., 2022).

Risius et al. revealed that, although some consumers considered the information provided on product packaging to be insufficient, they did not possess sufficient knowledge to enable them to distinguish between the different production methods

used. Similarly, consumers revered the importance of organic aquaculture production, citing sustainability as the main reason, yet most could not specify the criteria they associated with sustainable or certified organic production (Risius, et al., 2017). Most consumers could not evaluate process-related quality characteristics either since they knew too little about industrial aquaculture production methods. These results evidence the importance of accurate knowledge to aid consumers' decision making, although knowledge alone is not necessarily a driver of purchasing (Petereit, et al., 2022).

Socio-demographic factors can also affect the level of knowledge consumers have about aquaculture, particularly age and level of education (Fernandez-Polanco & Luna, 2012). Fernández-Polanco & Luna found that beliefs about aquaculture improved in the two years of their research (2005 and 2006) in more highly educated respondents below the age of 65. This segment of consumers is expected to possess a greater understanding of complex information related to aquaculture and fisheries (Sapp, 2003 as cited by (Fernandez-Polanco & Luna, 2012)), and thus be more accepting of aquaculture products. The OrAqua project found that, for the segment of consumers who view organic production positively, there is a willingness to pay the price premium that typically accompanies these products, especially among those who have a high educational level, high income, high knowledge about organic food, and young children (Altintzoglou, et al., 2016).

The literature and the stakeholder interviews showed that the level of knowledge about aquaculture production methods among consumers is uneven, and their perceptions of aquaculture, and thus their trust in its products, vary greatly.

3.3.12 Consumer trust

Consumer trust in seafood producers is built on many of the preceding factors. According to the stakeholder interview participants, trust in seafood products is also closely tied to trust in the local fish vendors, retail chains, and authorities involved in the supply chain. To increase consumer trust in seafood products, the interviewees suggested a range of factors, including certifications such as the MSC or ASC, transparent information on additives, QR codes for easy traceability, country of origin labelling, provenance stories, and locally sourced products.

However, the stakeholder interviewees also mentioned several issues that undermine consumer trust, such as sudden shifts in quality and price, broken traceability in the supply chain, and unethical practices exposed in the media, such as fraudulent products, illegal fishing, or pollution scandals.

The stakeholder interviews revealed that traceability issues play a significant role in both enhancing and diminishing trust in seafood products. Consequently, many stakeholders emphasised the growing need for transparency and traceability in the seafood industry. Some stakeholders even suggested that smart labelling technologies, electronic tags, and blockchain technology could be used more extensively in the future to improve traceability and transparency.

While some stakeholder representatives from both industrial and environmental backgrounds emphasised the importance of provenance and telling the story behind each product to engage consumers, others were sceptical. They argued that few consumers paid attention to QR codes that provided this type of information in previous trials. Despite this, most stakeholders agreed that improving transparency and traceability is essential for enhancing consumer trust in seafood products. Furthermore, a few stakeholder interviewees suggested the existence of a generational gap when it comes to the demand for increased traceability and transparency in the seafood industry, and that younger consumers tend to require more documentation about the seafood they buy (e.g., Norwegian Fisheries Directorate, Salmon Scotland).

4. Task 2.1 Conclusions

The literature reviews provided a wealth of information about the factors which influence consumers' purchasing and consumption of seafood, while the stakeholder interviews enabled a more nuanced picture of some of these factors to be developed. Significant headway was thus made in WP2 through identifying these factors and starting to understand both the complex ways in which their effects differ across different consumer groups and the ways in which they interact with one another. However, the work completed in task 2.1 highlighted a number of areas where further knowledge was needed in order to obtain the level of understanding required about current behavioural drivers.

While the literature reviews and stakeholder interviews provided a diverse range of perspectives, the next step was to turn directly to the consumers to get their views on various concepts. This included gathering further information on their understanding of sustainability, freshness, and quality as they relate to seafood products, and how this understanding influences their purchasing behaviours. The way these factors interact with one another and with other factors (such as certification, labelling, production method, and origin) was also felt to be worthy of further investigation.

Although the reviews identified a general preference among consumers for wild-caught fish products, further understanding of the reasons behind this preference was required. Consumers' knowledge and understanding of labelling and certification also needed further investigation, as did their knowledge and resulting perceptions of aquaculture.

Finally, task 2.1 highlighted that the barriers and drivers do not exert their effects uniformly across consumer groups (which differ in characteristics such as age, gender, education level, income, and family relationships), or across geographic locations.

Identifying how consumers' socio-demographic characteristics affect their preferences is a hard task which could however pave the way to effective and tailor-made intervention strategies. Further work was thus needed to build on existing knowledge such that targeted interventions can be developed (in WP2 tasks 2.3 and 2.4) to facilitate increased sustainable purchasing and consumption of European aquaculture products. These knowledge gaps helped inform the development of the survey and the subsequent cluster analysis in task 2.2.

Part 2. Task 2.2 Identification of consumers' behavioural clusters to identify target groups

5. Overview of Task 2.2

The next component of WP2 was task 2.2, the specific objectives of which were to identify consumers' key characteristics and behavioural drivers across the EU, and to use this information to identify clusters of consumers who exhibit similar behavioural patterns and/or experiences of barriers/drivers. The identification of these behavioural clusters will feed into the development and testing (in task 2.3) of tailored intervention strategies designed to facilitate increased sustainable seafood purchasing and consumption.

A survey was developed and distributed across three EU countries (Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia) to collect the relevant data on consumer behaviours in relation to seafood products. Initial analysis of the results provided information on respondents' demographics, purchasing preferences, and views on aquaculture. A cluster analysis was then performed on the survey results to identify distinct groups of consumers for whom intervention strategies will be tailored in tasks 2.3 and 2.4.

Part 2 of this deliverable presents the findings from task 2.2. A section on the methodology is followed by a presentation of survey respondents' socio-demographic and geographical characteristics, the barriers and drivers they experience when purchasing seafood, their seafood purchasing habits, and their knowledge and perception of aquaculture. There is then a discussion of the various distinct consumer clusters identified in each of the three countries, followed by task 2.2 conclusions.

6. Methodology

6.1 Country choices

The three countries selected to be the focus of task 2.2 were Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia. This selection provided one country each from Northern, Southern, and Central Europe. These countries also differed according to several additional relevant characteristics, which are outlined in *Table 7*.

Table 7 Relevant characteristics of three country choices (Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia) and the range exhibited across European Member States (where relevant)¹

Characteristic	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia	Range across all EU Member States
Geographic location in Europe	Northern	Southern	Central	
Consumption of fisheries & aquaculture products (2019) (kg/inhabitant/year) ²	42.56	31.21	12.18	59.91 (PT) - 6.00 (CZ)
% of total value of EU member states' aquaculture production (2019) ³	2.50	9.09	0.12	26.24 (UK) - 0.01 (BE)
% of total volume of EU member states' aquaculture production (2019) ³	2.94	11.26	0.15	16.06 (UK) - 0.01 (BE)
Main species in aquaculture per Member State (2019) ⁴	Rainbow trout; Atlantic salmon	Japanese carpet shell, Rainbow trout, Gilthead seabream, European seabass, Mediterranean mussel	Rainbow trout, Mediterranean mussel, warty venus, European seabass	

¹ Please note that the source used includes the UK as a member state as it is dated pre-Brexit.

² (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2022) https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/facts-and-figures/facts-and-figures-common-fisheries-policy/consumption_en

³ (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2022) https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/facts-and-figures/facts-and-figures-common-fisheries-policy/fisheries-and-aquaculture-production_en

⁴ (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2022) <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c2f39f4a-29a2-11ed-975d-01aa75ed71a1>

Bordering seas	North Sea and Baltic Sea	Mediterranean Sea	Mediterranean Sea	
Share of population within 5km from sea (%) ⁵	50	34	22	98(MT) - 6 (BE) (only countries with sea border)
Share of population within 15km from sea (%) ⁵	81	55	34	100 (MT) - 12 (BE) (only countries with sea border)
Share of population within 50km from sea (%) ⁵	99	94	93	100 (MT, CY) - 64 (DE) (only countries with sea border)

6.2 Sampling criteria

The respondent sample in each of the three survey countries was representative for age, gender (male/female), income, geographic region (including urban/rural), and household composition.

Sampling criteria were set prior to survey distribution and operationalised by the survey company. Respondents were required to be:

1. Resident in the survey country (Denmark, Italy, or Slovenia).
2. Eighteen years old or older.
3. Consumers of fish and/or seafood products.
4. Responsible for at least half of their household's grocery shopping.
5. People who purchase at least one of finfish, shellfish, cephalopods, or crustaceans more frequently than once a month.

Anyone who did not meet all five criteria was not invited to complete the rest of the survey.

6.3 Overview of survey questions and layout

The survey began with a welcome page which thanked respondents for taking part. They were informed that the survey would take them approximately 15 minutes to complete and that the information they provided would not be made public or used to identify them in any way.

The preliminary questions gathered information about respondents' age, gender, the proportion of their household's grocery shopping and cooking they performed, and the frequency with which they purchased different types of seafood (finfish, shellfish, cephalopods, and crustaceans). Following this, respondents were provided with a short description of the purpose of the survey and were informed that for the remainder of the survey the term "seafood" would be used to refer generally to all forms of fish (e.g. salmon, cod, plaice), shellfish (e.g. clams, oysters, mussels), cephalopods (e.g. octopus, squid), and crustaceans (e.g. prawns, crab, lobster). They were also told that unless a question asked about a specific type of seafood, they should assume that it referred generally to all the types of seafood that they purchase and eat.

The next questions related to the following topics:

- The location from which seafood is purchased (e.g. supermarket, fishmonger, market).
- The frequency with which seafood products that have undergone different types of processing (e.g. filleting, canning, freezing, pickling) are purchased.
- Perceived levels of knowledge about different types of seafood production (aquaculture and wild-caught) and certifications.
- Self-efficacy in relation to seafood storage, preparation, and cooking.
- The importance of various characteristics when choosing chilled seafood to purchase.
- The characteristics that are seen to make seafood more or less sustainable, fresh, high quality.
- Preferences for wild-caught or aquaculture-derived seafood and beliefs about these two production methods.

The final set of questions sought socio-demographic information about the respondents, specifically their main working situation, income, household size, the type of area they reside in (e.g. city, town, village), and the distance between their home and the coast.

⁵ (Collet & Engelbert, 2013)

The survey was prepared in English and then translated into Danish, Italian, and Slovenian by the survey company. Any questions that required context specificity (for example, the question about highest qualification held and that about income) were suitably adapted. The questions contained within the survey are presented in Appendix 4, in the original English version only.

6.4 Cluster analysis

Cluster analysis was then adopted to identify homogeneous groups of consumers in each of the three countries. To do so, answers provided by consumers in the survey were analysed implementing several hierarchical (single, average, complete, weighted-average, median, centroid, and Ward's linkage) and partition (k-means and k-medians) clustering methods.

Output for the Ward's minimum variance clustering was considered for the analysis, since it led to the identification of the most balanced number of clusters in terms of size. In addition, the Ward's minimum variance method of minimising the variance of results inside clusters and maximising the variance among the clusters, led to the identification of the most coherent groups of respondents, avoiding overlap between clusters. The cluster analysis enabled the identification of four homogeneous groups of consumers each in Denmark and Slovenia, and five in Italy.

Groups identified through this analysis presented internally homogeneous and externally heterogeneous behaviours related to: drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption; knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling; and perceptions and preferences related to wild-fish and aquaculture products. The number of clusters of consumers considered for each of the countries was defined by the values of the pseudo-F index calculated for the three samples.

The differences across clusters were statistically tested within each country and then a descriptive cross-country comparison was conducted among three sets of questions. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess whether the clusters differed significantly in terms of socio-demographic characteristics, drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption, knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling, or perceptions and preferences related to wild-caught and aquaculture products. The adoption of non-parametric tests such as Kruskal-Wallis to test differences for Likert scales is widely used in literature and has proven to be robust, especially given the size of the samples analysed in this work, and allows to operate with non-normally distributed data.

7. Survey Findings

7.1 Socio-demographic characteristics

The following three tables (*Table 8*, *Table 9* and *Table 10*) show the breakdown of ages and genders of each of the three countries' samples. Full details on survey respondents' socio-demographic and geographical characteristics can be found in Appendix 5.

Table 8 Number of respondents in each age and gender category in Denmark

Age	Gender			Total
	Male	Female	Prefer not to say	
18 – 29	130	97	2	229
30 – 39	103	124	1	228
40 – 49	81	92		173
50 – 59	83	89		172
60 – 70	55	53		108
>70	45	51		96
Total	497	506	3	1006

Table 9 Number of respondents in each age and gender category in Italy

Age	Gender			Total
	Male	Female	Prefer not to say	
18 – 29	63	74	2	139
30 – 39	76	72	1	149
40 – 49	97	95		192
50 – 59	103	105		208
60 – 70	114	129		243
>70	47	36		83
Total	500	511	3	1014

Table 10 Number of respondents in each age and gender category in Slovenia

	Gender			

Age	Male	Female	Other	Prefer not to say	Total
18 – 29	95	84	2	1	182
30 – 39	106	94			200
40 – 49	122	106	1		229
50 – 59	107	107			214
60 – 70	69	95			164
>70	12	9			21
Total	511	495	3	1	1010

7.2 Drivers of and barriers to seafood consumption

7.2.1 Important considerations when choosing chilled seafood to buy

The literature reviews and stakeholder interviews carried out in task 2.1 identified numerous factors that are important to consumers when they are choosing seafood to purchase. The survey examined the relevance of the following barriers and drivers in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia:

1. The geographic source of the product - whether from a consumer's country of residence rather than elsewhere in Europe
2. The geographic source of the product - whether from Europe rather than elsewhere in the world
3. The ease with which the product can be prepared and cooked
4. The presence of non-edible parts such as bones, scales, shells
5. The health benefits of the product
6. The presence/absence of colourants
7. Whether the product is familiar (i.e. has been tried before)
8. Whether the product is something that everyone in a consumer's household likes to eat
9. The price of the product
10. Whether the product comes from a sustainable source
11. The freshness of the product
12. The quality of the product
13. The self-efficacy of the consumer in relation to storing, preparing, and cooking the product
14. The production method (whether the product comes from an aquaculture or wild source)

The first twelve factors on the above list and their effects were examined using a simple Likert scale question format which required respondents to specify the importance of each factor to them when they are selecting fresh seafood to buy. The results of this component of the survey are presented below.

Questions that measured respondents' self-efficacy with regards to storing, preparing, and cooking seafood products are addressed in section 7.2.3.

It was not possible to use a simple Likert scale to examine consumers' preference for wild-caught or aquaculture-produced seafood. Thus, the barrier/driver 'production method' was dealt with separately in section 7.4.

Please note that, as highlighted in Part 1 of this report, not all of these factors are well-defined (namely sustainability, freshness, and quality). The survey thus also sought information on how consumers make judgements about these characteristics: the results of this element of the survey can be found in section 7.2.2.

Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 below show the results obtained when respondents in each of the three countries were asked to rate the importance of each of the first twelve factors listed above. The vertical line on each graph marks the division between the positive responses (i.e. 5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale), and the negative (1, 2, or 3 on the Likert scale) and neutral (4 on the Likert scale) responses.

In addition to the bar charts, the results are also summarised in tabular form: for each of the three countries' results, the factors were ranked according to the percentage of respondents who allocated a positive Likert scale score (5, 6, or 7). These rank order lists and the related percentages for each country are shown in *Table 11, Table 12, and Table 13*.

Denmark

Figure 7 Percentage of respondents in Denmark who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate how important 12 different characteristics of fresh seafood are when they are selecting products to buy

Table 11 The rank order of barriers and drivers according to the percentage of respondents in Denmark who allocated a positive Likert scale score

Rank	Barrier/driver	Percentage of respondents who selected a positive Likert scale score
1	It is of high quality	83.8
2	It is fresh	82.4
3	It is easy to prepare and cook	74.9
4	The price	73.9
5	It is something everyone in my household likes	72.7
6	It has health benefits	71.6
7	No colourants have been added	69.3
8	All non-edible parts (e.g. bones, shell. Scales) have been removed	64.2
9	It is produced in Europe rather than outside of Europe	60.1
10	It comes from a sustainable source	59.8
11	It is produced in Denmark rather than a different European country	55.5
12	It is something that that you have tried before	54.3

Italy

Figure 8 Percentage of respondents in Italy who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate how important 12 different characteristics of fresh seafood are when they are selecting products to buy

Table 12 The rank order of barriers and drivers according to the percentage of respondents in Italy who allocated a positive Likert scale score

Rank	Barrier/driver	Percentage of respondents who selected a positive Likert scale score
1	It is of high quality	86.7
2	It is fresh	84.9
3	No colourants have been added	84.0
4	It has health benefits	83.6
5	It is something everyone in my household likes	83.1
6	The price	81.1
7	It is easy to prepare and cook	78.8
8	It comes from a sustainable source	74.7
9	It is produced in Italy rather than a different European country	73.9
10	All non-edible parts (e.g. bones, shell. Scales) have been removed	69.9
11	It is something that that you have tried before	69.1
12	It is produced in Europe rather than outside of Europe	67.3

Slovenia

Figure 9 Percentage of respondents in Slovenia who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate how important 12 different characteristics of fresh seafood are when they are selecting products to buy

Table 13 The rank order of barriers and drivers according to the percentage of respondents in Slovenia who allocated a positive Likert scale score

Rank	Barrier/driver	Percentage of respondents who selected a positive Likert scale score
1	It is fresh	87.8
2	It is of high quality	87.3
3	It has health benefits	82.6
4	The price	79.3
5	No colourants have been added	79.2
6	It is something everyone in my household likes	78.5
7	It is easy to prepare and cook	74.4
8	All non-edible parts (e.g. bones, shell, scales) have been removed	73.3
9	It is something that that you have tried before	67.0
10	It comes from a sustainable source	63.7
11	It is produced in Europe rather than outside of Europe	61.9
12	It is produced in Slovenia rather than a different European country	51.3

In all three countries the freshness of the produce and the quality of the produce appeared in the first two ranked positions. In Denmark these two factors also received the highest percentages of '7 - very important' scores (41.9% and 35.6% of respondents, respectively).

The absence of added colourants in fresh seafood products was also found to be of high importance, particularly in Italy where almost as many respondents scored it within the positive range (84.0%) as they did the factor 'freshness' (84.9%). Furthermore,

in Italy, a higher proportion of respondents stated that the absence of colourants was 'very important' (a Likert score of 7) than any other factor (43.1%). In Denmark, whilst the absence of colourants received the seventh highest percentage of positive Likert scale scores, it received the third greatest percentage of highest scores (i.e. 7 – 'very important'). Similarly in Slovenia, the absence of added colourants received the fifth highest percentage of positive scores (5, 6, or 7) and the second highest percentage of '7 – very important' scores.

It can be observed that, in Italy, there was a general tendency to rate factors as important (rather than not important or of neutral importance), compared to in Denmark and Slovenia. More than 80% of respondents gave six of the factors a score of 5, 6, or 7; in Denmark and Slovenia more than 80% of respondents gave only two and three factors, respectively, a positive score.

7.2.2 How do consumers define the sustainability, freshness and quality of fresh seafood?

As highlighted in the literature reviews and noted above, whilst a number of barriers to and drivers of seafood purchase and consumption are commonly cited and accepted in the available literature, it is not easy to find clear definitions for all of these factors. Relevant to the FishEUTrust project, and therefore examined further within the context of the survey, were the terms 'freshness', 'quality', and 'sustainable'. Respondents were first asked to specify the degree to which these three factors are important when they are choosing chilled seafood to buy (as reported in Section 7.2.1). All respondents who selected 5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale (i.e. a positive response) were then directed to a series of questions about the features that are important to them when making judgements about a chilled seafood product's sustainability, freshness, and quality. The results obtained in relation to these follow-on questions are outlined in the three sub-sections below.

The features that are important in judging sustainability

According to a report on consumer trends produced by the Norwegian Seafood Council (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2021), sustainability is a concept. Thus, what individuals associate with sustainability and how it is understood varies. One of the aims of the survey was to help unpick what this understanding is across the three survey countries.

The number of respondents in each of the three countries who selected 5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale when asked if sustainability is an important factor when choosing chilled seafood to buy was:

- 602 of the 1006 respondents in Denmark (59.4%)
- 757 of the 1014 respondents in Italy (74.7%)
- 643 of the 1010 respondents in Slovenia (63.7%)

Having provided this positive response they were then shown a series of eight features and asked to rate, again using a seven-point Likert scale, how important each feature is to them when they are judging whether a chilled seafood product comes from a sustainable source (1 = not at all important; 4 = neutral; 7 = very important). The eight features were:

1. The certification that the product has
2. The product's country of origin
3. The brand of the product
4. The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)
5. The type of seafood product (whether it is a finfish, shellfish, crustacean, cephalopod)
6. The specific species of finfish, shellfish, crustacean, or cephalopod (whether it's a salmon or a tuna, whether it's a mussel or an oyster, etc.)
7. The catch method
8. Whether the product is wild or farmed

Figure 10, Figure 11, and Figure 12 show the results obtained in relation to these questions in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia, respectively.

Figure 10 Percentage of respondents in Denmark (to whom sustainability is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product comes from a sustainable source

Figure 11 Percentage of respondents in Italy (to whom sustainability is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product comes from a sustainable source

Figure 12 Percentage of respondents in Slovenia (to whom sustainability is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product comes from a sustainable source

A key observation from these three figures is that all of the features appear to play an important role in helping consumers to make judgements about whether a product comes from a sustainable source. The difference between the percentages of respondents using the first three points on the Likert scale to indicate that the features are not important is markedly lower than the percentages using the upper three points to indicate that they are important. Of all of the features, the brand of the produce claimed the lowest number of positive scores (5, 6, or 7) and the lowest number of '7 – very important' scores in all three countries; even so, the majority (62.5% in Denmark, 77.8% in Italy, and 70.4% in Slovenia) stated that this was an important feature.

The features that are important in judging freshness

As highlighted in the literature reviews and stakeholder interviews, there are a number of features that consumers may use to judge a product's freshness; principally the best before date and various sensory characteristics such as smell and appearance. To provide a closer examination of precise features that are important to consumers, all those who responded that freshness is important when choosing chilled seafood to buy (see section 7.2.1), were shown a series of six features and asked to rate, again using a seven-point Likert scale, how important each feature is to them when they are judging the freshness of a chilled seafood product (1 = not at all important; 4 = neutral; 7 = very important).

The number of respondents in each of the three countries who selected 5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale when asked if freshness is an important factor when choosing chilled seafood to buy was:

- 829 of the 1006 respondents in Denmark (82.4%)
- 861 of the 1014 respondents in Italy (84.9%)
- 887 of the 1010 respondents in Slovenia (87.8%)

The six features important in judging freshness that these respondents were then asked about were:

1. The best before or the use by date
2. The appearance of the product
3. The smell of the product
4. The brand of the product
5. The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)
6. The way in which the product is displayed (e.g. on ice at fishmonger or shop's fish counter, or packaged on supermarket shelf)

Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15 show the results obtained in relation to these questions in Denmark, Italy and Slovenia, respectively.

Figure 13 Percentage of respondents in Denmark (to whom freshness is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of six features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product is fresh

Figure 14 Percentage of respondents in Italy (to whom freshness is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of six features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product is fresh

Figure 15 Percentage of respondents in Slovenia (to whom freshness is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of six features of fresh seafood when they are judging whether a seafood product is fresh

All of the features played a role for more than half of the respondents (for whom freshness is an important characteristic when choosing seafood to buy) in all three countries. However, it appears that some of the features are distinctly more relevant than others.

Across all three countries the most salient features used by consumers to make an assessment about freshness appear to be the best before or use by date, the appearance of the product, and the smell of the product. The latter feature is intriguing as presumably often products are wrapped or out of reach of the consumer at the point of purchase and cannot be smelt. In each country over 85% of respondents stated that these features are important (5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale) and at least 44% stated that they were 'very important'.

In all three countries the feature 'brand' received the highest proportion of negative responses (i.e. 1, 2, and 3 on the Likert scale) and the highest proportion of 'neutral' responses (i.e. 4 on the Likert scale). This indicates that the brand of the produce is an important defining feature of freshness to fewer consumers than all of the other features.

The features that are important in judging quality

As described in section 3.3.6, the perceived quality of seafood is a further factor which influences consumers' choices, but which is ill-defined. It appears that quality is a somewhat amorphous virtue which can be stated as a driver or barrier in its own right (Senior & Stewardson, 2019) but which can also be attributed to produce with a particular origin (e.g., (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), (Untilov & Ganassali, 2017)), production method (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Director-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ed.), 2016)), brand (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016), degree of freshness (Lamy & Szejda, 2020), or capture method (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016).

To provide a closer examination of precise features that are important to consumers, all those who responded that quality is important when choosing seafood to buy (see section 7.2.1), were shown a series of eight features and asked to rate, again using a seven-point Likert scale, how important each feature is to them when they are judging the quality of a chilled seafood product (1 = not at all important; 4 = neutral; 7 = very important).

The number of respondents in each of the three countries who selected 5, 6, or 7 on the Likert scale when asked if quality is an important factor when choosing chilled seafood to buy was:

- 843 of the 1006 respondents in Denmark (83.8%)
- 879 of the 1014 respondents in Italy (86.7%)
- 887 of the 1010 respondents in Slovenia (87.8%)

The eight features important in judging quality that these respondents were asked about were:

1. The country of origin
2. The catch method

3. Whether the product was farmed or wild caught
4. The certifications that the product has
5. The appearance of the product
6. The brand of the product
7. The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)
8. The way in which the product is displayed (e.g. on ice at fishmonger or shop's fish counter, or packaged on supermarket shelf)

Figure 16, Figure 17, and Figure 18 show the results obtained in relation to these questions in Denmark, Italy and Slovenia, respectively.

Figure 16 Percentage of respondents in Denmark (to whom quality is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging the quality of a seafood product

Figure 17 Percentage of respondents in Italy (to whom quality is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging the quality of a seafood product

Figure 18 Percentage of respondents in Slovenia (to whom quality is important) who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when asked to rate the importance of eight features of fresh seafood when they are judging the quality of a seafood product

In all three countries more than half of the respondents (for whom quality is an important characteristic when choosing seafood to buy) gave a score of 5, 6, or 7 to all of the features they were asked about; none were primarily considered irrelevant. One feature in particular elicited a high score from respondents: the appearance of a product. In all of the countries, over 90% of the respondents who answered this question gave a Likert scale score of 5, 6, or 7 and over 46% stated that it was 'very important' (i.e. a score of 7). These were the highest scores of any of the features, thus highlighting the importance of this feature to consumers. The brand of the product and the catch method were the two features which attracted the highest proportion of respondents to a negative Likert scale score (1, 2, or 3) or a neutral response (4).

7.2.3 Self-efficacy

According to the literature reviews carried out in task 2.1 (section 3.3.3), consumers' perceived ability to prepare and cook the produce at home plays a role in determining whether people purchase and consume fish and seafood and, if so, how much (e.g., (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016), (Bruns, 2009), (Lamy & Szejda, 2020), (Ivoninskii, 2016), (Senior & Stewardson, 2019)). Self-efficacy is related to the driver/barrier 'convenience'. If fish and seafood is seen as difficult to prepare and cook, it is viewed as being less convenient than easier options, and this negatively affects consumption (Senior & Stewardson, 2019).

The survey asked respondents two questions related to self-efficacy. The first asked respondents to rate their level of knowledge about how fresh seafood should be stored on a scale from 1 (no knowledge) to 7 (very good knowledge). *Figure 19* shows the results obtained in relation to this question. It can be seen that little difference was observed between the three countries in terms of respondents' self-efficacy in relation to the storage of fresh seafood.

Figure 19 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = no knowledge; 7 = very good knowledge) when asked to rate their knowledge about how fresh seafood should be stored

The second self-efficacy question asked respondents to rate their skills in preparing and cooking fresh seafood using a scale from 1 (no skills) to 7 (very good skills). *Figure 20* shows the results obtained in relation to this question. It can be seen that, again, the results obtained in the three countries were similar; this is particularly the case for Denmark and Slovenia for which the greatest percentage point difference between the two countries for any given point on the Likert scale was 2.4%. A slightly higher proportion of respondents in Italy (67.0%) answered using the higher Likert scale scores (5, 6, and 7) compared to either Denmark (59.0%) or Slovenia (59.1%), indicating a slightly higher self-efficacy in Italy in relation to fresh seafood preparation and cooking.

Figure 20 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = no skill; 7 = very good skills) when asked to rate their skills in preparing and cooking fresh seafood

7.3 Frequency of purchase and purchasing preferences

Respondents were asked a series of questions about their purchasing habits in relation to seafood products; these related to the frequency with which they purchase different types of seafood, how frequently it is purchased from different types of retailer, and how frequently seafood that has been pre-prepared to varying degrees is purchased.

7.3.1 Purchasing frequency of different seafood types

The first of these questions asked respondents to indicate how frequently they purchased different types of seafood (finfish, shellfish, cephalopods, and crustaceans) using an ordinal scale. Please note that the inclusion criteria for the survey stipulated that respondents must be consumers of seafood products. Furthermore, if 'once a month or less often' was the response for all four of the seafood types, the survey ended and responses were not included. This was to ensure that the results were reflective of seafood consumers rather than non-consumers or those who consume it very infrequently. The results of this question can be seen in *Figure 21* and are discussed below.

Finfish

Of the four seafood categories presented, finfish received the lowest proportion of 'never' responses in all three countries. When the responses relating to finfish are viewed in isolation, the option which received the highest proportion of responses in all three countries was 'once a month or less often' (33.1% in Denmark, 30.3% in Italy, and 46.6% in Slovenia). The proportions of responses then declined across the remaining options with 'every day or almost every day' receiving the smallest share of responses.

The results show that of the three countries' respondents, those in Italy were most likely to purchase finfish once a week or more frequently (37.4% of respondents chose an option between 'once a week' and 'every day or almost every day'). In Denmark this figure was 35.6% and in Slovenia it was 20.6%.

Shellfish

The proportions of respondents in Denmark and Slovenia who claimed that they never purchase shellfish (39.2% and 41.1% respectively) were markedly higher than in Italy (10.6%). In Denmark 'never' was the most common response and in Slovenia both 'never' and 'once a month or less often' (41.6%) were most commonly claimed. In Italy the most common response was 'once a month or less often' (39.6%) and the proportions of responses then declined across the remaining options.

Of the three countries' respondents, those in Italy were most likely to purchase shellfish once a week or more frequently (24.1% of respondents chose an option between 'once a week' and 'every day or almost every day'). In Denmark this figure was 17.3% and in Slovenia it was 7.9%.

Cephalopods

In Denmark 60.6% of respondents stated that they never purchase cephalopods; this compares to just 12.6% in Italy and 21.7% in Slovenia. In both Italy and Slovenia the most common response was 'once a month or less often' (45.3% and 53.7% respectively). The general trend observed is that following the modal response, each remaining response received a declining proportion of responses; the exception to this trend is that in Denmark a slightly higher proportion of respondents stated that they purchase cephalopods '4 – 5 times per week' (4.4%) compared to the proportion who answered '2 – 3 times per week' (3.4%).

Of the three countries' respondents, those in Italy were most likely to purchase cephalopods once a week or more frequently (20.6% of respondents). In Denmark this figure was 12.7% and in Slovenia it was 10.0%.

Crustaceans

The 'once a month or less often' response received the largest proportion of responses in all three countries (43.1% in Denmark, 42.7% in Italy, and 46.6% in Slovenia). In Denmark the next most common responses were '2 – 3 times per month' (19.8%) and 'never' (17.3%). In Italy the next most common responses were '2 – 3 times per month' (23.1%), then 'once a week' (14.0%), and, in fourth place, 'never' (13.4%). In Slovenia, 'never' took a relatively large share of the responses (30.9%) and all other proportions were less than 15%.

A slightly higher proportion of respondents in Italy compared to Denmark responded that they purchase crustaceans once a week or more frequently (20.8% compared to 19.8%). Slovenia again exhibited the lowest proportion of frequent purchasers (9.7%).

Figure 21 Percentage of responses at each point on an ordinal scale when respondents in each country were asked how frequently they purchase fin fish, shellfish, cephalopods, and crustaceans

7.3.2 Purchasing frequency of seafood from different types of retailer

The second question relating to purchasing behaviours asked respondents to indicate how frequently they purchased seafood of any type from three different types of retailer (fishmonger, fish market, and supermarket). Again, an ordinal scale was used. The results obtained can be seen in Figure 22.

Across all three retailer types and all countries, in all but one case the most frequently selected option was 'once a month or less often' (the percentages ranged from 22.9% to 48.3%). The exception was that a slightly higher proportion of Italian

respondents chose the 'once a week' option for fish markets (24.2% compared to the 22.9% who selected the 'once a month or less often' option). Unsurprisingly, a relatively small proportion of respondents reported shopping for seafood products in any of the three types of retailer twice a week or more (between 5.5% and 26.6%).

Figure 22 Percentage of responses at each point on an ordinal scale when respondents in each country were asked how frequently they purchase seafood from a fishmonger, fish market or supermarket

7.3.3 Purchasing frequency of seafood which has undergone differing degrees and types of processing

The third question relating to purchasing behaviours asked respondents to indicate how frequently they purchased seafood of any type that has undergone various levels/types of processing. They were asked how frequently they purchase whole fish (i.e. including bones, scales, etc), fish fillets or steaks, seafood prepared with breadcrumbs, batter or sauce, frozen seafood, tinned seafood, and pickled seafood. The results obtained can be seen in *Figure 23* and are discussed below.

Whole fish

A markedly greater proportion of Danish respondents reported that they never purchased whole fish (42.4%) compared to respondents in either Italy (24.9%) or Slovenia (21.1%). Indeed, in Denmark 'never' was the most popular response whereas in both Italy and Slovenia the most common response was 'once a month or less often' (32.7% of respondents in Italy and 47.9% of respondents in Slovenia).

A greater proportion of the Italian respondents purchase whole fish once a week or more frequently (22.6%) than either the Danish or Slovenian samples (17.8% and 12.3%, respectively).

In all three countries, the proportion of responses declined across the ordinal scale from the mode (in the case of Denmark the modal group was 'never', and for Italy and Slovenia it was once a month or more frequently).

Fillets or steaks

As was the case for whole fish, a higher proportion of Danish respondents reported that they never purchased fish fillets or steaks (21.4%) compared to respondents in either Italy (7.5%) or Slovenia (10.6%). The 7.5% response rate seen in Italy was the lowest 'never' response rate seen across all categories of seafood that respondents were asked about in this series of questions.

The country where the highest proportion of respondents reported purchasing fillets or steaks once a week or more frequently was Italy (30.0%), second was Denmark (20.7%), and third was Slovenia (15.9%). The modal response across all three countries was 'once a month or less often' (37.1% in Denmark, 34.0% in Italy, and 48.4% in Slovenia).

Seafood prepared with breadcrumbs, batter, or sauce

Seafood pre-prepared with breadcrumbs, batter, or sauce is least popular in Slovenia: 79.2% of Slovenian respondents stated either that they never purchased such products or that they did so '2 – 3 times per month' or less often. This compares to a rate of 64.7% in Denmark and 65.1% in Italy.

The modal response to this question differed across the three countries. In Denmark, 40.1% of respondents answered '2 – 3 times per month' or less often; a response rate that was just over 15 percentage points higher than for any other item on the ordinal scale. In Italy and Slovenia, the proportions of responses were more equally distributed between the 'never' category and '2 – 3 times per month' or less often.

Frozen seafood

The lowest rate of 'never' responses to this question was seen in Italy (8.3% of respondents); this is compared to a rate of 17.9% in Denmark and 20.6% in Slovenia. The most popular response in both Denmark and Slovenia was '2 – 3 times per month' or less often (44.1% and 51.4%, respectively). In Italy, however, there was evidence that respondents are more frequent purchasers of frozen seafood: in addition to the comparatively low rate of 'never' responses, the '2 – 3 times per month' or less often and 'once a week' options received comparable proportions of responses (33.2% and 30.1% respectively) and the '2 – 3 times per week' option received a notably higher proportion of Italy's responses (18.5%) compared to the response rates in Denmark (9.7%) and Slovenia (6.9%).

Tinned seafood

Italy's 'never' response rate to the question of how frequently they purchase tinned seafood (12.0%) was lower than either Denmark's (21.5%) or Slovenia's (19.3%). The three countries' response rates for the 'once a month or less often' and the '2 – 3 times per month' or less often options were not dissimilar. Italy's response rate for the 'once a week' option (20.1%) was greater than that of Denmark (11.1%) or Slovenia (12.8%). The response rates to the remaining categories did not differ markedly, but when the three high frequency options ('every day or almost every day', '4 – 5 times per week', and '2 – 3 times per week') were added together, there is evidence of slightly higher proportions of high frequency tinned seafood consumers in Denmark (10.2%) and Italy (11.0%) than in Slovenia (5.4%).

Pickled seafood

A notably high proportion of respondents in Slovenia do not purchase pickled seafood at all (58.0%). This compared to a 'never' response rate of 41.8% in Italy and only 22.1% in Denmark. Whereas 'never' was the most common response in both Slovenia and Italy, in Denmark the modal group was 'once a month or less often', at 44.1%. 85.4% of Slovenian respondents chose one of the zero frequency or very low frequency options compared to 63.1% in Denmark and 71.9% in Italy. As would be expected given these figures, the highest proportion of high frequency consumers (once a week or more often) was seen in Denmark (19.0%); the second highest was in Italy (15.4%) and the lowest in Slovenia (8.4%).

Figure 23 Percentage of responses at each point on an ordinal scale when respondents in each country were asked how frequently they purchase seafood that has undergone different degrees and types of processing

7.4 Knowledge and perceptions of aquaculture

7.4.1 Self-reported knowledge

Respondents were asked a series of questions relating to their knowledge about seafood production methods and various certifications. Understanding what level of knowledge exists within the general population is important if this knowledge is to be relied upon to develop communication campaigns or marketing strategies which seek to promote or shape specific purchasing or consumption patterns. For example, one cannot necessarily rely on people's positive response to the Aquaculture Stewardship Council logo appearing on a fish product if some understanding of what aquaculture is and what the certification means is not in place.

Respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement with seven statements on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree). The order in which respondents were presented with the seven statements was randomised. The pattern of responses to each of these statements is outline below.

Statement 1 - I know what the term aquaculture means in relation to fish production

Figure 24 shows that, of the three sample groups, Danish respondents had a greater tendency to disagree or strongly disagree with this statement (46.5%) than either Italian (22.0%) or Slovenian (21.4%) respondents. The proportion of Danish respondents who strongly disagreed (25.8%) was also more than three times that of either Italian (7.8%) or Slovenian (7.3%) respondents. Conversely 57.4% of Italian respondents agreed or strongly agreed compared to 43.1% of Slovenian and 30.6% of Danish respondents. The highest proportion of responses that were neutral (neither agree nor disagree) was seen for the Slovenian sample (35.5% compared to 22.9% for Denmark and 20.6% for Italy).

Figure 24 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the term aquaculture means in relation to fish production'

Statement 2 - I know whether the seafood that I buy comes from a fish farm or is wild-caught

As for the previous question relating to knowledge about aquaculture, Figure 25 shows that, of the three countries' samples, the Danish respondents were more prone to disagreeing with this statement (31.0%) than either the Italian (19.23%) or Slovenian (18.0%) respondents, and they were also less prone to agreeing with it (43.0% compared to 56.2% of Italian and 54.4% of Slovenian respondents). The strength of feeling also appeared greater in the Danish sample, with 14.6% strongly disagreeing compared to 6.3% and 5.7% in Italy and Slovenia, respectively.

Figure 25 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know whether the seafood that I buy comes from a fish farm or is wild caught'

Statement 3 - I know what the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) logo on seafood products means

Figure 26 shows that overall, a lower proportion of respondents in Slovenia disagreed with this statement (23.0%) compared to those in Denmark (41.5%) or Italy (41.6%). Furthermore, the greatest difference was seen for the 'strongly disagree' response (only 7.1% in Slovenia compared to 22.3% and 19.2% in Denmark and Italy, respectively). Slovenian respondents also exhibited the highest agreement rate (44.8% compared to 37.1% in Denmark and 34.2% in Italy) and the highest rate of neutral responses (32.3% compared to 21.5% in Denmark and 24.2% in Italy).

Figure 26 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) logo on seafood products means'

Statement 4 - I know what the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) logo on seafood products means

The pattern exhibited by Figure 27 is similar to that exhibited in Figure 26. This is not surprising – the MSC and ASC badges could be thought of as equivalent certifications for wild and farmed seafood (Ecocert, 2021). Mirroring the results observed for statement 3, overall, Slovenian respondents appeared to have more knowledge about what the ASC logo means than respondents in either Denmark or Italy: 43.5% of Slovenian respondents agreed with the statement compared to 30.7% of Danish and 32.9% of Italian respondents, and only 23.1% disagreed compared to 45.3% of the Danish sample and 44.3% of the Italian sample. Once again, Slovenian respondents also exhibited the highest neutral response rate (33.5% compared to 24.0% in Denmark and 22.8% in Italy).

Figure 27 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) logo on seafood products means'

Statement 5 - I know what the organic label on seafood products means

Figure 28 shows that the responses to this statement given by respondents in Italy and Slovenia were similar; the biggest percentage point difference between these two samples for any given Likert scale score was 2.6 (for the Likert scale value 6). Overall, respondents in Denmark were more likely to disagree with the statement (30.2% compared to 19.9% in Italy and 17.7% in Slovenia), and less likely to agree with it (45.8% compared to 53.7% in Italy and 54.1% in Slovenia).

Figure 28 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the organic label on seafood products means'

Statement 6 - I know what the Friend of the Sea (FOS) logo on seafood products means

As can be seen in Figure 29, of the three countries' respondents, those who were the most inclined to disagree and least inclined to agree with this statement were Denmark's; almost half (47.1%) responded negatively and only 30.9% responded positively. In contrast, only 21.6% of Slovenia's sample disagreed and 46.9% agreed. Italy's agreement and disagreement rates fell between those of Denmark and Slovenia at 38.2% and 37.8%, respectively.

Figure 29 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the Friend of the Sea (FOS) label on seafood products means'

Statement 7 - I know what the Fairtrade logo on seafood products means

Figure 30 shows that there did not appear to be marked differences between respondents' understanding of what the Fairtrade logo on seafood products means in the three countries.

Figure 30 Percentage of respondents who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with the statement 'I know what the Fairtrade logo on seafood products means'

Summary of findings – self-reported knowledge

Respondents in Denmark had a general tendency to disagree more commonly with the statements about knowledge than respondents in either Italy or Slovenia. This was the case for four of the seven statements (1, 2, 5, and 6) and, for a further two (statements 3 and 4), respondents in Denmark and Italy provided similar responses whilst respondents in Slovenia were more positive. Respondents in Slovenia tended to agree most commonly with the knowledge statements (3, 4, 6). There was a much less well-defined pattern for respondents in Italy: in one case, Italian respondents gave the most positive responses overall (statement 1) but for other statements responses were either somewhere between those of Denmark and Italy (statement 6), at the more negative end of the spectrum along with those of Danish respondents (statements 3 and 4), or at the more positive end with Slovenian respondents (statements 2 and 5). There was little difference between the countries for the final statement about Fairtrade.

The mean rates of agreement and disagreement revealed that the three statements that respondents across all three countries agreed with the most commonly were statements 2, 5, and 7. Unsurprisingly, these were also the statements that respondents, on average, disagreed with the least.

7.4.2 Preferences for aquaculture-produced or wild-caught seafood and comparisons between the two

The literature reviews and stakeholder interviews reported that a common finding in previous research has been that in general consumers state a preference for wild-caught fish and seafood over farmed (e.g., (Special Eurobarometer 515, 2021)). However, there is also a recognition that there are variations across different countries (Sveinsdóttir, et al., 2016) and socio-demographic groups (e.g., (Altintzoglou, et al., 2016)). There was also evidence that, in many cases, consumers do not seem to know whether the seafood that they purchase is wild or farmed and may not be entirely clear on the distinction (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2016).

Preferences for aquaculture-produced and wild-caught seafood

The survey examined the preferences that exist for wild-caught and farmed seafood in the three focus countries. Using a simple nominal question format, respondents were asked which of the four following options was most accurate for them (the order of presentation of these options was randomised across participants):

- I prefer to buy farmed seafood over wild-caught seafood
- I prefer to buy wild-caught seafood over farmed seafood
- It makes no difference to me whether the seafood that I buy is farmed or wild-caught
- I do not know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood

The results pertaining to this question are presented in *Figure 31*. It can be seen that the most evident preference for wild-caught seafood was observed in Italy, where 50.2% of the respondents stated this preference, compared to 11.7% of respondents who stated that they preferred farmed seafood and 31.6% who stated that they do not have a preference. In

Denmark and Slovenia there appears to be a higher degree of ambivalence, with the proportion of respondents stating a preference for wild-caught seafood (36.8% in Denmark and 39.6% in Slovenia) more narrowly exceeding those who do not have a preference (32.7% in Denmark and 38.1%). A relatively small proportion of respondents in all three countries stated a preference for farmed seafood.

The percentages of respondents who stated that they do not know the difference between wild-caught and farmed seafood were 14.1% in Denmark, 11.7% in Italy, and 11.1% in Slovenia. Of course, these figures represent only those people who know that they do not know the difference; it does not capture those who have an inaccurate perception.

Figure 31 Preferences for wild-caught or farmed seafood in each surveyed country as percentages of the total surveyed sample in each

All respondents except those who answered 'I do not know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood' to the previous question were then asked to answer a series of nominal questions relating to their perceptions of the safety, taste, environmental impact, and quality of wild-caught and farmed seafood, and the animal-welfare associated with each production method. For each of these characteristics, three statements were presented (in a randomised order) and respondents were asked to select the one that they thought was most accurate. The results obtained in relation to these questions are outlined in the following section.

Comparisons of wild-caught and aquaculture-derived seafood

Wild-caught versus farmed seafood: Safety

Respondents were presented with the following three statements and asked to select the one that they thought most accurate.

- Farmed seafood is safer to eat than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the safety of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood is safer to eat than farmed seafood

The results are presented in *Figure 32*. In all three countries, the proportion of respondents who thought that there is no difference between the safety level of wild-caught as opposed to farmed seafood was greater than either the proportion that thought wild-caught is safer or the proportion that thought farmed is safer. The strength of this sentiment differs from country to country, however: in Denmark, 59.8% of respondents were of this opinion, in Italy it was 51.0%, and in Slovenia it was just 44.4%.

A comparison of the percentages of respondents who thought that either farmed or wild-caught seafood is safer is interesting. In Denmark, an almost equal proportion of the respondents were of each of these opinions (19.6% and 20.6%, respectively). In Italy, a greater proportion of respondents thought that farmed seafood is safer (31.9% compared to 17.9% for wild-caught seafood). In Slovenia, this trend was reversed, with a higher proportion of respondents stating that wild-caught fish is safer (32.7% compared to 23.0% for farmed).

Figure 32 Distribution of respondents' responses (those who feel they know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood) in each country to a nominal question which asked about the safety of seafood

Wild-caught versus farmed seafood: Taste

The three statements presented to respondents were:

- Farmed seafood tastes better than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the taste of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood tastes better than farmed seafood

The results are presented in Figure 33. It can be seen that the pattern of responses in Italy and Slovenia is the same: the most common response was that wild seafood tastes better than farmed (56.0% in Italy and 55.2% in Slovenia). The second most common response in each case was that there is no difference in taste (29.9% in Italy and 32.7% in Slovenia). Relatively few respondents thought that farmed seafood tastes better (14.1% in Italy and 12.2% in Slovenia).

The pattern of responses in Denmark is a little different. Although, as in Italy and Slovenia, relatively few respondents thought that farmed seafood tastes better than wild-caught (16.4%), the proportions of those who thought that there is no difference and those who thought wild-caught tastes best were very similar, with the 'no difference' option slightly leading (43.4% compared to 40.1%).

Figure 33 Distribution of respondents' responses (those who feel they know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood) in each country to a nominal question which asked about the taste of seafood

Wild-caught versus farmed seafood: Environmental impact

The three statements presented to respondents were:

- Farming seafood is less harmful to the environment than catching wild seafood
- There is no difference in the environmental effects of wild and farmed seafood production
- Catching wild seafood is less harmful to the environment than farming seafood

The results are presented in *Figure 34*. Once again, the results for Italy and Slovenia display the same pattern whereas Denmark's results are different. In Italy and Slovenia, the highest proportion of respondents thought that farming seafood is less harmful to the environment than catching wild seafood (40.3% in Italy and 37.7% in Slovenia). In Denmark, the biggest proportion of respondents thought that there is no difference (41.0%) and the proportion who thought that catching wild seafood is less harmful actually exceeded the proportion who thought that farming is less harmful.

Figure 34 Distribution of respondents' responses (those who feel they know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood) in each country to a nominal question which asked about the environmental impact of seafood

Wild-caught versus farmed seafood: Quality

The three statements presented to respondents were:

- Farmed seafood is generally better quality than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the quality of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood is generally better quality than farmed seafood

The results are presented in *Figure 35*. In this case, the general pattern of responses in all three countries was the same. The biggest proportion of respondents felt that wild-caught seafood is generally better quality than farmed seafood (43.0% in Denmark, 50.0% in Italy, and 54.8% in Slovenia). The second largest proportion thought that there is no difference in quality (48.4% in Denmark, 33.5% in Italy, and 28.3% in Slovenia). In Denmark, the difference between the proportion that selected this option and that which selected the 'wild-caught seafood is better quality' option was smaller than in the other two countries. In all three cases, the smallest proportions of respondents felt that farmed seafood is better quality (18.5% in Denmark, 16.5% in Italy, and 16.8% in Slovenia).

Figure 35 Distribution of respondents' responses (those who feel they know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood) in each country to a nominal question which asked about the quality of seafood

Wild-caught versus farmed seafood: Animal welfare

The three statements presented to respondents were:

- The animal welfare of farmed seafood is better than that of wild seafood
- There is no difference between the animal welfare of wild and farmed seafood
- The animal welfare of wild seafood is better than that of farmed seafood

The results are presented in Figure 36. In Denmark and Slovenia, wild seafood is associated with better animal welfare than farmed seafood by the largest proportion of respondents (46.6% in Denmark and 47.3% in Slovenia). The smallest proportion of respondents in these two countries felt that farmed seafood was associated with better welfare (20.6% in Denmark and 19.8% in Slovenia).

In Italy, however, there was little difference between the percentages of respondents who selected each of the three options: between 30% and 35% of respondents selected each.

Figure 36 Distribution of respondents' responses (those who feel they know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood) in each country to a nominal question which asked about animal welfare in relation to seafood production

7.4.3 Perceptions about aquaculture

The final set of questions relating specifically to production methods examined respondents' perceptions of aquaculture itself rather than of the seafood that it produces. It was hoped that understanding these perceptions would be helpful in unpicking the preferences that consumers display for one production method over another.

Respondents were shown a series of 'claims' about aquaculture and were asked to specify the degree of truth that they felt the statements held using a seven-point Likert scale (1 = I think there is no truth in this, 4 = neutral, 7 = I think this claim is completely true). The six claims included in the survey were:

1. Pollutants are released from fish farms
2. Fish farming has a negative effect on biodiversity, natural habitats and ecosystems
3. Farmed seafood contains contaminants such as antibiotics or medicines
4. Fish farms have a negative effect on the way the environment looks
5. The feed used in fish farming comes from unsustainable sources
6. Diseases spread from fish farms to wild fish

Figure 37, Figure 38, and Figure 39 display the results obtained in each country relating to these questions.

Figure 37 Percentage of respondents in Denmark who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with six claims that are sometimes made about aquaculture

Figure 38 Percentage of respondents in Italy who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with six claims that are sometimes made about aquaculture

Figure 39 Percentage of respondents in Slovenia who responded at each point on a 7-point Likert scale when presented with six claims that are sometimes made about aquaculture

Almost without exception the Likert scale response that the highest proportion of respondents used was 4 – neutral, indicating that they felt that the claim was neither correct nor incorrect, or that they did not know. There were two exceptions: i) in Slovenia the Likert score ‘5’ received a slightly higher percentage of the responses (28.1%) than the Likert score ‘4’ for the contaminants claim; ii) the percentage of responses allocated to Likert scores ‘4’ and ‘5’ in Italy for this same claim were very close (28.3% and 27.2%).

Across all claims and all three countries, the proportion of respondents who used the positive values of the Likert scale (5, 6, and 7), indicating that there is some truth in the claims, was greater than the proportion who used the negative values of the scale (1, 2, and 3). In Slovenia, the sum total of the negative scores tended to be closer in value to the sum total of the positive scores than in either Denmark or Italy. In turn, in Italy, the sum total of the negative scores tended to be closer in value to the positive scores than in Denmark. These differences between the three countries suggest the existence of less negative feeling towards aquaculture in Denmark than in either Italy or Slovenia, and the highest level of negative feeling in Slovenia.

8. Cluster Analysis Findings

The next step of the analysis of the survey results consisted of the identification of profiles of consumers through a cluster analysis approach. The cluster analysis enabled identification in each country of groups of consumers who provided homogeneous responses to the questionnaire, the groups that presented the highest level of internal homogeneity and the highest degree of differentiation among them. Through cluster analysis, four groups of consumers were identified in Denmark and Slovenia, and five groups in Italy. Given the representativity of the samples of consumers included in the survey, results of the cluster analysis and the definition of the consumers' profiles can be extended to the populations of the three countries.

After the identification of the clusters, the answers provided by their members in the survey were investigated to assess four key sets of characteristics: socio-demographic and geographical factors; barriers to and drivers of their consumption of fish products; their knowledge and understanding of aspects related to food labels and aquaculture; and their perception of and preferences for wild-fish and aquaculture products. Also, the four sets of characteristics were categorised from the perspective of the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework (see section 2.2.2 for discussion of the use of the MOA framework).

The clusters were then labelled with a name reflecting their peculiar characteristics. In particular, the name reflects the degree of awareness of a cluster's members about aquaculture, the eventual degree of pragmatism (whether they prefer food items that are easy to prepare and cook), and their peculiar focus, if present.

Table 14 includes a detailed description of the items from the questionnaire included in the four sets of cluster characteristics. References to the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability framework are indicated in parentheses: M for Motivation, O for Opportunity, A for Ability.

Table 14 Key sets of characteristics of groups of consumers

Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics	Drivers of and barriers to fish consumption	Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling	Consumer perception and preferences for wild-fish and aquaculture products
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age Gender Education level Income class Employment status Household composition Type of settlement Distance from the coast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-perceived ability to store, prepare and cook seafood (A) Origin of the product (M) Price (M) Ease of cooking (O) Whether non-edible parts have been removed (O) Health benefits of the product (O) Presence of colourants (O) Product already tried by household members (O) Product liked by household members (O) Whether produced from sustainable source (O) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of term aquaculture (A) Know whether the fish is wild-caught or from aquaculture (A) Knowledge of the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) logo's meaning (A) Knowledge of Aquaculture Stewardship (ASC) meaning (A) Knowledge of organic label's meaning (A) Knowledge of Friends of the Sea (FOS) logo's meaning (A) Knowledge of Fair-Trade logo's meaning (A) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Typology of shop where fish products are purchased (O) Frequency of purchase of different typologies of fish products (O) Preference for farmed or wild fish Perception of safety of food products (A) Perception of taste of food products (A) Perception of environmental sustainability of food products (A) Perception of general quality of food products (A) Perception of animal welfare compliance of food products (A) Perception of different negative impacts of aquaculture (A)

- Freshness (O)
- Quality (O)

As discussed in section 7.2, respondents were asked to answer questions using 7-points Likert scales, where 1 indicated the lower level of accordance with the proposed statement and 7 indicated the highest. The description of answers provided to those questions is conducted through the average value of answers provided by each group of consumers. The differences between those values are all statistically significant.

Two sets of questions investigated the frequency of adoption of purchasing choices (section 7.3). Answers to those questions ranged from 1 (never) to 6 (4 - 5 times per week). Answers provided by respondents to those questions have been analysed through the average values for each cluster. The differences between those values are all statistically significant.

8.1 Denmark

The cluster analysis for Danish consumers led to the identification of four homogenous groups: the largest, Cluster 2, includes 59% of consumers and the other three, Cluster 1, Cluster 3, and Cluster 4, represent respectively 13.2%, 13.5%, and 14.3% of Danish consumers.

8.1.1 Socio-demographics and geographical characteristics

Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Danish clusters are described in *Table 15*.

Table 15 Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Danish clusters

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Name	Not aware and pragmatic	Aware, healthy, and focused on quality	Aware, healthy, and pragmatic	Aware, demanding, and wealthy
Share of the population	13.2%	59.0%	13.5%	14.3%
Average age (years)	48.5	42.6	50.1	37.1
Average household size	2.2	2.4	2.2	3
Members of the household under 18 years old	0.8	0.8	0.5	0.9
% of females	55.9%	46.2%	41.2%	55.8%
% of males	44.1%	53.6%	58.8%	44.2%
Education level				
Primary and Secondary education	29.7%	33.9%	26.4%	14.2%
Higher education (Bachelor)	44.2%	36.7%	37.7%	18.3%
Higher education (Master and PhD)	23.4%	29.0%	35.9%	67.5%
No answer	2.7%	0.6%	-	-
Employment status				
Self-employed (alone or with others)	7.0%	5.0%	7.0%	5.8%
Full time employee	43.2%	47.0%	45.6%	74.2%
Part-time/seasonal employee	11.6%	13.3%	10.5%	9.2%
Full time student	2.6%	3.8%	2.6%	0.8%
Unemployed/homemaker	7.9%	7.7%	7.9%	1.7%
Retired	24.5%	21.6%	24.6%	8.3%
Other	1.8%	1.6%	1.8%	-
Income level (monthly)⁶				

⁶ Values in € converted from DKK with the rate 1 DKK = 0.13 €

Up to 2.166 €	15.3%	17.1%	14.9%	5.0%
2.166 € - 4.333 €	30.6%	33.7%	18.4%	15.0%
4.333 € - 7.040 €	19.8%	21.2%	26.3%	22.5%
More than 7.040 €	22.5%	18.5%	26.3%	53.3%
Not declared	11.7%	9.5%	14.1%	4.2%
Place of residence				
Metropolitan City (> 1 million inhabitants)	7.2%	7.7%	8.8%	35.8%
City (100.000 – 1 million inhabitants)	14.4%	21.8%	20.2%	17.5%
Large town (20-100.000 inhabitants)	31.6%	34.7%	27.2%	24.2%
Small town	30.6%	23.4%	21.1%	15.0%
Village	9.9%	9.8%	10.5%	5.0%
Rural	6.3%	2.6%	12.3%	2.5%
Distance from the coast				
Living on the coast	22.5%	22.8%	29.0%	41.7%
Nearby (less than 30 minutes to reach the coast)	50.5%	42.5%	40.4%	32.5%
Not so far (30 to 60 minutes to reach the coast)	21.6%	22.8%	16.6%	17.5%
Not so close (1 to 2 hours to reach the coast)	5.4%	9.9%	14.0%	6.7%
Far away (more than 2 hours to reach the coast)	0%	2.0%	0	1.6%

Concerning socio-demographics and geographical characteristics, Cluster 3 presents the highest average age of its members, 50 years, while Cluster 4 includes the youngest share of respondents, with an average age of 37 years.

Cluster 4 also represents the largest households, with an average size of 3 members, followed by Cluster 2, with an average of 2.4 members per household, and by Cluster 1 and Cluster 3, including households with an average size of 2.2 members. The average number of underage household members is similar in clusters 1, 2, and 4 (0.8 to 0.9), while Cluster 3 represents the households with a lower average number of young members, 0.5. Finally, Cluster 1 and Cluster 4 include the relative majority of female members, about 56%, while in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 male respondents are the majority, respectively 53.6% and 58.8%.

Considering education level, Cluster 4 includes the most educated members, with 67.5% of them having a master's degree or PhD. Cluster 2, on the other hand, presents the highest share of respondents with a primary or secondary education degree, almost one third of the total.

"Full time employee" is by far the most common employment status among the Danish population, followed by "Retired". However, relevant differences are present among the four Clusters. Cluster 4 presents the largest share of "Full time employees" of the Danish context (74.2%) and the lowest share of "Retired" (8.3%), "Unemployed/homemaker" (1.7%), and "Full time students" (0.8%). The share of "Full time employees" is quite similar for the other three groups, ranging from 43.2% to 47%. Cluster 2 includes the highest share of "Part-time/seasonally employed" and "Full time students" of the four groups (13.3% and 3.8%). Cluster 4 is confirmed to be the wealthier group, with the largest share of respondents declaring a monthly income of more than 7.040 €. On the other side, Cluster 2 is the relatively less wealthy, with more than 50% of its members declaring an income up to 4.333 €, followed by Cluster 1 and Cluster 3, with about 45% and 33% of respondents declaring that income level.

Place of residence and distance from the coast differ consistently among the four clusters. Cluster 4 is the most urban, including more than 50% of members living in a city or a metropolis, and the smallest share of inhabitants of villages and rural areas of the four groups (7.5% total). The most rural group is Cluster 3, including 12.3% of members living in rural areas and 10.5% in villages. Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 are more balanced, with a majority of members living in small and large towns, ranging from 56.5% of Cluster 2 to 62.2% of Cluster 1.

Given the geographical characteristics of Denmark, most of its population lives near to or on the coast. However, some differences are registered between the four clusters. Cluster 4 is the group with the largest share of members living on the coast (41.7%), and the lowest number of members living more than one hour from the coast (8.3%). On the opposite side, Cluster 3 includes the largest share of members living far from the coast, with 14% of them living more than one hour from the sea.

8.1.2 Drivers of and barriers to fish consumption

Barriers to and drivers of fish consumption declared by Danish consumers are represented in *Table 16*. *Figure 40* describes drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, and *Figure 41* those related to Opportunity.

Table 16 Barriers and drivers for fish consumption for Danish Clusters (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Self-declared ability in storing	4.0	4.7	5.0	6.3
Self-declared ability in preparing and cooking	3.9	4.7	5.1	6.2
Importance of being produced in Denmark	4.5	4.6	5.1	6.1
Importance of being produced in Europe	4.6	4.8	5.4	6.2
Importance of price	5.6	5.1	5.5	6.2
Importance of ease of cooking	5.5	5.1	5.2	6.2
Importance of removal of inedible parts	5.1	4.8	4.7	6.0
Importance of health benefits	4.9	5.2	5.4	6.3
Importance of no dyes	5.1	5.2	6.1	6.4
Importance of being already tried	4.5	4.5	4.2	6
Importance of being liked in the household	5.4	5.3	5.5	6.2
Importance of sustainability	4.1	4.9	5.3	6.4
Importance of freshness	5.8	5.7	6.4	6.3
Importance of quality	5.6	5.7	6.4	6.4

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 40 Drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability for fish consumption for Danish clusters (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Considering the drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, price is the most relevant element for all of the Danish consumers. Regarding the other elements, members of Cluster 4 give a high level of importance to all of them, with average values greater than 6. On the opposite side, members of Cluster 1 are more sceptical about their ability to prepare and properly store fish products, and neutral about the importance of fish being produced in Denmark or Europe.

Members of Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 are similar in terms of this typology of drivers, with consumers of Cluster 4 giving more importance to a European origin of products. Concerning the other drivers, consumers included in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 attribute a moderate level of importance to all Motivation-related drivers and declare moderate levels of ability in storing and preparing fish products.

Figure 41 Drivers and barriers related to Opportunity for Danish clusters (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Considering drivers and barriers related to Opportunity, Cluster 4 includes the more demanding consumers, who attribute high levels of importance to all the elements, in particular quality, sustainability, and absence of dyes.

Freshness and quality are also considered very important by consumers of the other three groups, who are less interested in the other aspects, while registering a level of importance higher than neutrality. A relevant exception is represented by members of Cluster 1, who are, on average, neutral about the sustainability of fish products.

8.1.3 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling.

The different level of knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and food labelling related to fish products of members of the Danish clusters are described in *Table 17* and *Figure 42*.

Table 17 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture of Danish consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Knowledge of term aquaculture	1.3	3.8	3.2	6.1
Importance to know if wild or aquaculture fish	2.5	4.3	4.5	6.2
Knowledge of MSC logo meaning	1.5	4.0	3.7	6.3
Knowledge of ASC logo meaning	1.4	3.8	2.8	6.2
Knowledge of organic label meaning	2.0	4.6	3.9	6.4
Knowledge of FOS logo	1.4	3.8	2.6	6.3
Knowledge of Fair-Trade Logo meaning	2.8	4.6	4.4	6.4

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 42 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture of Danish consumers (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 4 are the most aware about aquaculture and the different sets of labels that are related to it. Also, they are highly concerned about knowledge of the source of fish products.

On the opposite side, members of Cluster 1 are the least involved and aware of the topic of aquaculture, having the lowest values for all the considered items.

Consumers included in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 are in the middle, being less aware about aquaculture compared to members of Cluster 4 but showing a relevant level of knowledge about the topic. Consumers in both groups give a moderate level of importance to knowing the source of fish products and they are quite aware of the meaning of the most common labels, such as organic and fair-trade. However, members of Cluster 2 have, on average, a deeper knowledge of labels directly designed for fish-based products.

8.1.4 Consumer perception and preferences for wild-fish and aquaculture products

Purchasing preferences and habits of Danish consumer clusters related to fish products are represented in *Table 18* and *Figure 43*.

Table 18 Purchasing preferences and habits of Danish consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Frequency of fish purchasing from fishmonger	1.7	2.4	2.0	3.9
Frequency of fish purchasing from fish market	1.4	2.1	1.5	3.8
Frequency of fish purchasing from supermarket	2.4	3.0	2.7	4.3
Frequency of purchasing of whole fish	1.5	2.3	1.8	3.8
Frequency of purchasing of fish fillets or steak	1.9	2.7	2.1	4.0
Frequency of purchasing of prepared seafood	1.8	2.5	2.0	3.8
Frequency of purchasing of frozen seafood	2.0	2.6	2.2	4.0
Frequency of purchasing of tinned seafood	2.0	2.6	2.2	4.0
Frequency of purchasing of pickled seafood	1.9	2.6	2.1	3.9

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Figure 43 Purchasing preferences and habits of Danish consumers (average values)

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Members of Cluster 4 are frequent buyers of any considered typology of fish products, and they purchase in different typologies of shops, with a relative preference for supermarkets.

Members of the other groups are less frequent buyers of fish products, with consumers included in Cluster 1 declaring the lowest purchasing frequencies among Danish consumers.

In terms of products, fish fillets or steaks are the preferred typology of fish product, while whole fish is the lesser selected option. Considering shopping places, the supermarket is clearly the preferred option for all consumers, followed by fishmongers; fish markets are the least frequently declared choice.

Finally, Table 19 and Figure 44 represent the preference of members of the four Danish clusters for wild or farmed fish.

Table 19 Preference for wild or farmed fish of Danish consumers

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
I prefer farmed fish over wild fish	5.4%	14.3%	2.6%	51.7%
I prefer wild fish over farmed fish	27.9%	42.3%	77.2%	34.2%
No preference	66.7%	43.4%	20.2%	14.1%

Figure 44 Preference for wild or farmed fish of Danish consumers

Preferences for wild or farmed fish vary consistently between the four groups of Danish consumers. Cluster 3 includes the largest share of consumers who prefer wild fish over farmed (77.2%), followed by Cluster 2, with 42.3% of members preferring wild-caught fish. Members of Cluster 4 are instead more oriented toward farmed fish, with 51.7% of them preferring this typology over wild fish. Cluster 4 is also the group that registers the lowest share of consumers who did not express a preference for one of the two products. The level of indifference is the greatest for consumers of Cluster 1, with two thirds of them not choosing between farmed or wild fish.

8.1.5 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products

Table 20 and Figure 45 describe the perception of Danish consumers related to five aspects of wild and farmed fish products: safety, taste, environmental impact, quality, animal welfare.

Table 20 Perception of characteristics of wild fish and aquaculture products of Danish consumers

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Which is safer				
Farmed fish	4.4%	20.4%	4.4%	35.0%
No difference in safety	36.8%	65.7%	36.8%	45.8%
Wild fish	58.8%	13.9%	58.8%	19.2%
Which tastes better				
Farmed fish	7.2%	15.1%	3.5%	42.5%
No difference	60.4%	47.4%	22.8%	30.8%
Wild fish	32.4%	37.5%	73.4%	26.7%
Has less environmental impact				
Farmed fish	26.1%	24.4%	8.9%	36.7%
No difference	48.7%	46.2%	20.1%	32.5%
Wild fish	25.2%	29.4%	71.0%	30.8%
Better quality				
Farmed fish	11.7%	19.4%	3.5%	35.8%
No difference	50.5%	43.5%	14.0%	29.2%
Wild fish	37.8%	37.1%	86.5%	35.0%
Better animal welfare				
Farmed fish	12.6%	20.6%	4.4%	43.3%
No difference	38.7%	37.3%	13.2%	27.5%
Wild fish	48.7%	42.1%	82.4%	29.2%

Figure 45 Perception of characteristics of wild fish and aquaculture products of Danish consumers

Perceptions related to characteristics of food products from aquaculture and from wild catch are consistently different among the four groups of Danish consumers.

Concerning safety of the products, wild fish is considered safer by the majority of consumers included in Cluster 1 and Cluster 3, while the largest share of members of Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 declare they find no differences between the two typologies of product. However, within Cluster 4 the share of consumers considering farmed fish safer than wild fish is greater than the share of consumers declaring the opposite.

Considering the perceived taste, wild fish is preferred over farmed fish by consumers included in Cluster 1, Cluster 2, and Cluster 3, while the majority of Cluster 4 members prefer farmed fish. However, a large share of members of Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 find no difference in taste between wild and farmed fish.

In relation to the perceived environmental impact of food products, members of Cluster 2 and, strongly, of Cluster 3, perceive wild fish to have a lower footprint compared to farmed fish. This perception is quite different for the members of Cluster 4: the relative majority of them consider farmed fish more environmentally sustainable than wild fish. Even in this case, the share of consumers who find no differences between wild and farmed fish is relevant, in particular for Cluster 1 and Cluster 2.

Perceived quality of farmed fish is considered higher for wild fish by members of Cluster 1, Cluster 2, and Cluster 3, while consumers belonging to Cluster 4 are almost equally divided between those who perceive wild fish as better than farmed fish and those who report the opposite opinion. Also concerning perceived quality, the level of “no preference” answer is relevant, especially considering Cluster 1, Cluster 2, and Cluster 4.

The perceived level of animal welfare attributed to wild fish is higher than the animal welfare level in aquaculture plants for the majority of members of Cluster 1, Cluster 2, and especially Cluster 3. Consumers in Cluster 4 generally perceive aquaculture as more respectful of animal welfare standards. Also concerning this topic, Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 register relevant shares of the “no preference” option.

Finally, perceptions of negative impacts of aquaculture of Danish consumers is represented in *Table 21* and *Figure 46*.

Table 21 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture - accordance with the claim: (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Pollutants are released from fish farms	4	4,4	6,4	6,1
Fish farms have a negative impact on biodiversity	3,8	4,3	6,2	5,9

Farmed seafood contains contaminants	3,9	4,5	6,1	5,8
Fish farms have a negative impact on how environment looks	3,7	4,3	6,3	5,9
Feed used in fish farms comes from unsustainable sources	3,9	4,3	5,5	6
Diseases from fish farms spread to wild fish	3,6	4,3	5,9	6,1

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 46 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture - accordance with the claim: (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 3 and Cluster 4 present high levels of accordance with claims on negative impacts of aquaculture, with only some limited differences. Members of Cluster 3 are a bit more concerned about negative impact on environmental look caused by aquaculture plants, while consumers in Cluster 4 agree with the claim that feed used in aquaculture plants comes from unsustainable sources.

Cluster 1 includes consumers less in accordance with negative claims related to aquaculture. They disagree with the statement that diseases spread from aquaculture plants to wild fish. Finally, members of Cluster 2 are generally neutral about the claims on negative impacts of aquaculture, except for the claim on contaminants contained in aquaculture products, with which they moderately agree.

8.2 Italy

The cluster analysis for Italian consumers led to the identification of five homogenous groups: the largest, Cluster 1, includes 59% of respondents, the second, Cluster 2, represents 23.3% of consumers, while Cluster 4 and Cluster 5 include almost the same share of respondents, 17.4% and 14.3%, respectively. Cluster 3 is the smallest, representing 7.3% of Italian consumers.

8.2.1 Socio-demographics and geographical characteristics

Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Italian clusters are described in *Table 22*.

Table 22 Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Italian clusters

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Name	Aware and demanding	Slightly not aware, non-demanding	Aware, healthy, and sustainable	Not aware and pragmatic	Aware and healthy
Share of population	59.0%	23.3%	7.3%	17.4%	14.3%
Average age (years)	47.1	47.6	54.2	52.8	53.8
Average household size	3.0	2.7	2.7	2.5	2.8

Members of the household under 18 years old	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.3
% of females	47.9%	46.6%	46.4%	52.7%	58.1%
% of males	52.1%	53.4%	53.6%	47.3%	41.9%
Education level					
Primary education	0.8%	1.3%	2.9%	3.0%	0.7%
Secondary education	54.7%	72.0%	58.1%	73.3%	68.4%
Tertiary education (Bachelor)	17.4%	10.4%	11.5%	4.9%	6.7%
Tertiary education (Master or PhD)	26.6%	16.3%	27.5%	18.8%	23.5%
No answer	0.5%	-	-	-	0.7%
Employment status					
Self-employed (alone or with others)	15.7%	10.0%	15.9%	11.5%	14.0%
Full time employee	44.3%	33.9%	44.5%	28.5%	25.0%
Part-time employee	9.0%	8.2%	5.8%	10.9%	8.8%
Full time student	3.3%	5.4%	1.5%	3.6%	2.9%
Unemployed/homemaker	9.3%	22.6%	11.6%	26.1%	22.1%
Retired	17.6%	18.6%	21.8%	19.4%	27.2%
Other	0.8%	1.3%	-	-	-
Income level (monthly)					
Up to 2000 €	31.9%	50.7%	36.2%	47.3%	36.1%
2000-4000 €	42.6%	31.2%	37.7%	35.8%	36.9%
4000-7000 €	15.2%	11.8%	23.1%	10.9%	20.2%
More than 7000 €	10.3%	6.3%	3.0%	6.0%	6.8%
Not declared	-	-	-	-	-
Place of residence					
Metropolitan City (> 1 million inhabitants)	14.6%	9.1%	17.4%	9.7%	14.0%
City (100.000 – 1 million inhabitants)	24.4%	18.6%	27.6%	23.0%	27.9%
Large town (20-100.000 inhabitants)	30.5%	27.6%	34.8%	33.3%	25.0%
Small town	16.0%	19.9%	8.7%	15.8%	11.0%
Village	9.2%	18.5%	5.8%	12.7%	17.7%
Rural	5.3%	6.3%	5.8%	5.5%	4.4%
Distance from the coast					
Living on the coast	17.4%	14.5%	18.8%	13.9%	22.1%
Nearby (less than 30 minutes to reach the coast)	29.7%	20.4%	18.8%	16.4%	19.1%
Not so far (30 to 60 minutes to reach the coast)	21.9%	21.7%	18.8%	17.0%	15.4%
Not so close (1 to 2 hours to reach the coast)	16.0%	21.7%	20.4%	25.5%	22.1%

Far away (more than 2 hours to reach the coast)	15.1%	21.7%	23.2%	27.3%	21.3%
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Concerning socio-demographics and geographical characteristics, Cluster 5 presents the highest average age of its members, almost 54 years, while Cluster 1 includes the youngest share of respondents, with an average age of about 47 years.

Cluster 1 also represents the largest households, with an average size of 3 members, followed by Cluster 5 with 2.8 members, Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 with an average of 2.7 members per household, and Cluster 4 representing households with an average size of 2.5 members. The average number of underage household members is similar, and the lowest, in Clusters 2, 4, and 5 (0.3 to 0.4), while Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 include households with a higher average number of young members, 0.5 and 0.6, respectively. Finally, Cluster 4 and Cluster 5 include a relative majority of female members, about 53% and 58%, respectively, while in the other clusters male respondents are the majority, ranging from 52.1% to 53.6%.

Considering education level, Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 include the most educated members, with respectively 45% and 39% of them having a bachelor's degree, a master's degree, or a PhD. Cluster 4 and Cluster 2, on the other hand, present the highest share of respondents with a primary or secondary education degree, almost two thirds of the total.

"Full time employee" is in general the most common employment status among the Italian population, followed by "Retired". However, relevant differences are present among the five groups. Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 present the largest share of "Full time employees" of the Italian context (about 44%) and the lowest share of "Unemployed/homemaker" (9.3% and 11.6%), and "Full time students" (3.3% and 1.5%). The share of "Full time employees" is similar within the other three groups, ranging from 25% to 33.9%, Cluster 4 includes the highest share of "Part-time/seasonally employed" among the four groups (10.9%). Cluster 1 is confirmed to be the wealthier group, with the largest share of respondents declaring a monthly income of more than 7.000 € and 25.5% of them declaring more than 4.000€. On the other hand, Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 are the relatively less wealthy, with almost 80% of their members declaring an income up to 4.000 €. About 50% of these Clusters' members declare an income of 2.000 € or less.

It is also interesting to highlight that the share of "Full-time homemaker" consumers is very relevant in almost all the Italian clusters, representing about one half of the "Unemployed/homemaker" category in Clusters 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Place of residence and distance from the coast differs consistently among the five clusters. Cluster 5 is the most urban, with more than 40% of members living in a city or a metropolis and the smallest share of inhabitants of rural areas among the five clusters (4.4%). The most rural group is Cluster 2, with more than 6% of members living in rural areas and 18.5% in villages.

Concerning the distance of the place of residence from the coast, Cluster 1 is the group with the largest share of members living on or near to the coast (47.3%), and the lowest number of members living more than one hour from the coast (31.1%). On the opposite side, Cluster 3 includes the largest share of members living far from the coast, with 52.8% of them living more than one hour from the sea.

8.2.2 Drivers of and barriers to fish consumption

Barriers to and drivers of fish consumption declared by Italian consumers are represented in *Table 23*. *Figure 47* describes drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, and *Figure 48* those related to Opportunity.

Table 23 Drivers and barriers for fish consumption for Italian clusters (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Self-declared ability in storing	5.6	4.4	5.3	3.4	4.7
Self-declared ability in preparing and cooking	5.6	4.7	5.5	4.0	5.1
Importance of being produced in Italy	5.8	4.9	5.9	4.9	5.6
Importance of being produced in Europe	5.6	4.8	5.8	4.6	5.3
Importance of price	5.7	5.3	5.9	5.6	5.8
Importance of ease of cooking	5.7	5.0	6.0	5.7	5.6
Importance of removal of inedible parts	5.5	5.0	5.3	5.2	5.1
Importance of health benefits	6.1	5.3	6.6	5.7	6.1
Importance of no dyes	6.1	5.3	6.6	5.8	6.3
Importance of being already tried	5.5	4.7	5.8	4.9	5.2
Importance of being liked in the household	6.0	5.2	6.6	5.7	6.0

Importance of sustainability	5.9	5.0	6.2	4.7	5.6
Importance of freshness	6.2	5.4	6.4	5.6	6.3
Importance of quality	6.2	5.4	6.7	5.8	6.3

1= Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 47 Drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability for fish consumption for Italian clusters (average values)

1= Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Considering the drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, price and place of production are the most relevant elements for all of the Italian consumers. Considering the other elements, members of Cluster 4 declare quite low levels of ability in storing and preparing fish, followed by consumers in Cluster 2 and Cluster 5, who present a level of declared ability slightly over neutrality.

Members of Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 are similar in terms of this typology of drivers, with consumers of Cluster 1 declaring slightly higher levels of ability in storing and preparing fish-based food.

Figure 48 Drivers and barriers related to Opportunity for fish consumption for Italian clusters (average values)

1= Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Concerning drivers and barriers related to Opportunity, in general Italian consumers are highly demanding, presenting average levels of importance greater than neutral for all the explored elements. In particular, Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 include the more demanding consumers, who attribute higher levels of importance to all the elements, especially health benefits, the product being liked by all members of the household, and absence of dyes.

While considered important, the absence of non-edible parts is the least considered element for consumption by members of all the clusters.

Finally, members of Cluster 2 are the relatively least demanding among all the five groups, while still presenting quite high levels of importance given to all the drivers and barriers.

8.2.3 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling

The different level of knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and food labelling related to fish products of members of Italian clusters are described in *Table 24* and *Figure 49*.

Table 24 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling of Italian consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Knowledge of term aquaculture	5.7	4.4	5.8	3.1	4.1
Importance to know if wild or aquaculture fish	5.7	4.1	5.7	3.4	4.8
Knowledge of MSC logo meaning	5.1	4.0	4.6	1.8	2.0
Knowledge of ASC logo meaning	5.1	3.8	4.4	1.6	2.0
Knowledge of organic label meaning	5.6	4.3	5.7	2.9	4.1
Knowledge of FOS logo	5.3	4.1	4.8	1.7	2.4
Knowledge of Fair-Trade Logo meaning	5.5	4.4	5.6	2.6	4.2

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 49 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture of Italian consumers (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 1, Cluster 3, and, at a lower level, Cluster 2 are the most aware about aquaculture and the different sets of labels that are related to it, although consumers in Cluster 3 are slightly less aware of the meaning of labels dedicated to fish products such as MSC, ASC, and FOS logos. Also, they are highly concerned about the source of fish products.

On the opposite side, members of Cluster 4 are the least involved and aware about aquaculture, having the lowest values for all the considered items. Among the already low levels of knowledge, members Cluster 4 and Cluster 5 declare to be, on average, totally unaware of the meaning of fish-related logos, such as MSC, ASC, and FOS.

8.2.4 Consumer perception and preferences for wild-fish and aquaculture products

Purchasing preferences and habits of Italian consumers related to fish products are represented in *Table 25* and *Figure 50*.

Table 25 Purchasing preferences and habits of Italian consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Frequency of fish purchasing from fishmonger	3.2	2.5	2.7	1.8	2.4
Frequency of fish purchasing from fish market	2.8	2.2	2.1	1.6	1.8
Frequency of fish purchasing from supermarket	3.6	3.1	3.1	2.6	3.0
Frequency of purchasing of whole fish	3.0	2.4	2.8	1.9	2.4
Frequency of purchasing of fish fillets or steak	3.4	2.8	3.0	2.4	2.7
Frequency of purchasing of prepared seafood	2.9	2.4	2.4	1.9	1.9
Frequency of purchasing of frozen seafood	3.2	2.9	3.0	2.5	2.6
Frequency of purchasing of tinned seafood	3.3	2.9	2.9	2.5	2.6
Frequency of purchasing of pickled seafood	2.7	2.0	2.1	1.5	1.8

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Figure 50 Purchasing preferences and habits of Italian consumers (average values)

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Members of Cluster 1 are frequent buyers of any considered typology of fish products, except for pickled seafood, that are purchased in different typologies of shops, with a relative preference for supermarkets and fishmongers. On the other hand, members of Cluster 4 are less frequent buyers of fish products, and their preferred place of purchase is the supermarket.

In terms of typologies of fish products, fish fillets or steak, frozen, and tinned seafood are preferred by all the clusters. Prepared seafood and whole fish is appreciated by members of Cluster 1, while pickled seafood and prepared seafood are the products purchased least frequently, in particular by consumers in Cluster 4 and Cluster 5.

Considering shopping places, the supermarket is clearly the preferred option for all consumers, followed by fishmongers; fish markets are more frequent only among members of Cluster 1.

Finally, Table 26 and Figure 51 represent the preference of members of the five Italian clusters for wild or farmed fish.

Table 26 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products of Italian consumers (average values)

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
I prefer farmed fish over wild fish	17.1%	12.7%	20.3%	7.3%	2.9%
I prefer wild fish over farmed fish	63.3%	44.8%	39.1%	34.6%	73.5%
Not have preference	19.6%	42.5%	40.6%	58.1%	23.6%

Figure 51 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products of Italian consumers

Preferences for wild or farmed fish vary consistently between the five groups of Italian consumers, but two common elements can be identified: a general preference for wild fish over farmed, and a high share of consumers declaring no preference.

Cluster 5 includes the largest share of consumers who prefer wild fish over farmed (73.5%), followed by Cluster 1, with 42.3% of members preferring wild-caught fish. Members of Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 present the largest share of consumers who did not declare any preference for either of the two typologies of fish products. Cluster 3 presents the highest share of consumers preferring farmed fish, 20.3% of the total.

8.2.5 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products

Table 27 and Figure 52 describe the perception of Italian consumers related to five aspects of wild and farmed fish products: safety, taste, environmental impact, quality, animal welfare.

Table 27 Perception of characteristics of wild fish and aquaculture products by Italian consumers

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Which is safer					
Farmed fish	30.8%	37.6%	47.8%	26.7%	18.4%
No difference in safety	48.2%	54.3%	44.9%	62.4%	42.6%
Wild fish	21.0%	8.1%	7.3%	10.9%	39.0%
Which tastes better					
Farmed fish	20.2%	15.0%	17.4%	7.3%	3.7%
No difference	26.3%	44.3%	34.8%	30.3%	12.5%
Wild fish	53.5%	40.7%	47.8%	62.4%	83.8%
Has less environmental impact					
Farmed fish	41.5%	42.5%	66.7%	38.8%	22.1%
No difference	34.1%	42.1%	18.8%	44.8%	29.4%
Wild fish	24.4%	15.4%	14.5%	16.4%	48.5%

Better quality					
Farmed fish	21.3%	20.8%	23.2%	8.5%	2.9%
No difference	29.4%	46.6%	39.1%	38.2%	14.7%
Wild fish	49.3%	32.6%	37.7%	53.3%	82.4%
Better animal welfare					
Farmed fish	30.5%	33.5%	50.7%	27.3%	18.4%
No difference	31.1%	46.2%	36.2%	40.0%	18.4%
Wild fish	38.4%	20.3%	13.1%	32.7%	63.2%

Figure 52 Perception of characteristics of wild fish and aquaculture products of Italian consumers

Perceptions related to characteristics of food products from aquaculture and from wild catch differ among the five groups of Italian consumers, although the share of no stated preference is high for all the groups.

Concerning safety of the products, wild fish is considered safer by the majority of consumers included in Cluster 5 (39%), while the largest share of members of Cluster 3 (47.8%) declare they find farmed fish less harmful. Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 include the largest share of consumers who did not declare preferences (54.3% and 62.4%)

Considering the perceived taste, wild fish is preferred over farmed fish by consumers included in Cluster 1, Cluster 3, Cluster 4, and in particular Cluster 5, where 83.8% of respondents consider wild fish to taste better than farmed. Cluster 1, however, includes the highest share of consumers considering farmed fish to have a better taste (20.2%).

In relation to the perceived environmental impact of food products, members of Cluster 1, Cluster 2, and Cluster 3 perceive farmed fish to have a lower footprint compared to wild fish. This perception is quite different for the members of Cluster 5: the relative majority of them consider wild fish to be more environmentally sustainable than farmed fish. The relative majority of Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 members perceive no differences in the environmental impact of wild and farmed fish.

The perceived quality of products is generally considered higher for wild fish. In particular, this is true for members of Cluster 5 and Cluster 4: respectively, 82.4% and 53.3% of them consider wild fish to be of better quality. Cluster 2 presents the highest share of members perceiving no difference in quality between wild and farmed fish (46.6%), followed by members of Cluster 3 (39.1%) and Cluster 4 (38.2%).

The perceived level of animal welfare attributed to wild fish is higher than that in aquaculture plants for the majority of members of Cluster 5 (63.2%) and Cluster 1 (38.4%). Among other groups, the share of consumers declaring no preference is the highest, in particular for Cluster 2 (46.2%) and Cluster 4 (40%). Also, half of the consumers included in Cluster 3 consider farmed fish to guarantee a higher level of animal welfare compared to aquaculture products.

Finally, perception of negative impacts of aquaculture among Italian consumers is described in *Table 28* and *Figure 53*.

Table 28 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture of Italian consumers - accordance with the claim: (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Pollutants are released by fish farms	5.2	4.0	1.6	3.8	5.4
Fish farms have a negative impact on biodiversity	5.2	4.2	1.6	4.0	5.4
Farmed seafood contains contaminants	5.4	4.2	2.4	4.2	5.7
Fish farms have a negative impact on how environment looks	5.0	3.9	1.7	3.7	5.3
Feed used in fish farms comes from unsustainable sources	5.3	3.9	1.7	3.7	5.3
Diseases from fish farms spread to wild fish	5.0	4.0	1.9	3.8	4.5

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 53 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture of Italian consumers - accordance with the claim: (average value)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 1 and Cluster 5 present high levels of accordance with claims about negative impacts of aquaculture, with particular attention paid to the presence of contaminants in the products, and of feed coming from unsustainable sources. On the other hand, members of Cluster 3 show the lowest level of accordance with negative claims about aquaculture.

Consumers in Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 present similar degrees of accordance with negative claims on aquaculture, expressing a higher level of accordance with the claims related to the negative impact of fish farms on biodiversity and the presence of contaminants in aquaculture products.

8.3 Slovenia

The cluster analysis for Slovenian consumers led to the identification of four homogenous groups: Cluster 1 is by far the largest, including more than half of the respondents (55.4%), Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 represent similar shares of the Slovenian population (16.9% and 18%, respectively), and Cluster 4 is the smallest, including 9.7% of consumers.

8.3.1 Socio-demographics and geographical characteristics

Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Slovenian clusters are described in *Table 29*.

Table 29 Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics of Slovenian clusters

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Name	Not aware and healthy	Aware, healthy, and pragmatic	Aware, sustainable, and demanding	Not aware, healthy, and pragmatic
Share of the population	55.4%	16.9%	18.0%	9.7%
Average age	42.6	49.4	45.1	46.2
Members of the household	3	3	3	2.9
Members of the household under 18 years old	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.7
% of females	45.1%	52.0%	57.1%	42.5%
% of males	54.9%	48.0%	42.9%	57.5%
Education level				
Primary education	1.8%	2.6%	1.9%	2.3%
Secondary education	76.5%	66.6%	60.9%	52.9%
Tertiary education (Bachelor)	19.1%	24.8%	28.6%	29.9%
Tertiary education (Master or PhD)	1.8%	8.6%	8.6%	14.9%
No answer	0.8%	-	-	-
Employment status				
Self-employed (alone or with others)	8.1%	13.2%	11.8%	11.5%
Full time employee	54.9%	50.0%	54.0%	52.9%
Part-time employee	6.0%	5.9%	5.0%	3.5%
Full time student	7.0%	1.3%	6.2%	8.1%
Unemployed/homemaker	6.2%	5.9%	3.1%	6.7%
Retired	16.1%	23.0%	18.1%	16.1%
Other	1.6%	0.7%	1.9%	-
Income level				
Up to 2000 €	48.3%	43.4%	46.8%	47.1%
2000-4000 €	36.6%	40.2%	37.9%	31.2%
4000-6000 €	8.3%	9.9%	7.4%	16.1%
More than 6000 €	5.6%	6.5%	9.9%	4.6%

Not declared	-	-	-	-
Place of residence				
City (100.000 – 1 million inhabitants)	26.8%	22.4%	24.2%	27.6%
Large town (20-100.000 inhabitants)	23.1%	14.5%	24.8%	18.4%
Small town	29.6%	38.8%	31.1%	31.0%
Village	14.5%	14.5%	15.5%	16.1%
Rural	6.0%	9.9%	4.4%	6.9%
Distance from the coast				
Living on the coast	2.6%	4.6%	6.2%	5.8%
Nearby (less than 30 minutes to reach the coast)	6.4%	3.3%	7.5%	5.8%
Not so far (30 to 60 minutes to reach the coast)	16.1%	15.8%	14.3%	10.3%
Not so close (1 to 2 hours to reach the coast)	36.0%	40.8%	34.2%	39.1%
Far away (more than 2 hours to reach the coast)	38.8%	35.5%	37.9%	39.1%

Concerning socio-demographics and geographical characteristics, Cluster 2 presents the highest average age of its members, 49.4 years, while Cluster 1 includes the youngest share of respondents, with an average age of 42.6 years. The average number of household members is 3 for each cluster, and the average number of underage members is 0.8. Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 include the relative majority of female members (52% and 57.1%, respectively) while in Cluster 1 and Cluster 4 male respondents are the majority, respectively 53.6% and 58.8%.

Considering education level, Cluster 4 includes the most educated members, with 44.8% of them having a master's degree or PhD. Cluster 1, on the other hand, presents the highest share of respondents with a primary or secondary education degree, 78.3%.

"Full time employee" is by far the most common employment status among the Slovenian population, followed by "Retired". However, relevant differences are present between the four Clusters. Cluster 1 presents the largest share of "Full time employees" of the Slovenian context (54.9%) and the lowest share of "Retired" (16.1%), tied with Cluster 4. The share of "Full time employees" is quite similar for the other three groups, ranging from 50% to 54%.

Cluster 2 includes the highest share of "Retired" members (23%). Cluster 4 is confirmed to be the wealthier group, with the largest share of respondents declaring a monthly income of more than 4.000 € (20%). On the other side, Cluster 1 is the relatively less wealthy, with 48.3% of its members declaring an income up to 2.000 €, followed by Cluster 4 and Cluster 3, with about 47% and 46% of respondents declaring that income level, respectively.

Place of residence and distance from the coast differ consistently between the four clusters. Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 are the most urban, with about half of their members living in a city or large town and the smallest share of inhabitants of villages and rural areas among the four groups (20.5% and 19.9%, respectively). The most rural group is Cluster 4, which includes 6.9% of members living in rural areas and 16.1% in villages.

Given the geographical characteristics of Slovenia, most of its population lives far from the coast. However, some differences are registered between the four clusters of consumers. Cluster 4 is the group with the largest share of members far from the coast (78.2%), while Cluster 3 includes the largest share of members living near the coast, with 13.7% of them living less than 30 minutes from the seaside.

8.3.2 Drivers of and barriers to fish consumption

Drivers of and barriers to fish consumption declared by Slovenian consumers are represented in *Table 30*. *Figure 54* describes drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, and *Figure 55* those related to Opportunity.

Table 30 Drivers and barriers for fish consumption for Slovenian consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
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Self-declared ability in storing	4.6	5.2	5.4	4.1
Self-declared ability in preparing and cooking	4.6	5.3	5.5	4.2
Importance of being produced in Slovenia	4.5	4.6	5.3	3.9
Importance of being produced in Europe	4.8	5.2	5.8	4.3
Importance of price	5.3	5.8	6.0	5.6
Importance of ease of cooking	5.1	5.5	5.9	5.1
Importance of absence of inedible parts	5.2	5.4	5.9	5.2
Importance of health benefits	5.5	6.2	6.5	5.4
Importance of no dyes	5.5	6.2	6.5	5.5
Importance of being already tried	5.0	5.3	5.6	4.7
Importance of being liked in the household	5.3	6.0	6.2	5.6
Importance of sustainability	4.8	5.3	6.1	4.1
Importance of freshness	5.8	6.5	6.7	6.3
Importance of quality	6.0	6.6	6.6	6.3

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 54 Drivers and barriers for fish consumption related to Motivation and Ability for Slovenian consumers (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Considering the drivers and barriers related to Motivation and Ability, price is the most relevant element for all the Slovenian consumers. Considering the other elements, members of Cluster 3 give the highest level of importance to all of them, with average values greater than 5. On the other side, members of Cluster 4 are more sceptical about their ability to prepare and properly store fish products, and neutral about the importance of fish being produced in Slovenia or Europe.

Members of Cluster 2 are similar in terms of this typology of drivers, to consumers of Cluster 3, giving more importance to European and national origin of the fish product.

Figure 55 Drivers and barriers for fish consumption related to Opportunity for Slovenian consumers (average values)

1= Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Considering drivers and barriers related to Opportunity, quality and freshness are the most relevant factors for all the Slovenian consumers.

Considering the four groups, Cluster 3 includes the most demanding consumers, who attribute high levels of importance to all the elements, in particular freshness, quality, health benefits, the product being liked by household members, and absence of dyes.

Ease of cooking and the absence of inedible parts are the least considered barriers by all the Slovenian consumers, followed by the product have been already tried before purchasing.

The four clusters are different in terms of the importance given to sustainability of fish products. Members of Cluster 3 assign the highest average level of importance to sustainability, followed by Cluster 2. Consumers less interested in sustainability are those included in Cluster 1 and Cluster 4.

8.3.3 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling

The different levels of knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling of members of Slovenian clusters are described in Table 31 and Figure 56.

Table 31 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling for Slovenian consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Knowledge of term aquaculture	1.3	3.8	3.2	6.1
Importance to know if wild or aquaculture fish	2.5	4.3	4.5	6.2
Knowledge of MSC logo meaning	1.5	4.0	3.7	6.3
Knowledge of ASC logo meaning	1.4	3.8	2.8	6.2
Knowledge of organic label meaning	2.0	4.6	3.9	6.4
Knowledge of FOS logo	1.4	3.8	2.6	6.3
Knowledge of Fair-Trade Logo meaning	2.8	4.6	4.4	6.4

1= Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 56 Knowledge and understanding of aquaculture and labelling for Slovenian consumers

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 4 are the most aware about aquaculture and the different sets of labels that are related to it. Also, they are highly concerned about knowledge of the source of fish products.

On the opposite side, members of Cluster 1 are the least involved and aware about the topic of aquaculture, having the lowest values for all the considered items.

Consumers in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 are in between the other two groups, being less aware about aquaculture compared to members of Cluster 4 but showing a relevant level of knowledge about the topic. Consumers in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 give a moderate level of importance to knowing the source of fish products and they are quite aware of the meaning of the most common labels, such as organic and fair-trade. However, members of Cluster 2 have, on average, a deeper knowledge of labels directly designed for fish-based products, in particular the MSC logo.

8.3.4 Consumer perception and preferences for wild-fish and aquaculture products

Purchasing preferences and habits of Slovenian consumers related to fish products are represented in *Table 32* and *Figure 57*.

Table 32 Purchasing preferences and habits of Slovenian consumers (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Frequency of fish purchasing from fishmonger	2.2	2.1	2.4	1.6
Frequency of fish purchasing from fish market	1.9	1.6	2	1.3
Frequency of fish purchasing from supermarket	2.7	2.6	2.8	2.3
Frequency of purchasing of whole fish	2.4	2.3	2.5	1.9
Frequency of purchasing of fish fillets or steak	2.6	2.5	2.7	2.2
Frequency of purchasing of prepared seafood	2.2	1.8	2.1	1.5
Frequency of purchasing of frozen seafood	2.4	2.3	2.4	1.8
Frequency of purchasing of tinned seafood	2.6	2.6	2.7	2.3
Frequency of purchasing of pickled seafood	1.9	1.6	1.8	1.2

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Figure 57 Purchasing preferences and habits of Slovenian consumers (average values)

1=Never – 6 = 4-5 times per week

Slovenian consumers register a similar pattern in terms of frequency of purchasing fish in different typologies of shops, as well as frequency of purchasing different typologies of products. In particular, supermarkets and fishmongers are the preferred typologies of shop for the members of all clusters, while fish markets are chosen less frequently. In terms of typology of product, fish fillets or steak and tinned seafood are the most frequently purchased, probably because of their long shelf life. Pickled and prepared seafood are, on the other hand, the least frequently purchased by members of all the Slovenian clusters.

Differences are present, however, in terms of absolute values of frequencies: Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 include the consumers with the highest frequency of purchasing, while members of Cluster 4 are the least frequent consumers of all the considered products, in particular prepared and tinned seafood.

Table 33 and Figure 58 represent the preference of members of the four Slovenian clusters for wild or farmed fish.

Table 33 Preferences for wild or farmed fish of Slovenian consumers

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
I prefer farmed fish over wild fish	11.1%	16.5%	15.5%	8.1%
I prefer wild fish over farmed fish	44.3%	38.2%	57.8%	33.3%
Not have preference	44.6%	45.3%	26.7%	58.6%

Figure 58 Preferences for wild or farmed fish of Slovenian consumers

Although preferences for wild or farmed fish vary consistently between the four groups of Slovenian consumers, wild fish is in general preferred. Cluster 3 includes the largest share of consumers who prefer wild fish over farmed (57.8%), followed by Cluster 1, with 44.3% of members preferring wild-caught fish. Cluster 3 is also the group that registers the lowest share of consumers who did not express a preference for one of the two products (58.6%). The level of indifference is the highest for

consumers of Cluster 4, with almost 60% of them not choosing between farmed or wild fish. The share of consumers not expressing a preference for farmed or wild fish is high also in Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 (44.6% and 45.3%, respectively).

8.3.5 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products

Table 34 and Figure 59 describe the perception of Slovenian consumers related to five aspects of wild and farmed fish products: safety, taste, environmental impact, quality, animal welfare.

Table 34 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products of Slovenian consumers

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Which is safer				
Farmed fish	22.3%	26.3%	23.6%	19.5%
No difference in safety	20.1%	38.2%	31.7%	46.0%
Wild fish	27.6%	35.5%	44.7%	34.5%
Which tastes better				
Farmed fish	14.3%	11.2%	9.9%	5.8%
No difference	37.4%	23.7%	25.5%	34.5%
Wild fish	48.3%	65.1%	64.6%	59.7%
Has less environmental impact				
Farmed fish	36.4%	46.7%	33.5%	36.8%
No difference	36.4%	29.6%	24.8%	40.2%
Wild fish	27.2%	23.7%	41.6%	23.0%
Better quality				
Farmed fish	20.3%	14.5%	14.3%	5.8%
No difference	30.4%	24.3%	23.0%	33.3%
Wild fish	49.3%	61.2%	62.7%	60.9%
Better animal welfare				
Farmed fish	21.9%	18.4%	16.8%	16.1%
No difference	35.6%	31.6%	24.8%	34.5%
Wild fish	42.5%	50.0%	58.4%	49.4%

Figure 59 Perception of wild fish and aquaculture products of Slovenian consumers

Perceptions related to characteristics of food products from aquaculture and from wild catch are consistently different between the four groups of Slovenian consumers.

Considering safety, wild fish is preferred over farmed fish by consumers in Cluster 1 and Cluster 3. The relative majority of Cluster 2 and Cluster 4 members find no difference in taste between wild and farmed fish. Cluster 2 includes the largest share of members who consider wild fish safer, 26.3%.

Concerning perceived taste, the largest share of Slovenian consumers prefer wild fish, ranging from 65.1% of Cluster 2 to 48.3% of Cluster 1. As a consequence, the shares of consumers considering farmed fish safer than wild fish are considerably smaller, ranging from 5.8% of Cluster 4 to 14.3% of Cluster 1. Also, the share of consumers declaring no difference in taste between the products ranges from 23.7% of Cluster 2 to 37.4% of Cluster 1.

In relation to the perceived environmental impact of food products, farmed fish is considered to have a lower environmental footprint by the relative majority of consumers who belong to Cluster 1 and Cluster 2. More than 40% of members of Cluster 3 perceive wild fish to be more environmentally friendly than farmed fish, while 40% of consumers in Cluster 4 express no preference. In general, the perception of the environmental impact of wild and farmed fish is multifaceted among clusters, indicating a consistent variance of perceptions.

Perceived quality of fish products is considered higher for wild fish by the largest shares of consumers in all the Slovenian clusters. In particular, this perception is strongest for the members of Cluster 3 (62.7% of them consider wild fish to be of better quality than farmed), while it is less present in Cluster 1, where 49.1% of members consider fish from wild catch to be of better quality than farmed. Also, Cluster 1 includes the largest share of consumers expressing no preference, 30.4%.

The perceived level of animal welfare granted by fish production systems follows a path similar to the perceived quality. Even for this aspect, the relative majority of members in each cluster prefer wild fish. This preference is strongest in Cluster 3, where 58.4% of members consider wild fishing more respectful of animal welfare, and weakest in Cluster 1, with 42.5% of consumers declaring the same. Cluster 1 is confirmed to include the largest share of consumers with no preferences, 35.6%.

Finally, perceptions of Slovenian consumers of negative impacts of aquaculture is represented in *Table 35* and *Figure 60*.

Table 35 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture - accordance with the claim: (average values)

Item	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Pollutants are released by fish farms	4.6	2.8	5.6	4.1
Fish farms have a negative impact on biodiversity	4.4	2.5	5.3	3.5

Farmed seafood contains contaminants	4.7	3.5	5.8	4.4
Fish farms have a negative impact on how environment looks	4.3	2.0	5.1	3.3
Feed used in fish farms comes from unsustainable sources	4.6	3.4	5.5	4.2
Diseases from fish farms spread to wild fish	4.4	2.4	5	3.5

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Figure 60 Perception of negative impacts of aquaculture - accordance with the claim: (average values)

1=Totally disagree; 7= Totally agree

Members of Cluster 3 present the highest levels of accordance with the claims related to negative aspects of aquaculture. In particular, the highest level of accordance is given to the claim related to the presence of contaminants in farmed seafood, followed by the release of pollutants from fish farms into the environment.

Members of Cluster 2 are the most confident with aquaculture, since they moderately or strongly disagree with all the negative claims about aquaculture proposed. They strongly disagree with the claim that fish farms have a negative impact on how the environment looks and that aquaculture has a negative impact on biodiversity. These consumers are almost neutral regarding the claims related to the presence of contaminants in farmed seafood and the fact that feed used in fish farms comes from unsustainable sources.

Consumers included in Cluster 1 and Cluster 4 are almost neutral about the presented claims, with the former slightly more concerned. For both groups, the claims presenting the higher relative values of accordance are those related to pollutants released by fish farms, to the presence of contaminants in farmed seafood, and to the fact that feed used in fish farm comes from unsustainable sources.

8.4 Summary: characteristics of clusters for Denmark

Cluster 1: Not aware and pragmatic (13.2% of population)	Cluster 2: Aware, healthy, and focus on quality (59% of population)	Cluster 3: Aware, healthy, and pragmatic (13.5% of population)	Cluster 4: Aware, demanding, and wealthy (14.3% of population)
<i>Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics</i>			
Average age: 48.5 years	Average age: 42.6 years	Average age: 50.1 years	Average age: 37.1 years
Household size: 2.2 members	Household size: 2.4 members	Household size: 2.2 members	Household size: 3 members
Gender: 55.9% females; 44.1% males	Gender: % 46.2 females; 53.6% males	Gender: 41.2% females; 58.8% males	Gender: 55.8% females; 44.2% males
Education level: medium	Education level: medium	Education level: medium/high	Education level: high
Income level: medium/high	Income level: medium	Income level: medium/high	Income level: high
Residence: small and large town, nearby or on the coast	Residence: small town and city; near or not so far from the coast	Residence: towns and city, nearby and on the coast	Residence: metropolitan city or city; on the coast or nearby
<i>Drivers and barriers to fish consumption</i>			
Medium ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/high ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/high ability in storing and preparing fish food	High ability in storing and preparing fish food
Focus on price, ease of cooking, freshness, quality	Focus on freshness, quality, product being liked in the household	Focus on freshness, quality, absence of dyes, price, products being liked in the households	Focus on all the characteristics, especially absence of dyes, sustainability and quality.
Lower importance to sustainability and previous knowledge of the product	Lower importance to origin and previous knowledge of products	Lower importance to absence of inedible parts and previous knowledge of the product	Relatively lower importance to absence of inedible parts.
<i>Frequency and preferences of purchase</i>			
Low frequency of purchasing of all products	Medium/low frequency of purchasing of all products	Medium frequency of purchasing of all products	High frequency of purchasing of all products
Wild fish preferred to farmed fish	Wild fish preferred to farmed fish, but high share of no preferences	Wild fish preferred to farmed fish	Farmed fish preferred to wild fish
Supermarket as preferred shop	Supermarket as preferred shop	Supermarket as preferred shop	Supermarket and fishmongers as preferred shop
Preference for fish fillets and steak and all prepared products, not for whole fish	Preference for fish fillets and steak and all prepared products, not for whole fish	Preference for all prepared products, not for whole fish	High frequency of purchasing of all typologies of fish. Heavy consumers
<i>Knowledge and perception of aquaculture</i>			
Low level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Medium level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Medium level of knowledge of aquaculture topic, lower for aquaculture-related labels	High level of knowledge of aquaculture topic
Wild fish considered safer and more respectful of animal welfare;	Wild fish considered more respectful of animal welfare	Wild fish considered safer, better tasting, with less environmental impact, of better quality, and more respectful of animal welfare	Farmed fish considered, better tasting, with less environmental impact, of better quality, and more respectful of animal welfare
No perceived differences about taste, quality and environmental impact	No perceived differences about safety, taste, quality and environmental impact	High level accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture, in particular about negative impacts on biodiversity, pollutants released from fish farms, and negative impact on how environment looks	No perceived differences about safety;
Neutral about the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture	Moderate accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture		High level accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture, in particular about pollutants released from fish farms, unsustainability of feed used in fish farms, and the possible diffusion of diseases from fish farms to wild fish

8.5 Summary: characteristics of clusters for Italy

Cluster 1: Aware and demanding (37.6% of population)	Cluster 2: Slightly aware, non-demanding (23.3% of population)	Cluster 3: Aware, conscious, and healthy (13.5% of population)	Cluster 4: Not aware and pragmatic (17.4% of population)	Cluster 5: Slightly not-aware and healthy (14.3% of population)
<i>Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics</i>				
Average age: 47.1 years	Average age: 47.6 years	Average age: 54.2 years	Average age: 52.8 years	Average age: 53.8 years
Household size: 3 members	Household size: 2.7 members	Household size: 2.7 members	Household size: 2.5 members	Household size: 2.8 members
Gender: 47.9% females; 52.1% males	Gender: % 46.6 females; 53.4% males	Gender: 46.4% females; 53.6% males	Gender: 52.7% females; 47.3% males	Gender: 58.1% females; 41.9% males
Education level: medium/high	Education level: medium/low	Education level: medium/high	Education level: medium/low	Education level: medium/high
Income level: medium/high	Income level: low	Income level: medium	Income level: low	Income level: medium/high
Residence: metropolitan cities to large towns; nearby to not so close to the coast	Residence: large towns to villages, highest share of rurals; not so far to far away from the coast	Residence: metropolitan cities to large towns; evenly divided among different distances from the coast	Residence: city to village, from not so far to far away from the coast	Residence: metropolitan city to large town, and villages; on the coast or not so close to far away
<i>Drivers and barriers to fish consumption</i>				
High ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium ability in storing and preparing fish food	High ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/low ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/high ability in storing and preparing fish food
Focus on health benefits, absence of dyes, freshness, and quality	Focus on price, freshness, quality, health benefits and absence of dyes	Focus on sustainability, freshness, quality, product liked in the household, health benefits, absence of dyes	Focus on ease of cooking, absence of dyes, quality, and product liked in the household	Focus health benefits, absence of dyes, product liked in the household, freshness and quality.
Relatively lower importance to absence of inedible parts and to previous knowledge of the product	Lower importance to origin and previous knowledge of the product	Lower importance to absence of inedible parts	Lower importance to sustainability and European origin of the product	Lower importance to absence of inedible parts and previous knowledge of the product
<i>Frequency and preferences of purchase</i>				
Low frequency of purchasing of all products	Low frequency of purchasing of all products	Low frequency of purchasing of all products	Low frequency of purchasing of all products	Low frequency of purchasing of all products
Wild fish preferred to farmed fish	Wild fish preferred to farmed fish; high share of no preferences	No preference between wild and farmed fish; high share of preference for wild fish	No preference between wild and farmed fish; high share of preference for wild fish	Wild fish preferred to farmed fish
Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops	Supermarket as preferred shop	Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops	Supermarket as preferred shop	Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops
Preference for whole fish, fish fillets or steak, frozen and tinned seafood; lower preference for prepared and pickled seafood	Preference for fish fillets or steak, frozen and tinned seafood; lower preference for whole fish, prepared and pickled seafood	Preference for whole fish, fish fillets or steak, frozen and tinned seafood; lower preference for prepared and pickled seafood	Relative preference for frozen and tinned seafood	Preference for fish fillets or steak, frozen and tinned seafood; lower preference for whole fish, prepared and pickled seafood
<i>Knowledge and perception of aquaculture</i>				
High level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Medium level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	High level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Low level of knowledge of aquaculture topic; low knowledge of aquaculture-related labels	Medium level of knowledge of aquaculture topic; low knowledge of aquaculture-related labels
Wild fish considered better tasting, of better quality, and more respectful of animal welfare;	Farmed fish considered to have lower environmental impact (but high share of no difference);	Wild fish considered to taste better	Wild fish considered safer and better tasting of animal welfare;	Wild fish considered better tasting, having

<p>Farmed fish perceived to have lower environmental impact</p> <p>No perceived differences in safety</p> <p>Moderate/high level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture, in particular related to the presence of contaminants in farmed seafood</p>	<p>No perceived differences in safety, taste, quality, and animal welfare</p> <p>Neutral about the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture</p>	<p>and with higher level of animal welfare</p> <p>No perceived differences about quality</p> <p>Very low level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture</p>	<p>No perceived differences quality, environmental impact, and animal welfare</p> <p>Neutral about the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture</p>	<p>less environmental impact, of better quality, and more respectful of animal welfare;</p> <p>No perceived differences of safety</p> <p>Moderate/high level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture, in particular related to the presence of contaminants in farmed seafood</p>
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8.6 Summary: characteristics of clusters for Slovenia

Cluster 1: Not aware and healthy (55.4% of population)	Cluster 2: Aware, healthy, and pragmatic (16.9% of population)	Cluster 3: Aware, sustainable, and demanding (18% of population)	Cluster 4: Unaware, healthy, and pragmatic (9.7% of population)
<i>Socio-demographic and geographical characteristics</i>			
Average age: 42.6 years	Average age: 49.4 years	Average age: 45.1 years	Average age: 46.2 years
Household size: 3 members	Household size: 3 members	Household size: 3 members	Household size: 2.9 members
Gender: 45.1% females; 54.9% males	Gender: % 52.0 females; 48.0% males	Gender: 57.1% females; 42.9% males	Gender: 42.5% females; 57.5% males
Education level: low	Education level: medium	Education level: medium	Education level: medium/high
Income level: medium/low	Income level: medium/low	Income level: medium	Income level: medium/high
Residence: city to small town; not so close or far away from the coast	Residence: city or small town, high share of rural; not so close or far away from the coast	Residence: city to small town; not so close or far away from the coast	Residence: city or small town, high share of rural; not so close or far away from the coast
<i>Drivers and barriers to fish consumption</i>			
Medium ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/high ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium/high ability in storing and preparing fish food	Medium ability in storing and preparing fish food
Focus on health benefits, absence of dyes, freshness, and quality	Focus on health benefits, product being liked in the household, freshness, quality	Focus on each element, in particular to health benefits, absence of dyes, freshness, and quality	Focus on price, product being liked in the household, freshness, quality
Lower importance to sustainability and origin of the product	Lower importance to sustainability and Slovenian origin of the product	Lower importance to origin and previous knowledge of the product	Lower importance to sustainability and origin of the product
<i>Frequency and preferences of purchase</i>			
Medium/low frequency of purchasing of all products	Medium/low frequency of purchasing of all products	Medium/low frequency of purchasing of all products	Low frequency of purchasing of all products
No preferences between wild and farmed fish; high share of preference for wild fish	No preferences between wild and farmed fish; high share of preference for wild fish	Wild fish preferred to farmed fish	No preferences between wild and farmed fish; high share of preference for wild fish
Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops	Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops	Supermarket and fishmonger as preferred shops	Supermarket as preferred typology of shop
Preference for tinned and frozen seafood, fish fillet or steak, whole fish	Preference for tinned and frozen seafood, fish fillet or steak, whole fish	Preference for all products, except pickled seafood	Preference for fish fillet or steak and tinned seafood, pickled and prepared seafood avoided
<i>Knowledge and perception of aquaculture</i>			
Low level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Medium level of knowledge of aquaculture topic	Medium/low level of knowledge of aquaculture topic; low knowledge of aquaculture-related labels	High level of knowledge of aquaculture topic
Wild fish considered safer, better tasting, of higher quality, and more respectful of animal welfare;	Wild fish considered better tasting, of higher quality and more respectful of animal welfare;	Wild fish considered safer, better tasting, with lower environmental impact, of higher quality, and more respectful of animal welfare;	Wild fish considered better tasting, of higher quality, and more respectful of animal welfare;
No perceived differences about environmental impact (high share of consumers considering farmed fish having lower impact)	No perceived differences in safety (with similar shares of consumers choosing wild or farmed fish), quality and environmental impact	Moderately high level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture, in particular related to presence of contaminants in farmed seafood	No perceived differences about safety and environmental impact
Moderately high level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture	Farmed fish perceived as having less environmental impact		Neutral about the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture
	Moderately low level of accordance with the statements on negative impacts of aquaculture		

9. Task 2.2 Conclusions

The second part of this report summarises the findings from the survey distributed in task 2.2 and the subsequent cluster analysis conducted to identify consumers' profiles.

The results of those activities provided a comprehensive picture of seafood consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours in three European countries, representative of Northern Europe (Denmark), Southern Europe (Italy), and Central Europe (Slovenia). The cluster analysis led to the identification of 13 distinct profiles of seafood consumers, four each in Denmark and Slovenia, and five in Italy, each with peculiar characteristics and patterns of choice related to fish-based products.

While these 13 groups of consumers present distinctive aspects and declared behaviours, some common trends can be identified across countries.

First, wild fish is preferred over farmed fish by the majority of consumer groups in the three countries, with the only relevant exception being the wealthier group of Danish consumers. However, despite the preference for wild fish over farmed fish, several clusters presented a high share of respondents who stated they had no preference between the two typologies of products. This was registered for one group in Denmark, and three groups in Italy and Slovenia, and could be considered as a market opportunity for aquaculture products, since there is not a preclusion towards them in a large share of consumers.

Considering the drivers of and barriers to fish consumption, price is the most relevant item for all the clusters of consumers. This is observed in particular for groups who declared lower income levels, which are also the groups who generally declared a lower frequency of purchasing fish-based foods and a preference for frozen and tinned products. A partial exception to this trend is registered for Slovenia, where groups with lower income levels also declared some preferences for whole fish.

Besides price, the groups of respondents identified in each of the three countries declared different drivers and barriers as relevant, but with several commonalities. In general, the origin of a product, while considered important, was not the main driver for consumption for the largest number of identified groups, this being true especially for Slovenia. On the other hand, freshness and quality were considered as crucial drivers for consumption by the majority of the clusters in all three countries.

Also, groups of consumers focusing on the health benefits of eating fish-based food can be observed. In particular, two 'healthy' groups were identified for Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia. These results show that the focus on health benefits generated by FishEUTrust solutions could represent an effective driver for their diffusion among relevant European consumers.

Finally, concerning knowledge and perception of fish products and aquaculture, wild fish is considered better tasting than farmed fish by a large share of consumers in all three countries. Farmed fish is considered better tasting than wild fish only by the wealthier cluster of Denmark, while only one cluster in Denmark and one in Italy do not perceive a difference in taste between the two products.

Consumers' self-declared levels of knowledge of aquaculture and aquaculture-related labels is often directly related to their education level: groups of more educated consumers self-declare the highest level of awareness about the topic. This self-perceived knowledge, however, is often followed by a high level of accordance with misleading statements on the negative impact of aquaculture: this can be observed in two consumer groups each in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia. On the other hand, one cluster each in Denmark, Italy, and Slovenia present a medium or high education level and do not agree with the misleading statements on the negative impacts of aquaculture.

To a broader extent, the results show a general negative perception of aquaculture and its products. Hence, information actions and campaigns aiming at disseminating accurate information about the impact of aquaculture on the environment, and the quality and safety of its products, will be crucial for the success of FishEUTrust activities and solutions.

Conclusion

It is a central goal of FishEUTrust to facilitate a shift in consumer trends and behaviours whereby purchasing aquaculture products is more sustainable, and produce from European and local sources is authenticated as such. The FishEUTrust project aims to increase consumer trust in, and thus uptake of, EU aquaculture products by addressing two problems: a current lack of product traceability and transparency, and a lack of trust in aquaculture products. To address the latter problem, the aim of WP2 is to design and validate a tailored set of intervention strategies intended to increase consumers' trust in and consumption of seafood products produced in the EU. FishEUTrust project partners can then use these intervention strategies to define and develop the most effective methods for promoting uptake of FishEUTrust products.

The literature reviews and stakeholder interviews carried out in task 2.1 provided a wealth of information about the factors which influence consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours, and how those factors interact with one another to influence behaviours.

The survey distributed in task 2.2 provided a comprehensive picture of seafood consumers' purchasing and consumption behaviours in three European countries, representative of Northern Europe (Denmark), Southern Europe (Italy), and Central Europe (Slovenia). The subsequent cluster analysis enabled the identification of 13 distinct clusters of seafood consumers, four each in Denmark and Slovenia and five in Italy.

The detailed profiles of the consumers identified within the 13 clusters, together with the results from the literature reviews and stakeholder interviews, will provide a strong base from which to begin the development and testing of activities foreseen for tasks 2.3 and 2.4.

In particular, the identification of profiles of consumers will be the base for the development of tailored real and virtual consumer experiences (task 2.3) that will test a set of solutions identified in FishEUTrust, and co-defined with project partners, with consumers matching the characteristics identified through the survey and the cluster analysis.

Results from the previous three tasks will then form the base for the design of tailored intervention strategies for the promotion of FishEUTrust solutions that will be developed in task 2.4. These strategies will increase consumer knowledge of, and demand for, FishEUTrust products, with the ultimate goal of encouraging increased consumption of sustainable and authentic EU aquaculture products.

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- Witter, A., Murray, G. & Sumaila, U. R., 2021. Consumer seafood preferences related to alternative food networks and their value chains. *Marine Policy*, Volume 131.
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- Yi, S., 2019. Determinants of Consumers' Purchasing Behaviour for Certified Aquaculture Products in South Korea.. *SUSTAINABILITY*, Issue 11.
- Zander, K. et al., 2018. *D2.5: Manuscript on consumer preferences and potentials for future fish consumption*, [Online]: SUCCESS Project: Strategic Use of Competitiveness towards Consolidating the Economic Sustainability of the European Seafood Sector.

Appendix 1 Sources used in the grey literature review

Link	Title	Year	Source type	Author type	Country / region
https://thefishsite.com/articles/trends-in-consumer-attitude-and-selection	Trends in consumer attitude and selection	2009	Report	Knowledge site	Europe
https://thefishsite.com/articles/uk-fish-consumption-trends-and-predictions	UK fish consumption trends and predictions	2012	Online article	Knowledge site	U.K.
https://www.seafoodcrc.com/components/com_virtuemart/attachments/2008-779%20Danenberg.pdf	Tracking seafood consumption and measuring consumer acceptance of innovation in the Australian seafood industry	2012	Report	Research institute	Australia
https://dem.ri.gov/sites/g/files/xkgbur861/files/programs/bnatres/agricult/rismc/2012rep.pdf	Rhode Island Seafood Marketing Collaborative: Report to the Rhode Island General Assembly	2012	Report	Rhode Island Seafood Marketing Collaborative	U.S. - Rhode Island
https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/what-are-drivers-for-seafood-consumption/	What are the drivers of seafood consumption?	2014	Online article	Columnist	International
https://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/pdf/FE/FE965/FE965-7937830.pdf	Seafood knowledge, perceptions, and use patterns in Florida: Findings from a 2013 survey of Florida residents	2014	Survey report	Research institute	U.S. - Florida
https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/32332426.pdf	Seafood consumption in Portugal. Patterns, drivers and sustainability	2014	Thesis	PhD student	Portugal
https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK305180/	A Framework for Assessing Effects of the Food System. Annex I	2015	Book	Committee	U.S.
https://repositorio.unican.es/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10902/6505/Global%20Aquaculture%2006.pdf;sequence=1	Public Opinions Pose Barriers For Tuna Consumption	2015	Magazine article	Organisation	International

https://www.michigan.gov/-/media/Project/Websites/mdard/documents/animals/aquaculture/aquaculturemisbdc.pdf?rev=bae6826f227b406bbf4f01e2becb7985	Aquaculture industry report	2015	Report	Industry research company	U.S.
https://www.royalgreenland.com/globalassets/news--si/seafood--sustainability-report-2015.pdf	Seafood & sustainability - Influences on the buying behaviour of seafood purchasers	2015	Report	Seafood company (Greenland) and consultancy company	International
https://www.msc.org/docs/default-source/default-document-library/about-the-msc/msc-consumer-survey-2016-infographic-seafood-consumers-put-sustainability-before-price-and-brand.pdf	Seafood consumers put sustainability before price and brand	2016	Infographic	MSC	International
https://www.aquafeed.com/newsroom/news/uk-consumers-rate-seafood-sustainability-over-price/	UK - Consumers rate seafood sustainability over price	2016	News article	Aquafeed company	International
https://sustainablebrands.com/read/stakeholder-trends-and-insights/majority-of-global-seafood-consumers-putting-sustainability-concerns-over-price-brand	Majority of Global Seafood Consumers Putting Sustainability Concerns Over Price, Brand	2016	News article	Brand leaders community	International
https://www.seafoodsource.com/news/foodservice-retail/new-survey-sees-seafood-consumers-placing-sustainability-before-price-and-brand	New seafood survey sees seafood consumers placing sustainability before price and brand	2016	Online article	Columnist	International
https://www.msc.org/media-centre/press-releases/press-release/seafood-consumers-put-sustainability-before-price-and-brand	Seafood consumers put sustainability before price and brand	2016	Online article	Marine Stewardship Council	International

https://www.statista.com/statistics/629687/seafood-purchase-drivers-united-kingdom-uk/	General purchase drivers for why a particular seafood product was chosen in Great Britain in 2015	2016	Online survey results	Data provision company	U.K.
https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/seafood-in-europe-a-food/file	Seafood in Europe: A food system approach for sustainability	2016	Report	EU agency	Europe
http://www.primfish.cetmar.org/sites/default/files/D4_2_Qualitative_research_report.pdf	Deliverable 4.2 Qualitative research report: analysis interviews aimed mainly at identifying the main positive and negative drivers of fish/seafood consumption (for the chosen species)	2016	Report	EU project	Europe (France, Germany, UK, Italy, and Spain)
https://www.oraqua.eu/content/download/110480/file/OrAqua%20D%203_1.pdf	Deliverable D3.1: Consumer aspects: Report on consumer aspects related to European organic aquaculture	2016	Report	EU project	Europe
https://www.seafish.org/document/?ufprt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	Fish as Food: An initial review of developments, implications and practical responses from industry and Seafish	2016	Report	Public body	U.K.
https://seafood.no/contentassets/6b8fa7b9742b4b0d9b2cc4a8d87af7a5/french-seafood-study.pdf	Seafood study 2016 Insights and outlook: The French and seafood	2016	Survey report	Norwegian Seafood Council	France
https://munin.uit.no/bitstream/handle/10037/9374/thesis.pdf?sequence=2	Examining barriers to seafood consumption among young adults in Norway and Russia	2016	Thesis	Master's student	Norway & Russia

https://www.todaysdietitian.com/newarchives/0317p16.shtml	Seafood: Fishing for answers	2017	Magazine article	Columnist	U.S.
https://cetmar.org/the-european-research-project-primefish-delivers-its-first-results-on-seafood-consumption-patterns/	The European research project PrimeFish delivers its first results on seafood consumption patterns	2017	Online article	Research institute	Europe
https://www.eumofa.eu/documents/20178/84590/EU+consumer+habits+final+report+.pdf/5c61348d-a69c-449e-a606-f5615a3a7e4c	EU consumer habits regarding fishery and aquaculture products final report	2017	Report	EU agency	Europe
https://www.eumofa.eu/documents/20178/84590/Annex+1+-+Mapping+of+studies.pdf	EU consumer habits regarding fishery and aquaculture products. Annex 1 - mapping and analysis of existing studies on consumer habits.	2017	Report	EU agency	Europe
http://www.primefish.cetmar.org/sites/sites/default/files/D4_6_Demand_stimulation.pdf	Deliverable 4.6 Report on social awareness, attempts to stimulate fish consumption and negative press	2017	Report	EU project	Europe
https://www.spring-nutrition.org/publications/reports/sierra-leone-barrier-analysis-survey-fish-and-pumpkin	Sierra Leone: Barrier Analysis Survey on Fish and Pumpkin	2017	Report	Funded project	Sierra Leone
https://edepot.wur.nl/421667	From aid to responsible trade: driving competitive aquaculture sector development in Kenya.	2017	Report	University & State Department of Fisheries, Kenya	Kenya

https://agriculture.canada.ca/en/international-trade/market-intelligence/exporting-your-agri-food-european-union/exporting-fish-and-seafood-european-union-guide-canadian-business	Exporting fish and seafood to the European Union: A guide for Canadian business	2018	Business guide	Government ministry	EU
https://literatur.thuenen.de/digbib_extern/dn_060975.pdf	D2.5 Manuscript on consumer preferences and potentials for future fish consumption: summary of WP2 results	2018	Report	EU project	Europe
Found via link on https://www.seafish.org/insight-and-research/consumer-research/	Seafish State of the nation study 2018 UK report	2018	Report	Non-departmental public body	UK
https://oceanpanel.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/The-Future-of-Food-from-the-Sea.pdf	The Future of Food from the Sea	2019	Blue paper	Expert group	International
https://www.foodandlandusecoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Seafood-Demand-Literature-Review- final.pdf	Seafood demand literature review: Consumer preferences, drivers of seafood demand, and demand for sustainable ocean management	2019	Literature review	Lab	International
https://www.supermarketperimeter.com/articles/4118-foodservice-drives-retail-growth-in-mollusk-category	Foodservice drives retail growth in mollusk category	2019	Magazine article	Columnist	U.S.
https://www.frdc.com.au/sites/default/files/products/2018-092%20Food Australia April-May%202019.pdf	Promoting sustainable Australian fish and seafood	2019	Magazine article	Market research company	Australia
https://www.winsightgrocerybusiness.com/fresh-food/seafood-demand-rises-retailers-aim-splash	Seafood demand rises as retailers aim for a splash	2019	Online article	Information services company	U.S.

https://sciworthy.com/when-it-comes-to-buying-seafood-there-are-five-kinds-of-people-which-one-are-you/	When it comes to buying seafood, there are five kinds of people. Which one are you?	2019	Online article	Nonprofit organisation	Germany
https://www.mpi.govt.nz/dmsdocument/38750-New-Zealand-seafood-consumer-preferences	New Zealand seafood consumer preferences	2019	Report	Government ministry	International (New Zealand, Australia, US, Japan, China)
https://www.frdc.com.au/sites/default/files/2021-06/2019_Unpackingseafoodexperience_report.pdf	Unpacking the consumer seafood experience	2019	Report	Market research company	Australia
https://fyi.extension.wisc.edu/localfoodmarketing/files/2019/04/ConsumerAttitudesTowardWisconsinFarm-RaisedFish.pdf	Consumer Attitudes Toward Wisconsin Farm-Raised Fish Public Opinion and Marketing Recommendations	2019	Report	University professors	U.S. - Wisconsin
https://www.msc.org/understanding-seafood-consumers	Understanding seafood consumers	2020	Infographic	Marine Stewardship Council	International
https://eurofish.dk/a-decline-in-norwegian-consumption-of-seafood-is-being-fought-at-several-levels/	A decline in Norwegian consumption of seafood is being fought at several levels	2020	Magazine article	Eurofish	Norway
https://www.ift.org/news-and-publications/food-technology-magazine/issues/2020/november/features/sea-change-new-horizons-in-aquaculture?gclid=EAlaIqobChMIuoGZ8sLY-gIVBOd3Ch2TAgPHEAMYASAAEgJpSfD_BwE	Sea change: New Horizons in aquaculture	2020	Magazine article	Online magazine	International

https://www.grocerydive.com/spons/fish-school-education-is-key-to-driving-sales-of-sustainable-seafood/570600/	Fish School: Education is key to driving sales of sustainable seafood	2020	Online article	Columnist	U.S.
https://en.seafood.no/news-and-media/news-archive/seafood-consumption-driving-shift-towards-more-sustainable-diets/	Seafood consumption driving shift towards more sustainable diets	2020	Online article	Norwegian Seafood Council	International
https://www.msc.org/docs/default-source/default-document-library/for-business/rise-of-the-conscious-food-consumer--europe-webinar-slides.pdf?sfvrsn=6c009b42_4	The rise of the conscious seafood consumer: COVID, climate and conservation; how will these affect consumer habits?	2020	Report slides	MSC and Globescan	Europe
https://seagrant.uconn.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/1985/2020/04/CTSeafoodSurvey.final_.pdf	The Connecticut Seafood Survey	2020	Survey report	Research institute	U.S. - Connecticut
https://gfi.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Seafood-Consumer-Research-Literature-Review-2020-final-as-of-7-7-20-.pdf	Consumer Preferences for Seafood and Applications to Plant-Based and Cultivated Seafood	2020	White paper	Nonprofit think tank	International
https://www.seafoodsource.com/news/foodservice-retail/asmi-report-finds-covid-19-pandemic-boosted-seafood-consumption	ASMI report finds COVID-19 pandemic boosted seafood consumption	2021	Online article	Columnist	U.S.
https://www.supermarketnews.com/seafood/seafood-makes-splash-wellness-shopper	Seafood makes a splash with the wellness shopper	2021	Online article	Columnist	U.S.
https://www.supermarketnews.com/seafood/seafood-sustainability-top-mind-shoppers	Seafood sustainability top of mind for shoppers	2021	Online article	Columnist	U.S.

https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/news/eurobarometer-eu-consumers-stay-loyal-fish-and-seafood-despite-covid-19-crisis-2021-09-09_en	Eurobarometer: EU consumers stay loyal to fish and seafood despite COVID-19 crisis	2021	Online article	European Commission	EU
https://www.safefood.qld.gov.au/newsroom/spotlight-on-the-seafood-industry/	Spotlight on... Australia's seafood consumption	2021	Online article	Regulator	Australia
https://canari.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/CARICOM-SeafoodTrade_StewardFish_Final.pdf	Examination of public policy and private sector purchasing practices to improve consumption and intra-regional trade of seafood for the Caribbean small-scale fisheries sector	2021	Report	Caribbean Natural Resources Institute	Caribbean
https://merid.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Aquaculture-Sectoral-Insights-Summary-Brief-June-2021_Final-1.pdf	Sectoral Insights on the Future of Aquaculture in the US	2021	Report	Nonprofit consultancy	U.S.
https://www.aqua.cl/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Top-Seafood-Consumer-Trends-2021.pdf	Top Seafood Consumer Trends 2021	2021	Report	Norwegian Seafood Council	International
https://digitalarchive.worldfishcenter.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12348/51115/a8a0374ca750f607469af6e05298bb91.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y	A review of fish supply - demand in Tanzania	2021	Report	WorldFish	Tanzania
https://auri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/AURI_Food-Fish-Survey-Report_051821.pdf	Food Fish Consumer Survey	2021	Survey report	Research institute	U.S. - Minnesota
https://aquaculture2020.org/uploads/gca-tr9-value-chains-and-market-access-for-aquaculture-products.pdf	Thematic paper: Value chains and market access for aquaculture products	2021	Thematic paper	Conference attendees (FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture and	International

				two university professors)	
https://www.todaysdietitian.com/newarchives/0222p30.shtml	Seafood innovations: How a pandemic pivot and consumer curiosity created the perfect seafood storm	2022	Magazine article	Columnist	U.S.
https://www.nourish.marketing/news/canada-has-plenty-of-fish-only-why-arent-we-eating-them	Canada has plenty of fish. Only, why aren't we eating them?	2022	News article	Marketing agency	Canada
https://www.perishablenews.com/seafood/most-comprehensive-asc-consumer-research-to-date-highlights-potential-of-seafood-to-be-sustainable-source-of-protein/	Most Comprehensive ASC Consumer Research to Date Highlights Potential of Seafood to be Sustainable Source of Protein	2022	Online article	Certification programme (Aquaculture Stewardship Council - ASC)	International
https://aquafeed.co.uk/entrada/most-comprehensive-asc-consumer-research-to-date-highlights-potential-of-seafood-to-be-sustainable-source-of-protein?-55044	Most comprehensive ASC consumer research to date highlights potential of seafood to be sustainable source of protein	2022	Online article	Aquafeed company	International
https://thefishsite.com/articles/new-asc-research-shows-that-health-and-sustainability-claims-are-driving-global-seafood-purchases	New ASC research shows that health and sustainability claims are driving global seafood purchases	2022	Online article	Knowledge site	International
https://storebrands.com/gone-fishing-growing-demand-gives-retailers-new-opportunities-seafood	Gone fishing: Growing demand gives retailers new opportunities for seafood	2022	Online article	Magazine	U.S.
https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5c3f248bb10598f8fdb7fbf6/t/630f872006d7342f9c80f5b3/1661962022195/APPG+on+Fisheries+Policy+Brief+Fisheries+and+Food+Policy.pdf	UK All Parliamentary Group on Fisheries Policy Brief Fisheries and food policy.	2022	Policy brief	Parliamentary group	U.K.
https://assets.gov.ie/231811/0c06ecfc-aceb-4db6-bdf7-bc9f4bbb1022.pdf	Draft national strategic plan for sustainable aquaculture development	2022	Report	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Ireland	Ireland

https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/fish-seafood/certified-sustainable-seafood	Exporting certified sustainable seafood to Europe	2022	Report	Government ministry	Europe
https://munin.uit.no/bitstream/handle/10037/24489/thesis.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y	Consumers' Value Perceptions of Seafood: An analysis of consumer attitudes, preferences, and willingness to pay for seafood in Bangladesh	2022	Thesis	PhD student	Bangladesh

Appendix 2 Sources used in the scientific literature review

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Alexander et al (2016)	To investigate the public understanding of aquaculture benefits and impacts, knowledge of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA), and also collecting demographic information.	n 2520	Ireland, Israel, Italy, Norway, The UK	<p>Drivers: improved health and nutrition, job creation, prevention of overfishing, reliable and affordable food source, economic boost in coastal areas.</p> <p>Barriers: pollution from feed & waste, animal welfare, impacts on scenery, overfishing, escapes eat wild fishes, spread of diseases and parasites, conflicts with other marine users.</p>
Allegro et al (2021)	To know and evaluate consumption, preferences and the knowledge of labelling legislation about wild and farmed seafood products in Sicily (Italy).	n 1700	Italy (Sicily)	<p>Drivers: taste, texture, quality, nutritional properties, naturalness, safety, charm of the product, digestibility.</p> <p>Barriers: lack of habit, wild fish, environmental impact, lack of animal welfare.</p>
Ankamah-Yeboah et al (2019)	To determine whether consumers are willing to pay more for aquacultured fish products with organic labels when informed specifically about environmental and animal welfare aspects of the production criteria	n 1236	Germany	<p>Drivers: organic label, animal welfare, convenience, country of origin.</p>
Banovic et al (2019)	To examine the effect of health and nutrition claims, country-of-origin (COO), and eco-labels on consumer choice of new aquaculture products in a cross-cultural context.	n 1598	France, Germany, Italy, Spain, the UK	<p>Drivers: country of origin, eco-label, health and nutrition.</p> <p>Barriers: concerns about sustainability.</p>
Brayden et al (2018)	To investigate consumer preferences for product attributes of shellfish and seaweed salad focusing on production source (farm-raised, wild-harvested), certification status (organic, sustainably harvested, non-certified), and product origin (home state, U.S., imported).	n 2155	USA	<p>Drivers: origin, local production, certification, price.</p> <p>Barriers: harvesting method, wild produce.</p>
Bronnmann & Hoffmann (2018)	To investigate the importance of different attributes, including farmed and wild caught, and non-eco-labelled and eco-labelled, for turbot in the	n 485	Germany (North)	<p>Drivers: quality, taste, freshness, health, appearance.</p> <p>Barriers: lifestyle (e.g. vegan/vegetarian), production method, environmental concerns, taste.</p>

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
	German market as well as consumers' willingness to pay for specific attributes.			
Budhathoki et al (2022)	Therefore, this paper aims to perform consumer segmentation through the food-related lifestyle instrument and determine the factors influencing intention to buy organic fish among Danish consumers applying the theory of planned behaviour.	n 237	Denmark	Drivers: purchase frequency, past experience, household size with children under five years, employment status, consumer segments. Barriers: difficulty to judge the quality, and availability of organic fish.
Cantillo et al (2021)	To compare consumer preferences and attitudes, analysing whether or not the implementation of EU policies and regulations improves the market conditions.	n 27,732	European Union	Drivers: healthiness, taste, low price, age, wealth, presence of children in the household, household size, satisfaction with own life. Barriers: Poor understanding about label information.
Cardoso et al (2016)	To present and analyse the results of a survey into the seafood preferences and patterns in the Portuguese population, with an emphasis on education level, age, and health determinants.	n 1083	Portugal	Drivers: fish type, cultural habits, organoleptic characteristics, product presentation, education level, age (younger). Barriers: age (elderly), higher values of body mass index.
Carrasson et al (2021)	To determine whether scientific-supported information contrasting one myth related to aquaculture (the food provided in aquaculture have detrimental effects on fish quality) could contribute to a better perception of farmed products.	n 300	Spain	Drivers: nutritional aspects, healthiness, affordable price. Barriers: low level of trust in production methods, low level of safety of products, low level of information about production process.
Claret et al (2012)	To identify the relative importance of different attributes on consumer perception of different factors (country of origin, obtaining method, storage conditions and purchasing price) in the decision-making process when choosing sea fish.	n 81	Spain	Drivers: country of origin, price, harvesting method. Barriers: wild fish, quality.
Claret et al (2016)	To determine consumers' liking for both farmed and wild fish, and to evaluate the effect of information regarding the species and the	n 597	Spain	Drivers: origin of fish, sensory characteristics, sustainability, safety, quality, nutritional value Barriers: origin of fish, sensory characteristics

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
	method of production (wild capture/aquaculture) on it.			
Danso et al (2017)	To assess households' willingness to pay for different characteristics of fish (i.e., reared with different sources of water, including wastewater, and certified or not) and the potential implications for wastewater-based aquaculture businesses.	n 136	Vietnam (Hanoi)	Drivers: belief in the efficiency of the wastewater treatment technology, safety level of the treated wastewater, quality of wastewater fed-fish, location of purchase, certification by a government agency, taste, origin, reliable sellers available, safety, freshness, healthiness of fish, easiness to process and cook fish.
Danso et al (2022)	To explore the potential market opportunities and challenges facing the commercialization of wastewater aquaculture systems in Peru.	n 443	Peru	Drivers: wastewater fed fish. Barriers: freshwater fed fish, label.
Davidson et al (2012)	To investigate Hawaii consumers' willingness to pay for fish product attributes including farmed vs. wild-caught.	n 566	Hawaii	Drivers: seafood type, product presentation (fresh), origin label, harvesting method, price. Barriers: environmental concerns, taste, freshness.
Ellingsen et al (2014)	To assess how concerned Norwegians are about fish welfare, to investigate Norwegians' willingness to pay for salmon filet made from welfare-assured farmed fish with high levels of welfare, and to examine Norwegian opinions about the appropriate way to pay for better welfare standards in fish production.	n 2147	Norway	Drivers: gender, household income. Barriers: age, education.
Fernández-Polanco & Luna (2012)	To identify factors that contribute to improve the appraisal of aquaculture among seafood consumers, avoiding expectancy of risk and rejection and help to identify which factors exert the strongest influence on perceptions about aquaculture, and what are the categories of each which favour positive or negative effects on consumer's beliefs.	n 3200 (2005) and n 2934 (2006)	Spain	Drivers: consumers' beliefs about safety and environmental benefits of aquaculture, level of education, trust in the sources of information, attitudes towards food harvest technologies. Barriers: perceived risk from food technology.
Freeman et al (2012)	To report on bi-national (Germany–Israel) research on relationships between public attitudes, behaviours and preferences related to marine aquaculture.	n 431 (Israel), n 363 (Germany)	Germany, Israel	Drivers: environment concerns, food security, prevention of overfishing, relieve pressure on wild fish stocks, knowledge, sources of information.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Galati et al (2021)	To investigate the role of consumer altruism and other socio-cultural factors in predicting how much attention consumers pay to seafood eco-labels.	n 354 (Italy) n 332 (Spain)	Spain, Italy	Drivers: sustainability, work conditions, eco-labels, level of education, age, knowledge, altruism.
Grimsrud et al (2013)	To estimate Norwegian consumers' willingness to pay for improving farmed salmon welfare through breeding.	n 771	Norway	Drivers: concern about animal welfare. Barriers: animal welfare, environmental concerns, source of information.
Güney (2019)	To investigate consumers' motivations and perceptions of fish obtained from different production methods, namely wild or farmed.	n 526	Turkey	Drivers: availability, decrease in wild fish stocks, production process, easiness to prepare, fish variety, age (younger), income (low). Barriers: wild fish freshness, place of eating, naturalness, origin, age (elderly).
Hall et al (2013)	To understand general seafood preferences (familiarity, price, freshness, health and environmental concerns), beliefs and attitudes specific to aquaculture versus wild products, and how those cognitive factors affect decisions to consume types of farmed seafood products.	n 1159	USA	Drivers: healthiness, environmental benefits. Barriers: wild fish, pollution and contamination.
Hoerterer et al (2022)	To identify the socio-demographic factors that influence seafood consumption behaviour, the knowledge base on and attitude towards aquaculture of different groups on a showcase basis in Germany.	n 442	Germany	Drivers: sustainability, social welfare, price, sustainability as compared to terrestrial livestock (i.e. beef), fish welfare, food security, eating frequency, healthy lifestyle, environmental sustainability, availability of information on animal welfare, local/domestic or European production, natural production methods, moral and ethical reasons, daily habits, vicinity to fish farms. Barriers: wild fish, pollution, use of antibiotics, parasites, impact on wild fish populations, moral barriers, high prices.
Hoque (2021)	To measure consumers' perceived value of sustainability indicators for fish consumers.	n 490	Bangladesh	Drivers: sustainability of the product, presence of environmental indicators. Barriers: high price, water pollution, health concerns, use of inappropriate feeding.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Hoque & Alam (2020)	To examine the influence of consumers' perceived knowledge, knowledge discrepancy and confusion on the intention to purchase farmed fish via a survey design regarding perceptions, buying and consumption practices of urban households in Chittagong, Bangladesh.	n 498 households	Bangladesh (Chittagong city)	
Hoque & Myrland (2021)	To understand consumer preferences regarding food safety.	n 422	Bangladesh	Drivers: coastal-farmed fish, local inspection. Barriers: inland-farmed fish.
Hoque et al (2021)	To assess the market potential for organically farmed shrimp.	n 660	Bangladesh	Drivers: farmed fish, organic farming, inland farming, coastal farming. Barriers: conventional aquaculture methods, price.
Hoque et al (2022a)	To examine the effects of consumers' ambiguity tolerance and confusion avoidance on their perceived knowledge of farmed fish and the aquaculture industry and to assess the impacts of consumers' socio-economic factors on the level of their perceived knowledge of farmed fish.	n 1041	Bangladesh	Barriers: excessive information, reliable sources of information limited.
Hoque et al (2022b)	To explore seafood markets by assessing the demand for traceability information attributes by utilising data from an experimental survey in an emerging market such as Bangladesh.	n 404	Bangladesh	Drivers: local production, imported fish, low use of additives as formaline. Barriers: wild fish, concern for food safety.
Hynes et al (2019)	To examine Norwegian and Irish consumers' willingness to pay a premium for sustainably farmed salmon using the contingent valuation method.	n 1960	Norway, Ireland	Drivers: origin, environmentally friendliness, environmental labelling Barriers: environmental risks (threat to marine environment)
Jonell et al (2016)	To investigate which psychological consumer characteristics influence demand for eco-labelled seafood by correlating consumers' stated purchasing of eco-labelled seafood.	n 406	Sweden (Stockholm)	Barriers: food illiteracy, lack of trust for commercial actors, concern for negative environmental impacts. Drivers: recognition of eco-labels, consumer awareness, consumers' subjective knowledge, consumers' pro-environmental self-identification, perceived consumer effectiveness, sources of information.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Kim et al (2017)	To examine the role of subjective knowledge and attitude about aquaculture, and their effect on intention to participate in value-added culinary aquaculture tourism experiences.	n 629	USA (six regions of Florida and South Carolina)	Drivers: subjective knowledge and attitudes, knowledge about aquaculture, culinary preferences, familiarity with media against aquaculture, frequency of eating or familiarity with specific products, retailers' promotions. Barriers: lack of knowledge, negative public perception of aquaculture.
Kitano & Yamamoto (2020)	To understand how consumers compare fish to other protein sources and how different consumer attributes influence the purchase frequency of fish.	n 3000	Japan	Drivers: past experience, knowledge, socio-economic attributes, familiarity with fish, accessibility, closeness to fish, eating habits, availability, easiness to prepare, easiness to consume. Barriers: knowledge on fisheries, availability, wild fish, quality, price of meat, price.
Kralik et al (2022)	To examine the market potential of aquaponics by conducting a series of multidisciplinary studies to compare yellow perch from a combined Recirculating Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture System with fish from traditional production methods (wild-caught & farm-raised).	n 63 n 344	USA	Drivers: taste, texture, appearance, health, labelling, quality, environmental impact, eco-labelling, production method.
Krešić et al (2022)	To profile Croatian fishery consumers based on their intention to consume farmed fish.	n 977	Croatia	Drivers: health, self-efficacy, availability, taste, quality, safety, price, origin, eco-labelling, income levels, place of residence, place of purchase, eating frequency, place of eating, product information, age (older). Barriers: wild fish, lack of understanding of labelling information, price, income level (low), healthiness.
Kuleszl et al (2019)	To identify Swedish consumers' opinions about use of hormone and triploidization sterilization techniques for salmonids.	n 1005	Sweden	Drivers: price, no sterilization treatment. Barriers: price, sterilization treatment.
Lee & Nam (2019)	To identify determinants of live fish consumption frequency.	n 800	South Korea	Drivers: safety, fish species. Barriers: price.
Lourenço et al (2021)	To characterize consumers motivations and preferences regarding sea urchin roe.	n 281	Portugal	Drivers: place of eating, high valued seafood, place of residence (coastal areas).

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Pupavac et al (2022)	To study the socio- demographic factors related to the consumption of fish and seafood among the population of the Primorsko-goranska County in Croatia and to determine people's attitudes, choices, and reasons for the consumption of fish and seafood.	n 2910	Croatia (Primorsko-goranska County)	Drivers: age (older), education level, lifestyle, habits, origin, price, labels, quality, lifestyle, eating frequency, taste, health, source of information. Barriers: quality, taste, colour, shape, price, wild fish.
Moutopoulos et al (2022)	To investigate consumers' attitudes towards the purchase and consumption of bivalves, and more specifically, towards the edible pearl oyster <i>Pinctada imbricata radiata</i> , in the Greek shellfish market.	n 133	Greece	Drivers: place of residence (coastal areas), occasion for consumption, season, freshness, expiration date, packaging, hygiene, age, education level, point of sales, occasion for consumption, food processing, packaging, hygiene.
Murray & Little (2022)	To assess underlying reasons for the recurrent poor market demand and future prospects for the policy and rural food-security through an evaluation of positive (actual) and normative (aspirational) consumer preferences for inland fish and its farmed substitutes.	n 39 (Fase 1) n 165 (Fase 2)	Sri-Lanka	Drivers: size of fish, cultural norms, fish species, food (vegetables) availability, food security.
Murray et al (2017)	To better understanding of the relative importance that grocery store consumers assign to several factors when purchasing seafood in British Columbia, Canada.	n 315	Canada	Drivers: past experience, taste, smell, appearance, price, health benefits, local food.
Onozaka et al (2014)	To investigate the effects healthiness, value for money, and convenience have on salmon consumption frequencies.	n 2500 (500 per country)	The UK, Germany, France, Russia, Sweden	Drivers: healthiness, value for money, convenience, freshness, taste, cooking method, product information, price, quality. Barriers: Lack of consumer knowledge, perceived inconvenience.
Pereira et al (2017)	To measure: consumption habits with respect to all types of fish; the market share of aquaculture fish; market size and channels; the factors determining the acceptance of the new product; the consumer probability of buying and recommending the new product; the fair price of the new product; and the consumer profile.	n 105	Portugal (Algarve region)	Drivers: external characteristics of the fish, fish species, nutritional values, origin, processing method, price, freshness, place of purchase, quality certification, product information, expert advice.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Petereit et al (2022)	To understand the extent to which country-specific contexts and degree of scientific knowledge contribute to the purchasing behaviour of consumers across Europe.	n 383	Spain, Belgium, Germany, Poland	Drivers: lifestyle, personal beliefs, vicinity to a farm, processing methods, cultural practices, social pressure, world views, traceability, certification, animal welfare, health benefits, origin, price. Barriers: source of information.
Pulcini et al (2020)	To provide: 1) a national picture of consumer habits, preferences, and perceptions regarding aquaculture products; 2) information about consumer willingness to pay for some added values of aquatic food, such as sustainability, certification, traceability, and security; and 3) recommendations for stakeholders interested in promoting certified aquaculture products on the Italian market.	n 7795	Italy	Drivers: place of eating, age (younger), type of fish, product presentation, freshness, taste, easiness to prepare, traceability, label. Barriers: age (older), difficulty to recognize freshness, lack of knowledge, unavailability, lack of trust, price, taste, safety.
Quagrainie (2019)	To assess the potential market for striped bass grown in the Midwest through consumers' willingness to pay.	n 581	USA	Drivers: origin, freshness, presentation. Barriers: harvesting method, presentation.
Ribeiro et al (2019)	To assess consumers' preferences regarding fish consumption, and their perception of farmed seabream as a functional food.	n 778	Portugal	Drivers: freshness, taste, price, quality, nutritional value, texture, convenience of use, easiness to prepare, ecological impact, harvesting method, fish species, label.
Rickertsen et al (2017)	To investigate consumers' preferences expressed either as attitudes, sensory valuations, or willingness to pay for wild and farmed fish, and country or area of origin.	n 276	France	Drivers: price, taste, convenience, family liking, easiness to prepare, easiness of use, occasion for consumption, environmental sustainability, fish welfare. Barriers: healthiness, safety, price, taste, convenience, family habits, easiness to prepare, occasion for consumption, origin, environmental impact.
Ruiz-Chico et al (2020)	To determine the social acceptance in Andalusian Atlantic provinces (Spain) of aquaculture industries compared to that of traditional fisheries based on their corresponding social carrying capacity.	n 579	Spain (Andalucia)	Drivers: acceptance of aquaculture, socio-economic benefits, price (affordability), variety of species, gender, income levels, satisfaction with farmed fish as a food, health, nutrition. Also in comparison with traditional fishery. Barriers: income levels, environmental impact (industrial feeds and chemical products), quality, taste.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
Sagun & Saygi (2021)	To determine the consumption habits of consumers in Turkey's coastal region.	n 650	Turkey (coastal areas)	Drivers: naturalness, price, environmental sustainability, freshness, presentation.
Santeramo et al (2017)	To investigate the role of consumers' attitudes with respect to sustainable attributes (namely food safety and respect of the environment) in order to suggest on their potential role to catalyse the transition toward bioeconomies.	n 800	Italy (Milano, Bologna, Roma and Bari)	Drivers: taste, health, status symbol. Barriers: safety risks.
Schlag & Ystgaard (2013)	To compare consumer perceptions of the production and consumption of wild and farmed fish in Europe.	n 208 participants (28 focus groups)	France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Spain, Norway, The UK	Drivers: local economic benefits, environment benefits, healthiness. Barriers: socio-economic risks, lack of trust, production methods, unnatural, unfamiliar.
Soley et al (2019)	Assess influence of shrimp product labelling on consumers' acceptance, perceptions, and willingness to pay.	n 505	USA	Drivers: freshness, local produce, environmental standards.
Stancu et al (2021)	To identify and profile food-related lifestyle segments of consumers that vary in terms of their willingness to buy new aquaculture fish products.	n 1500 (500 per country)	Spain, France, Germany	Drivers: healthiness, nutrition, taste, safety, openness to innovation, frequency of eating. Barriers: reluctance to innovation, easiness to prepare.
Temesi et al (2020)	To explore perceived risks that serve to exacerbate Hungarian consumers' low fish consumption, and to measure their effects to identify potential strategies to most effectively increase fish consumption.	n 1042	Hungary	Barriers: physical risk, functional risk, social risk.
van Osch et al (2019)	To assess how the public makes decisions on what type of salmon or sea bream to buy based on the attributes of the product.	n 2520 (Ireland n 500), Israel (n 500), Italy (n 508), Norway (n 501) and the UK (n 511)	Ireland, The UK, Italy, Israel, Norway	Drivers: quality, freshness, taste, sustainability, origin, knowledge, price, eco-label. Barriers: lack of knowledge, lack of trust, price.
Vanhonacker et al (2012)	To improve current knowledge and bridge geographical gaps with respect to image studies in Europe	n 3213	France, Spain, the Netherlands, Greece, The UK, Belgium, Poland, Italy, Finland,	Drivers: availability, price. Barriers: wild fish, inability to prepare, production methods, health, quality, environment, price, animal welfare, freshness.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
			Hungary, Germany, Denmark, Czech Republic	
Weir & Sproul (2019)	To clarify willingness to pay for salmon fillets with varying characteristics, including GM technology and GM feed.	n 1043	USA	Drivers: subjective knowledge, perceived personal competence on GM technologies. Barriers: healthiness, environmental risks.
Weir et al (2020)	To investigate how production process labels and information about potential positive and/or negative aspects of GM technology affects demand for novel seafood products.	n 1041	United States	Drivers: taste, freshness, healthiness, origin, price, local, expert advice, low fat. Barriers: wild fish, GMO in feeding, GMO in fish.
Witter et al (2021)	To assess the potential demand for products supplied through seafood alternative food networks (AFNs) and provide better understanding of how consumer seafood preferences and demographic patterns in the Canadian marketplace may affect the future potential of seafood AFNs.	n 2006	Canada	Drivers: taste, appearance, freshness, price, product information, health benefits, sustainability, production method, origin, easiness to prepare, local economic benefits, certification, species type, quality, presentation. Barriers: taste, price, healthiness, environmental impacts, easiness to prepare, availability, lifestyle, ethical concerns, accessibility, safety concerns.
Wongprawmas (2022)	To examine the influence of consumers' perceptions and knowledge on their intention to purchase farmed and wild fish.	n 804	Italy	Drivers: information, nutritional values, healthiness, ethical aspects, safety, price. Barriers: wild fish, environmental impacts, age (younger), habit.
Xuan (2020)	To identify socio-economic and fish-eating trends in an Eastern Community in Sri Lanka.	n 353	Vietnam	Drivers: eco-label, knowledge of certification. Barriers: wild produce.
Yi (2019a)	This study aims to investigate consumers' decision-making process for purchasing certified aquaculture products using the theory of the planned behaviour model.	n 960	South Korea	Drivers: consumer attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control.
Yi (2019b)	To investigate how psychological characteristics affect consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable integrated agriculture–aquaculture (IAA) products by estimating the value consumers place on sustainable rice–fish	n 525	South Korea	Drivers: household income, attitude, social norms, age.

Author(s)	Aim of the study	Sample size	Country	Drivers and barriers
	farming products (i.e., organic rice and loach from IAA systems).			
Yi (2019c)	To determine consumer perception of the environment through the context of red seabream (<i>Pagrus major</i>) aquaculture and the use of copper-alloy nets.	n 1000	South Korea	Drivers: fish type, production method, consumption frequency.
Yin et al (2022)	To measure Chinese consumer preferences and willingness to pay for different aquatic product safety information attributes considering stated attribute non-attendance.	n 556	China	Drivers: safety, organic certification, traceability, brand, geographical indication.
Yip et al (2017)	To investigate consumer acceptance of and willingness to pay for Integrated Multitrophic versus Closed Containment Aquaculture as alternative methods of production of farmed salmon.	n 1631	USA	Drivers: naturalness, healthiness, environmental friendliness, taste, availability, price, production technology.
Zander et al (2017)	To identify ways to increase the market share of sustainable fish from aquaculture by analysing consumer awareness and preferences for sustainable aquaculture products and by drawing conclusions on improving communication in the German market.	n 56	Germany	Drivers: availability of information, transparency. Barriers: lack of knowledge.
Zhang et al (2021)	To understand the Chinese market, in particular its consumer behaviour for seafood consumption.	n 1201	China (Beijing, Shanghai, Xian, Nanchang, Shenyang, Yinchuan)	Drivers: seafood types, price, income levels, local, education level, healthiness, nutrition, are associated with regional economies. Barriers: environmental concerns.

Appendix 3 Stakeholder interview guide

Stakeholder Interview Questionnaire

Introduction

FishEUTrust is an EU-funded project which aims to define means to increase consumers' trust in the consumption of farmed seafood by ensuring sustainability and delivering solutions for a transparent and traceable seafood supply chain necessary to promote high-end, pan-European farmed seafood. To assure the trust of consumers it is necessary to understand their concerns, drivers and barriers to consume farmed seafood. After proceeding with a literature review, both in scientific and policy and market literature, we are interviewing experts from the following stakeholder groups: academia, industry, civil society, government, and environment. In a sample of consortium countries. The purpose of these interviews is to validate the findings from the literature review and to clarify concepts terminology highlighted by the literature review as important. In turn, this will inform the development of a survey that we will distribute to consumers in the countries covered by FishEUTrust.

The objectives of the interviews are the following:

1. To further define terms that are currently ill-defined in the literature, such as "freshness", "sustainability", "trust", "quality", "safety", and "labelling".
2. To understand the interactions between these terms.
3. To understand how consumers perceive aquaculture/farmed fish and wild fish, and the differences between the two.
4. To understand what drives consumer behaviours, from each specific stakeholder (industry, academia, civil society, government, academia) perspective towards consumption of farmed fish and seafood.

The project follows regulations of data privacy protection as you have been previously informed.

We are grateful for your availability and generosity to share your knowledge with FishEUTrust.

Funded by the
European Union

2	3
<p style="text-align: center;">Dissemination level - Confidential</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> FishEUTrust</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Which drivers and barriers do you observe in the seafood supply chain regarding sustainability? (Relevant for both fisheries and aquaculture). 4. How do consumers see other dimensions (economic and social) of sustainability for aquaculture products? <p>Regarding "Labelling"</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the labelling categories utilized in aquaculture? 2. How do consumers understand the different categories of labels, including voluntary attributes, for aquaculture production and products? 3. Is the current labelling system adequate for farmed seafood? In case not, what needs to be changed? <p>Regarding "Trust"</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do consumers understand trust when it comes to purchasing fish and seafood products? 2. How important is transparency in the supply chain for building trust in fish and seafood products? How can transparency be assured? 	
<p>Funded by the European Union</p>	

Appendix 4 English language version of the consumer survey

Aim of study

The purpose of this study is to collect information about consumers' seafood purchasing habits and the drivers and barriers of seafood consumption in three European countries – Italy, Slovenia, and Denmark – and how these factors interact with socio-demographic characteristics.

Sample criteria

Resident in survey country

Age: ≥18 years

Diet: Includes fish and/or seafood

Only people who are responsible for at least half of their household's grocery shopping

Representative sample of each country's household composition

Representative spread of age, gender (M/F), income, geographic region (including urban/rural)

Welcome!

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this survey.

The survey will take no longer than 15 minutes to complete.

The information you provide will not be made public and will not be used to identify you in any way.

Please be honest in your responses as they will remain anonymous and confidential.

Age. How old are you?

Age groups

- < 18 → End of survey
- 18-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60-75
- 75 → End of survey

Gender. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other
- I don't wish to answer

Screener

Consumption and purchasing habits

S1. How much of the grocery shopping for your household are you responsible for?

- Less than half → End of survey
- About half
- More than half

S2. How much of the cooking do you do for your household?

- Less than half

- About half
- More than half

S3. Please indicate how frequently you purchase different types of seafood using the scale provided.

	Once a month or less often	2 – 3 times per month	Once a week	2 – 3 times per week	4 – 5 times per week	Every day or almost every day
Finfish (e.g. salmon, cod, plaice)						
Shellfish (e.g. clams, oysters, mussels)						
Cephalopods (e.g. octopus, squid)						
Crustaceans (e.g. prawns, crab, lobster)						

If 'Once a month or less often' at all 4 items → End of survey

Information for respondents

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Its purpose is to collect information about the seafood that people purchase and eat and how products' characteristics and the shopping environment influence purchasing decisions.

All of the questions relate to the purchase of seafood for eating at home rather than the seafood that is chosen in restaurants or cafes.

For the purposes of this questionnaire the term seafood includes all forms of fish (e.g. salmon, cod, plaice), shellfish (e.g. clams, oysters, mussels), cephalopods (e.g. octopus, squid), and crustaceans (e.g. prawns, crab, and lobster). Unless a question asks about a specific type of seafood, please assume that it refers generally to all the types of seafood that you purchase and eat.

Q1. Please indicate how frequently you purchase seafood (of any type) from different places using the scale provided.

	Once a month or less often	2 – 3 times per month	Once a week	2 – 3 times per week	4 – 5 times per week	Every day or almost every day
From a fishmonger						
From a fish market						
From a supermarket						

Q2. This question focuses on how often you purchase seafood that has been pre-prepared to varying degrees.

Please indicate how frequently you purchase the following products using the scale provided.

	Once a month or less often	2 – 3 times per month	Once a week	2 – 3 times per week	4 – 5 times per week	Every day or almost every day
Whole fish (including bones, scales etc)						

Fish fillets or fish steaks						
Seafood (of any type) prepared with breadcrumbs, batter or sauce						
Frozen seafood (of any type)						
Tinned seafood (of any type)						
Pickled seafood (of any type)						

Knowledge

Q3. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements using the scale provided.

	Strongly disagree			Neutral			Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I know what the term 'aquaculture' means in relation to fish production							
I know whether the seafood that I buy comes from a fish farm or is wild-caught							
I know what the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) logo on seafood products means							
I know what the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) logo on seafood products means							
I know what the organic label on seafood products means							
I know what the Friend of the Sea (FOS) logo on seafood products means							
I know what the Fairtrade logo on seafood products means							

Self-efficacy in relation to seafood storage, preparation and cooking

Q4. The following questions relate to seafood that is chilled when purchased rather than frozen, tinned, pickled or otherwise preserved.

a. How good do you think your knowledge is about how fresh seafood should be stored?

No knowledge			Neutral			Very good knowledge
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

b. How good do you think your skills in preparing and cooking fresh seafood are?

No skills			Neutral			Very good skills
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Importance of different characteristics for chilled seafood

Q5. The following questions relate to seafood that is chilled when purchased rather than frozen, tinned, pickled or otherwise preserved.

How important are the following aspects to you when choosing chilled seafood to buy?

1. that it is produced in {Italy/ Slovenia / Denmark} rather than a different European country
2. that it is produced in Europe rather than outside of Europe
3. that it is easy to prepare and cook
4. that all non-edible parts (e.g. bones, shell, scales) have been removed
5. that it has health benefits
6. that no colourants have been added
7. that it is something that you have tried before
8. that it is something that everyone in your household likes to eat
9. the price
10. that it comes from a sustainable source

Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

(If sustainable source is important) → If Q5_10 > 4

Q6. How important are the following features in judging whether a chilled seafood product comes from a sustainable source?

	Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The certifications that the product has							
The product's country of origin							
The brand of the product							
The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)							
The type of the seafood product (whether it is a fish, shellfish, crustacean, cephalopod)							
The specific species of fish, shellfish, crustacean or cephalopod (whether							

it's a salmon or a tuna, whether it's a mussel or an oyster, etc.)							
The catch method							
Whether the product is wild or farmed							

Q7. When choosing chilled seafood to buy how important is it to you that it is fresh?

Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

(If freshness is important) → Q7 > 4

Q8. How important are the following features in judging a chilled seafood product's freshness?

	Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The best before date or the use by date							
The appearance of the product							
The smell of the product							
The brand of the product							
The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)							
The way in which the product is displayed (e.g. on ice at fishmonger or shop's fish counter, or packaged on supermarket shelf)							

Q9 When choosing chilled seafood to buy how important is it to you that it is high quality?

Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

(If quality is important) → Q9 > 4

Q10. How important are the following features in judging a chilled seafood product's quality?

	Not at all important			Neutral			Very important
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The country of origin							
The catch method							
Whether the product was farmed or wild-caught							
The certifications that the product has							
The appearance of the product							

The brand of the product							
The place of sale (e.g. fishmonger, supermarket, fish market)							
The way in which the product is displayed (e.g. on ice at fishmonger or shop's fish counter, or packaged on supermarket shelf)							

Preferences for wild/farmed fish

Q11. Which of the following statements is most accurate for you?

- I prefer to buy farmed seafood over wild-caught seafood
- I prefer to buy wild-caught seafood over farmed seafood
- It makes no difference to me whether the seafood that I buy is farmed or wild-caught
- I do not know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood

Answer following two Qs unless respondents answer 'I do not know the difference between farmed and wild-caught seafood' to the previous Q)

(Q12_a/e only if Q11 <> 4)

Q12a. Please indicate which of the following statements you think is most accurate

- Farmed seafood is safer to eat than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the safety of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood is safer to eat than farmed seafood

Q12b. Please indicate which of the following statements you think is most accurate

- Farmed seafood tastes better than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the taste of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood tastes better than farmed seafood

Q12c. Please indicate which of the following statements you think is most accurate

- Farming seafood is less harmful to the environment than catching wild seafood
- There is no difference in the environmental effects of wild and farmed seafood production
- Catching wild seafood is less harmful to the environment than farming seafood

Q12d. Please indicate which of the following statements you think is most accurate

- Farmed seafood is generally better quality than wild seafood
- There is no difference in the quality of wild and farmed seafood
- Wild seafood is generally better quality than farmed seafood

Q12e. Please indicate which of the following statements you think is most accurate

- The animal welfare of farmed seafood is better than that of wild seafood
- There is no difference between the animal welfare of wild and farmed seafood
- The animal welfare of wild seafood is better than that of farmed seafood

Q13. Below are listed some specific claims that are sometimes made about fish farming (aquaculture). Please indicate the extent to which you think these claims are true using the scale provided.

	I think there is no truth in this claim			Neutral			I think this claim is completely true
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Pollutants are released from fish farms							
Fish farming has a negative effect on biodiversity, natural habitats and ecosystems							
Farmed seafood contains contaminants such as antibiotics or medicines							
Fish farms have a negative effect on the way the environment looks							
The feed used in fish farming comes from unsustainable sources							
Diseases spread from fish farms to wild fish							

Demographics

To end this survey we would like to ask you some questions about your background. Note that all answers will be completely confidential.

Education. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Local list

Work What is your main (working) situation?

- Self-employed (and I have other employees)
- Self-employed (work alone)
- Full-time employee
- Part-time employee
- Temporarily/seasonally employed
- Full-time homemaker
- Full-time student
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other

Income. What is your average combined monthly household income before tax?

- Less than € 500
- € 500 - 999
- € 1000 - 1999
- € 2000 - 2999
- € 3000 - 3999
- € 4000 - 4999
- € 5000 - 5999
- € 6000 - 6999
- € 7000 - 7999
- € 8000 - 8999

- € 9000 - 9999
- € 10000 and more

(will be adjusted to the local currencies and values)

HH1. How many people live in your household including you?

If HH1 > 1

HH2. How many of the people living in your household are under 18 years?

Locationa. Which of the following best describes your current place of residence?

- Metropolitan (at least 1 million inhabitants)
- City (100 000 – up to 1 million inhabitants)
- Large town (20 000 – 100 000 inhabitants)
- Small town
- Village
- Rural

Locationb. Which of the following best describes the distance between your residence and the coast?

- Living (more or less) on the coast
- Nearby (takes less than 30 minutes to get to the coast)
- Not so far (takes between 30 minutes and 1 hour to get to the coast)
- Not so close (takes between 1 and 2 hours to get to the coast)
- Far away (takes more than 2 hours to get to the coast)

Appendix 5 Socio-demographics of survey respondents

Place of residence

Respondents were asked two questions in relation to where they live. The first asked respondents to indicate which of a list of types of places best describes their current place of residence: metropolitan (at least 1 million inhabitants); city (100,000 – 1 million inhabitants); large town (20,000 – 100,000 inhabitants); small town; village; or rural. *Figure 61* shows the results obtained in relation to this question.

Figure 61 Percentage of each country's respondents who are resident in each of six types of habitation

The second location question asked which of a list of options best described the distance between their current residence and the coast: living (more or less) on the coast; nearby (takes less than 30 minutes to get to the coast); not so far (takes between 30 minutes and 1 hour to get to the coast); not so close (takes between 1 and 2 hours to get to the coast); far away (takes more than 2 hours to get to the coast). *Figure 62* shows the results obtained.

Figure 62 Percentage of each country's respondents who live in varying degrees of proximity to the coast

Number of people in household

Respondents were asked how many people live in their household including them. *Table 36* shows the results for all three countries.

Table 36 Number of people living in the household of the respondent by country

Number of people in household	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia
1	275	134	121

2	347	314	284
3	179	286	254
4	154	212	238
5	44	56	87
6	5	7	17
7	4	2	3
8	1	2	2
9			2
10	1	1	
12			1
20			1
Total	1006	1014	1010

Number of people under 18 in household

Those who declared that more than one person lived in their household were then asked how many of the people living in the household were under 18 years of age. Of the 2501 respondents who have more than one person in their household, 1072 have at least one household member who is under the age of 18. *Table 37* shows the number of under 18s living in the households of those respondents who have more than one person in their household.

Table 37 Number of under 18s in households composed of more than one member, by country

Number of under 18s in household	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia
0	370	585	474
1	215	184	220
2	112	94	163
3	32	17	25
4	2		6
5			1
10			1
Total	731	880	890

Responsibility for grocery shopping in the household

Respondents were asked how much of the grocery shopping they do for their household. This question also acted as a screening question; if respondents were responsible for less than half of the grocery shopping, they were not invited to complete the rest of the survey, as the aim was to gather information about seafood purchasing habits. Those who answered that they are responsible for about half or more than half of the grocery shopping proceeded to the next question.

Table 38 shows the number of respondents per country who are responsible for about half or more than half of the grocery shopping in their households. These respondents were invited to complete the full survey. *Table 39* shows these respondents broken down further by gender.

Table 38 Number of respondents in each grocery shopping category per country

Amount of grocery shopping	Country			Total
	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia	
About half	314	286	454	1054
More than half	692	728	556	1976
Total	1006	1014	1010	3030

Table 39 Number of respondents in each grocery shopping category per country, by gender

Amount of grocery shopping	Denmark			Italy			Slovenia			
	Male	Female	Prefer not to say	Male	Female	Prefer not to say	Male	Female	Other	Prefer not to say
About half	193	121		183	100	3	274	177	2	1
More than half	304	385	3	317	411		237	318	1	
Total	497	506	3	500	511	3	511	495	3	1

Responsibility for cooking in the household

Respondents were next asked how much of the cooking they do for their household. Three options were given: less than half; about half; or more than half. *Table 40* shows the results by country.

Table 40 Number of respondents in each cooking category per country

Amount of cooking	Country			Total
	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia	
Less than half	110	171	185	466
About half	246	267	294	807
More than half	650	576	531	1757
Total	1006	1014	1010	3030

Education

Respondents were asked to indicate the highest level of education they had completed. Due to the differing natures of education systems across Europe, respondents were given different options depending on which of the three sample countries they live in.

Denmark

Respondents in Denmark were offered six options for their highest level of schooling, plus the option of preferring not to disclose this information: Folkeskole (primary school); Efterskole (continuation school); Gymnasium; Erhvervsskole (vocational school); Kandidatgrad (Masters degree); and Doktorgrad (doctorate). *Table 41* provides the results for the Danish sample.

Table 41 Highest level of education for the Danish sample, shown as a number and a percentage

Level of education	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Folkeskole	102	10.14
Efterskole	32	3.18
Gymnasium	175	17.40
Erhvervsskole	358	35.59
Kandidatgrad	278	27.63
Doktorgrad	51	5.07
Prefer not to say	10	0.99
Total	1006	100

This information can be further broken down by gender, as shown in *Table 42*.

Table 42 Highest level of education for the Danish sample, by gender

Level of education	Gender		
	Male	Female	Prefer not to say
Folkeskole	55	47	
Efterskole	17	14	1
Gymnasium	100	74	1
Erhvervsskole	168	190	
Kandidatgrad	133	145	
Doktorgrad	20	31	
Prefer not to say	4	5	1
Total	497	506	3

Italy

Respondents in Italy were given 12 options for their highest level of education, plus a prefer not to say option: Nessuna scuola / scuola elementare non conclusa (no schooling / unfinished primary school); Scuola elementare con licenza (finished elementary school); Scuola media inferiore non conclusa (unfinished lower secondary school); Scuola media inferiore con licenza (finished lower secondary school with licence); Scuola media superiore non conclusa (unfinished high school); Scuola media superiore con diploma (high school with diploma); Istituto professionale non concluso (unfinished vocational institute); Istituto professionale con diploma (vocational institute with diploma); Alcuni anni di università senza conseguire la laurea (a few years of university); Laurea Triennale (Bachelor's degree); Alcuni anni di formazione post-laurea (a few years of postgraduate training); and Laurea magistrale, dottorato, ecc (Master's degree, doctorate, etc). *Table 43* shows the highest level of education of the Italian respondents, and *Table 44* shows the sample further broken down by gender.

Table 43 Highest level of education for the Italian sample, shown as a number and a percentage

Level of education	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
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Nessuna scuola / scuola elementare non conclusa	2	0.20
Scuola elementare con licenza	4	0.39
Scuola media inferiore non conclusa	8	0.79
Scuola media inferiore con licenza	71	7.00
Scuola media superiore non conclusa	38	3.75
Scuola media superiore con diploma	373	36.79
Istituto professionale non concluso	7	0.69
Istituto professionale con diploma	93	9.17
Alcuni anni di università senza conseguire la laurea	78	7.69
Laurea triennale	100	9.87
Alcuni anni di formazione post-laurea	12	1.18
Laurea magistrale, dottorato, ecc.	225	22.19
Preferisco non dirlo	3	0.30
Total	1014	100

Table 44 Highest level of education for the Italian sample, by gender

Level of education	Gender		
	Male	Female	Prefer not to say
Nessuna scuola / scuola elementare non conclusa	1		1
Scuola elementare con licenza	2	2	
Scuola media inferiore non conclusa	5	3	
Scuola media inferiore con licenza	36	35	
Scuola media superiore non conclusa	27	11	
Scuola media superiore con diploma	189	183	1
Istituto professionale non concluso	2	5	
Istituto professionale con diploma	56	36	1
Alcuni anni di università senza conseguire la laurea	34	44	
Laurea triennale	38	62	
Alcuni anni di formazione post-laurea	2	10	
Laurea magistrale, dottorato, ecc.	108	117	
Preferisco non dirlo		3	
Total	500	511	3

Slovenia

Respondents in Slovenia were also given 12 options for their highest completed level of education, plus an option to decline to say: No school or Primary incomplete; Primary school complete; Secondary school; Grammar school; Technical or Vocational; Sixth form; Some university; Associated degree; University bachelor's degree; University master's degree; Some post graduate studies; and Doctoral degree. Table 45 shows the highest level of education of the Slovenian respondents, while Table 46 shows this information broken down by gender.

Table 45 Highest level of education for the Slovenian sample, shown as a number and a percentage

Level of education	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
No school or Primary incomplete	4	0.40
Primary school complete	19	1.88
Secondary school	286	28.32
Grammar school	90	8.91
Technical or Vocational	141	13.96
Sixth form	117	11.58
Some university	44	4.36
Associated degree	37	3.66
University bachelor's degree	181	17.92
University master's degree	64	6.34
Some post graduate studies	15	1.49
Doctoral degree	8	0.79

Prefer not to say	4	0.40
Total	1010	100

Table 46 Highest level of education for the Slovenian sample, by gender

Level of education	Gender			
	Male	Female	Other	Prefer not to say
No school or Primary incomplete	4			
Primary school complete	14	5		
Secondary school	151	133	1	1
Grammar school	38	51	1	
Technical or Vocational	89	52		
Sixth form	53	63	1	
Some university	22	22		
Associated degree	15	22		
University bachelor's degree	88	93		
University master's degree	24	40		
Some post graduate studies	7	8		
Doctoral degree	5	3		
Prefer not to say	1	3		
Total	511	495	3	1

Employment

Respondents were asked about their employment status. Ten options were provided: self-employed (and I have other employees); self-employed (work alone); full-time employee; part-time employee; temporarily/seasonally employed; full-time homemaker; full-time student; unemployed; retired; and other. *Table 47* shows the number of respondents per country in each of the employment categories.

Table 47 Employment status of respondents, by country

Employment status	Country		
	Denmark	Italy	Slovenia
Self-employed (and I have other employees)	22	63	42
Self-employed (work alone)	26	71	59
Full-time employee	473	360	537
Part-time employee	105	77	50
Temporarily/seasonally employed	20	16	10
Full-time homemaker	22	95	16
Full-time student	45	38	60
Unemployed	50	92	46
Retired	222	196	176
Other	21	6	14
Total	1006	1014	1010